

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

MASTER OF DEVELOPMENT COMMUNICATION

ALJOHN T. TORRETA

**Building Community Resilience:
A Case Study on the Localization of the Early Warning System**

Thesis Adviser:

Dr. RUTH B. RODRIGUEZ
Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

9 August 2025

Permission of the classification of this academic work access is subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR policy and any contractual obligations:

Invention (I)			Yes or	No
Publication (P)			Yes or	No
Confidential (C)			Yes or	No
Free (F)			Yes or	No

Student's signature:

Thesis adviser's signature:

University Permission Page

Building Community Resilience: A Case Study on the Localization of the Early Warning System

“I hereby grant the University of the Philippines a non-exclusive, worldwide, royalty-free license to reproduce, publish and publicly distribute copies of this Academic Work in whatever form subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR policy and any contractual obligations, as well as more specific permission marking on the Title Page.”

“I specifically allow the University to:

Specifically, I grant the following rights to the University:

- a. Upload a copy of the work in the theses database of the college/school/institute/department and in any other databases available on the public internet

- b. Publish the work in the college/school/institute/department journal, both in print and electronic or digital format and online; and

- c. Give open access to the work, thus allowing “fair use” of the work in accordance with the provision of the Intellectual Property Code of the Philippines (Republic Act No. 8293), especially for teaching, scholarly and research purposes.

ALJOHN T. TORRETA

2025

Acceptance Page:

This paper prepared by **ALJOHN T. TORRETA** with the title: **Building Community Resilience: A Case Study on the Localization of the Early Warning System** is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree program.

DR. RUTH B. RODRIGUEZ

Chair, Thesis Committee

(Date)

DR. ALEXANDER G. FLOR

Member, Thesis Committee

(Date)

DR. MELINDA DELA PEÑA BANDALARIA

Member, Thesis Committee

(Date)

DR. ROBERTO B. FIGUEROA, JR.

Dean

Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

2025

Biographical Sketch

The author of this research, Mr. Aljohn T. Torreta, was born and raised in Barangay Baguingin, Tigbauan, Iloilo. He is a coffee lover, fur dad, and aspiring multimedia artist. While being a part-time student at UP Open University, he also serves as a full-time teacher at UP Visayas, teaching radio broadcasting, journalism, and other Communication courses.

Before entering the academe, the author worked for five years as a radio reporter and anchor on a commercial AM radio station in Iloilo City –DYOK Aksyon Radyo Iloilo. He specialized on Special Assignments and Investigative Reports. He also worked in the Information Unit and Capacity Building and Training Section of the Office of Civil Defense- Western Visayas at the height of COVID-19 Pandemic. He was a member of the Regional Inter-Agency Task Force Against COVID-19 and was primarily tasked for the documentation.

At present, the author is the station programmer for DYUP 102.7 FM, the educational radio station of UP Visayas. He also serves as the Project Development Assistant for Crisis Management of UPV Chancellor Clement C. Camposano.

With his interests in Disaster Risk Reduction and Management, and community broadcasting and journalism, the author intends to specialize in Disaster and Risk Communication.

Acknowledgement

To my family, life partner, colleagues, and friends, thank you for your unwavering support of my journey.

To the participants, thank you so much for the valuable insights in our dialogues and Key Informant Interviews.

To my adviser, Dr. Ruth Rodriguez, thank you so much for your guidance and understanding. I am beyond grateful for your invaluable insights. I highly appreciate your organized management and immediate responses to my inquiries.

To the members of my thesis panel, Dr. Alexander Flor and Dr. Melinda dela Peña Bandalaria, thank you so much for your comments and suggestions. Thank you for the guidance on how to make this research more specific and impactful.

To the Division of Humanities in the University of the Philippines Visayas, thank you for believing in me to pursue my graduate studies while serving in the university.

To the University of the Philippines Visayas, thank you for your financial support to me, the privilege to study with a reduced fee helped me a lot.

Lastly, this is all made possible by the grace and glory of the Almighty God

Dedication

This research is dedicated to all members of the community. We are not just passive actors in our society, we can be active citizens to contribute to the betterment of the larger community. We may have various roles and varied status but all of us can do something to achieve the common goal — for we are not just part of the community, we are the community.

This research is also dedicated to the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) practitioners. During crisis situations, it is expected that we rise above the difficulty and uncertainty. May this research help us to strengthen our Early Warning System and the overall DRRM strategy, to save more lives, to protect more properties and even the environment.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title Page	i
University Permission Page	ii
Acceptance Page	iii
Biographical Sketch	iv
Acknowledgement	v
Dedication	vi
Table of Contents	vii
List of Tables	viii-ix
List of Figures	x
ABSTRACT	
CHAPTER I: INTRODUCTION	1-6
Background of the Study	6
Statement of the Problem	6-7
Objectives of the Study	7
Significance of the Study	7-8
Scope and Limitations of the Study	8-9
Definition of Terms	9-10
CHAPTER II: REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE	11- 18
The Body of the Review	19- 21
Theoretical Framework	21-25
CHAPTER III: METHODOLOGY	
Research Design	26-27
Locale of the Study	27
Participants of the Study	27
Selection of Participants	28
Research Instrument	28
Data Gathering Procedure	28-29
Data Analysis	30-31
Ethical Considerations	31

CHAPTER IV: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Process of Communicating the Early Warning System	32-53
Most Common Hazard Communicated	53-56
Strategies in Communicating the Early Warning System	57-79
Challenges in Communicating the Early Warning System	79-95
Emerging Themes in the Localization of Early Warning System	96-115

CHAPTER V: SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary	116-119
Conclusion	119-120
Recommendations	120-123

REFERENCES	124-132
------------	---------

APPENDICES	133-210
------------	---------

List of Tables

Table 1. Profile of Participants

Table 2. Emerging Themes in the Localization of Early Warning System

Table 3. Localization of the Mechanism

Table 4. Localization of the Language

Table 5. Inclusive Early Warning System

Table 6. Strengthened Community Resilience

List of Figures

Figure 1. Framework of the Social Mobilization Continuum

Figure 2. Graphic representation on how the City Government communicates its Localized Early Warning System

Figure 3. Modified Framework of the Theory of Participatory Communication and Social Mobilization in the Communication a Localized Early Warning System

Abstract

The Philippines has been the world's most at-risk country since 2022. While disasters cannot be controlled, its negative impacts can be mitigated. One of these is through the institutionalization and operationalization of the Early Warning System (EWS). The elements of EWS namely 1.) Risk Knowledge, 2.) Monitoring and Forecasting, 3.) Dissemination and Communication, and 4.) Preparedness to respond, are of equal significance because each contributes for the safety and resilience of the community.

In the Philippines, the creation and institutionalization of the EWS in every Local Government Unit (LGU) is clearly defined in the Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act of 2010. The LGUs from the provincial down to the barangay level are obligated to operate a multi-hazard EWS to provide accurate and timely advice for immediate response, and for the information of the general public. The LGUs play a vital role in Disaster Risk Reduction and Management, this includes the creation, institutionalization, and communication of the EWS.

The Philippines having a diverse ethno-linguistic culture makes the communication of EWS also challenging. A lot of studies have explored the preparedness of the LGUs for disasters but research focusing on the communication aspect of DRRM and of EWS, is quite limited.

This research qualitatively explores the communication of EWS of the subject Local Government Unit through Key Informant Interviews to individuals who have a vital role in their communication process. The subject of this study, as the regional hub in Western Visayas and an awardee in disaster resilience, employs various strategies like the localization of its EWS to build a resilient community. The localization of the EWS is not only limited to the language used in communicating its early warning messages, it also pertains to the established mechanisms to ensure that it is responsive, inclusive, and sustainable.

It is crucial to explore and analyze the communication of the EWS to ensure that it is functional and responsive to the needs of the public. With the right and timely information, everybody will be guided as well to do the right actions.

The results of this qualitative research are vital in strengthening the operationalization and the communication of the EWS in the locality. The localization of the EWS, as an innovation, strengthens community resilience as it empowers the community. It ultimately contributes to the development and implementation of an inclusive, sustainable, and innovative DRRM and EWS.

This research is aligned with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals, specifically No. 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), No. 13 (Climate Action), and No. 16 (Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions).

Key words: DRRM, early warning system, localization, community resilience

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

The Philippines has been identified as the most at-risk country in the world since 2022 because of its hazards, exposure, vulnerability, and overall capacity (World Risk Index, n.d.). More than being a hindrance to economic growth, disasters pose a big threat to human lives, properties, and even the environment.

In a report by the Asian Development Bank (2018, p. 4), there were 23, 304 recorded deaths, 173, 319 injured individuals, and 125.62 million Filipinos who were affected by disasters from 2000 to 2016. The reported cost of damage from disasters within the said period was estimated at 19,910 (\$ million).

The most recent devastating disaster that struck the country was the Severe Tropical Storm Kristine. According to the National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council, as reported by Inquirer.net (2024), the number of reported deaths due to STS Kristine reached 146, with damage to agriculture amounting to P4.85 billion.

One of the existing interventions of the Philippine Government in Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) is the creation and establishment of an Early Warning System (EWS). According to the United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction or UNDRR (n.d.), EWS is an integrated system of hazard monitoring, forecasting and prediction, disaster risk assessment, and communication and preparedness activities systems and processes that enables individuals, communities,

government, businesses and other sectors in the community to take timely action in reducing disaster risks.

The creation and implementation of EWS has long been embedded in local governance. Based on the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act (Official Gazette, 2010, p. 23), all the Local Chief Executives (LCEs) should establish their Local Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office (LDRRMO). Part of the responsibilities of the DRRMOs from the provincial to the barangay level is to operate a multi-hazard early warning system.

The role of EWS in DRRM is vital and critical because it can save lives and properties. The early warning messages, if communicated properly can translate into early actions. However, it is important to note that not all Local Government Units (LGUs) have established their EWS. In a study by Domingo and Manajar (2018, n.d.), they emphasized that there were only 1,180 established EWS across the various levels of governance in the country in 2016. This was equivalent to 69% of the total number of LGUs from the provincial, municipal, and city levels.

At the macro level, the Philippine Government through the Office of Civil Defense (OCD) has utilized PhilAWARE, a multi-hazard early warning, hazard monitoring, and risk intelligence platform. It was developed by the Pacific Disaster Center (PDC) but was turned-over to the Philippine Government in 2021. According to Mr. Joemar Perez, the Operations Center Chief of OCD, PhilAWARE allowed them to visualize the threat of the disaster and plot its possible affected areas. It further gave them real time warning and tracking which were essential for their quick response (PDC, 2022).

Despite these efforts from the national and local governments, records show that there is still a high number of recorded casualties and impact due to disasters.

In 2022, the Office of Civil Defense (2022) recorded 164 deaths, 270 injured, and 28 missing individuals because of Tropical Cyclone Paeng. A year before that, there were 405 recorded deaths, 1, 371 injured, and 52 missing because of Tropical Cyclone Odette. Another devastating typhoon struck the country that same year leaving 214 deaths, 8 injured, and 132 missing individuals.

In a study by GSMA (2022, p. 9), they emphasized that effective EWS is a critical part of DRRM and climate change adaptation strategies. They posited that EWS can significantly reduce the mortality due to disasters when effectively implemented. This point was also emphasized by Fakhruddin et al. (2020, p.1) who believes that the ability to communicate hazard forecasts and risk information to vulnerable communities and stakeholders successfully is crucial for effective disaster preparedness and response.

A compelling case highlighting the importance of clear communication is the usage of the term 'storm surge' during the Super Typhoon Haiyan in 2013. According to Jibidi et al (2015, p. 1), the local residents did not understand the meaning of the term "storm surge". This resulted in their failure to evacuate because they underestimated the severity of the typhoon.

In the policy brief of the Senate Economic Planning Office entitled Examining the Philippines' Disaster Risk Reduction and Management System (2017, p. 8), it was also found out that one of the problems experienced in the implementation of DRRM in the country is the lack of and difficulty in accessing DRRM data/information such as disaster risks and cost, and damages.

Communicating early warnings is challenging especially that the Philippines has many ethnicities and languages. According to Philippine Statistics Authority (2023, para. 1), 26% of the Filipino reported Tagalog as their ethnicity. The other major ethnicities were Bisaya/Binisaya (14.3%), Ilocano and Cebuano (8% each), Ilonggo (7.9%), Bikol/Bicol (6.5%), Waray (3.8%), Kapampangan (3%) and Maguindanao and Pangasinan (1.9% each). The other reported local ethnicities in the country were grouped in one category reaching 18.5%.

With various ethnicities and languages, a localized Early Warning System should be institutionalized to ensure that the scientific and technical pieces of information are understood in the locality considering its nuances.

In the case of the subject of this research which is a 1st class Highly Urbanized City and is considered as the regional hub of education, culinary, religion, healthcare, tourism, culture, industry, and economy in the Western Visayas (Iloilo City Government, n.d.), its EWS has been institutionalized by the local government unit through the operationalization of its Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office (DRRMO).

The subject LGU for this research, having seven districts and 180 barangays has a dense population of 457, 626 (PSA, 2020). According to the Climate and Disaster Risk Assessment Report (2020, p. 21) of the subject LGU, “they have high susceptibility to flooding and storm surge. The other hazards that they are at risk are drought, typhoon, tsunami, earthquake, and liquefaction.”

While the concerned LGU is strengthening its capacity and capability in Disaster Risk Reduction and Management to include the operationalization of its Early Warning System, it can be noted that some areas can still be improved on. Even the

most-resilient communities continue and enhance their preparation, for no disaster is alike and the worsening of the climate change makes it more complex.

To be prepared for the mentioned hazards which can result in the occurrence of disasters, the LGU has implemented various trailblazing DRRM efforts and initiatives. These enabled them to achieve various awards and recognitions such as the Gawad KALASAG (KALamidad at Sakuna LABanan, SARiling Galing ang Kaligtasan) Seal “Beyond Compliant” from 2022 to 2023.

The said awards were given by the National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council for LGUs that exceeded the standards for the establishment and functionality of the local DRRM council and offices. Its best practices were also considered beyond the regular DRRM programs implemented by the national government.

Aside from this, the concerned LGU also won the first place in the resilience category in the Cities and Municipalities Competitiveness Index Awards 2019; this recognition was issued by the Department of Trade and Industry (Daily Guardian, 2019).

While the subject LGU has implemented various DRRM programs, it is crucial to look at the fundamentals of their DRRM, specifically the communication of its EWS. In understanding its process and identifying its challenges, a better EWS can be further developed for their better DRRM as well. This can also be shared and replicated by other LGUs if applicable to their locality.

The situation in the locality is not an isolated case, this is also the common scenario among other LGUs in the country. They have implemented various programs

but this can still be improved on. The geographical coverage of singular hazards like tsunami had improved from 2005 to 2015 however, a lot of interventions should be done on the local level especially among the remote rural communities (ASEAN, 2013; Thomson, 2019, p. 287). In a policy brief entitled Building Local Resilience Platforms for Disaster Risk Reduction by Djalante et al. (2021), they highlighted that there is an immediate need for the establishment of various multi-stakeholders platforms at the local level to bring together knowledge and resources. These are necessary and fundamental for building community resilience — this is what the concerned LGU has been trying to achieve, and the communication gap that this research explores.

Communicating EWS is not enough. With the worsening disasters, as exacerbated by climate change, there is a need to innovate the implementation and communication of the EWS. In utilizing a localized approach in operationalizing and communicating EWS, the community will be properly informed and they will have an active role in it. This enables an inclusive, innovative, and sustainable DRRM – strengthening community resilience as it empowers the community.

Statement of the Problem

There are mechanisms that institutionalize Early Warning System (EWS) among Local Government Units (LGUs) : however, the communication of EWS is not fully explored, documented, and analyzed. In the case of the subject of this research which is multi-awarded and a trailblazer in the field of DRRM, various innovative strategies have been implemented to institutionalize and operationalize their EWS. This study aims to answer the question: How does the Local Government Unit communicate its Early Warning System?

Objectives of the Study

This study aims to:

1. Describe the City Government's process of communicating its Early Warning System;
2. Identify the common hazards communicated by the City Government;
3. Determine the City Government's strategies and challenges in communicating its Early Warning System.

Significance of the Study

Despite the many efforts to institutionalize EWS, there are only a few studies in the country that explore how early warning messages are being communicated by the LGUs as an integral component of its Disaster Risk Reduction and Management.

The EWS, as a vital component of risk communication and disaster communication, is a vital element in DRRM. Furthermore, as vital facets of development communication, risk and disaster communication play a crucial role in the society especially during crisis situations and emergencies.

Since this study explores the communication of EWS among the residents, it can be the key to better understand the action, responsiveness, and appreciation of the populace to the threats and risks that they are facing.

The results of the study primarily serve as a basis and guidance for the LGU in its development of a more responsive, inclusive, and sustainable Early Warning System. The findings may also serve as a basis in the recalibration of its Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) Campaigns and may provide valuable insights for policymakers and practitioners in DRRM for the institution of new policies or mechanisms related to it.

Ultimately, this research empowers communities to serve not as mere beneficiaries or target audience but as active members of the community. Their participation in the development and communication of the early warning system is vital to ensure that it is responsive, inclusive, and sustainable – empowering the community as it strengthens their community resilience.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

While recognizing the broader context of Early Warning System involving the Provincial Government, this study will primarily focus on the City Government due to the nuances in the area and scope of their governance jurisdiction, and the operationalization of their respective DRRM Office.

The study focused on the communication process of the City Government of their Early Warning System through the City Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office (CDRRMO) and the Public Information Office (PIO). The study was conducted over a period of one year, encompassing the formulation of the research proposal to the final defense. The research resources that have been utilized in this study includes books, research papers, electronic publications, and news articles.

This study focused on the key personnel of the City Government that have significant roles in the creation and implementation of EWS. Other individuals from other sectors were also considered (e.g., punong barangay, media, and government agency) to determine and document their role in the communication of EWS in the locality in collaboration with the City Government.

Definition of Terms

Disaster - in this research, disaster refer to the disruption in the community due to the hazards, and its vulnerabilities and risks which could result in the loss of lives and/or properties

Early Warning System – in this research, early warning system refers to the integrated system implemented by the Local Government Unit in communicating hazards, vulnerabilities, risks, and disasters among others to the general public, it is comprised of the following:

- a) Risk knowledge
- b) Observation and Forecasting
- c) Dissemination and Communication
- d) Preparedness to respond

Early warning message - in this research, it pertains to any information related to the early warning system

Risk Knowledge – in this research, risk knowledge pertains to the understanding of the public to the hazards, threats, and risks in their locality and their vulnerability to it

Observation and Forecasting - in this research, it refers to the monitoring, analysis, and forecasting of hazards

Dissemination and Communication – in this research, it corresponds to the communication of early warning messages to the public

Preparedness to response – in this research, it refers to the capability of the individual or community to respond to disasters

Localization – in this research, it refers to the processing and/or translating early warning messages in the local language and the establishment of mechanisms in the locality to communicate it

Contextualization – in this research, it means considering the socio, economic, and cultural dynamics of the locality in communicating the early warning messages

Community Resilience - in this research, it pertains to the ability of the community to resist, withstand, adapt to, and recover from the adverse effects of a hazard

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Background

An effective Early Warning System can save lives, properties, and even the environment. The early warnings are not just communicated to disseminate information but to translate these into early actions. According to the United Nations

Office of Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR, n.d.), Early Warning System (EWS) is an integrated system of hazard monitoring, forecasting and prediction, disaster risk assessment, communication and preparedness activities systems and processes that enables individuals, communities, government, businesses and others to take timely action to reduce disaster risks in advance of hazardous events. Moreover, it emphasized that EWS is and should be science-based and people-centered.

Based on the United Nations International Strategy for Disaster Reduction Terminology on Disaster Risk Reduction (2009, p. 5), EWS is defined as a set of capacities needed to generate and disseminate timely and meaningful warning information to enable individuals, communities and organizations threatened by a hazard to prepare and to act appropriately and in sufficient time to reduce the possibility of harm or loss.

Last 2016, the UN updated this working definition. On a resolution passed in the United National General Assembly, EWS has been considered as an integrated system of hazard monitoring, forecasting and prediction, disaster risk assessment, communication and preparedness activities systems and processes that enable individuals, communities, governments, businesses and others to take timely action to reduce disaster risks in advance of hazardous events (UN, 2016, p. 17).

The vital role of EWS in disaster risk reduction has long been realized from the local to the international levels. The United Nations, through the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) launched the Early Warnings For All: The UN Global Early Warning Initiative for the Implementation of Climate Adaptation Executive Action Plan 2023-2027 (2022). This project aims that all people on Earth are covered by early warning systems by 2027.

UN Secretary-General António Guterres pointed out that it is vital to invest equally in early warnings as part of strengthening the adaptation and resilience (WMO, 2022, p. 1). Moreover, Guterres added that the information that allows us to anticipate storms and other disasters are necessary for us to respond accordingly as it can save lives. It also has vast financial benefits. In the estimates of the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO, 2021, p.5), families could benefit seven dollars (\$7) and avoid losses in every dollar (\$1) invested in anticipatory action where the early warning system plays a vital role.

In one of the meetings on the UN Climate Change Conference- United Arab Emirates in 2023, it was reported that over 98% of crisis financing is still arranged after the impact of a disaster (COP28, n.d.). This has been happening despite reliable scientific information to predict them.

At present, the UN is encouraging countries to not only develop and implement EWS but to also advocate the use of multi-hazard EWS as a response to the dynamics and complexities of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management.

As its name implies, MHEWS address several hazards and/or impacts of similar or different type in contexts where hazardous events may occur along, simultaneously, cascadingly or cumulatively over time, as well as its potential interrelated effects (UN, n.d.).

The World Meteorological Organization reported that there are 101 countries in the world which have their own MHEWS (2023); this is more than half of the world's countries. While this has significantly improved as compared to previous years, it was noted that the effectiveness of early warnings is affected by the limited risk knowledge. There were also gaps in observations and forecasting specifically the existence of fully operational warning and alerting services. Specifically, a lot of countries are yet to

have satisfactory monitoring systems. Moreover, they also lack real-time data and necessary tools for their forecasters to identify and accurately forecast their threats.

At the regional level, there were also challenges in the implementation of the Early Warning System. According to ASEAN (2022, p. 14), they observed that there was a difficulty in the accessibility of the public to EWS, missing linkages between the EWS in the national and regional levels, and even a lag in communicating early warnings.

The Philippines is one of the countries to have a functional MHEWS. According to UNDRR (2023), the Philippines has a multi-hazard early warning, hazard monitoring and risk intelligence platform called PhilAWARE system which was developed by the Pacific Disaster Center (PDC). This system was turned-over to the Office of Civil Defense (OCD) in 2021 and it was reported to have contributed significantly to managing disasters like Typhoon Nalgae (with local name Paeng) which struck the country in 2022.

While this project has great contributions, its implementation was limited to OCD's Operation Center alone, on the national level.

Under the Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act of 2010, the OCD shall have the primary mission of administering a comprehensive national civil defense and disaster risk reduction and management program by providing leadership in the continuous development of strategic and systematic approaches as well as measures to reduce the vulnerabilities and risks to hazards and manage the consequences of disasters (Official Gazette, 2010)

In addition, the Administrator of the OCD is also tasked as the Executive Director of the National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council, an inter-agency council that is empowered with policy-making, coordination, integration, supervision, and monitoring and evaluation functions with regards to DRRM.

The NDRRMC or National Council, headed by the Department of National Defense (DND) has four (4) vice chairpersons namely:

- 1) Secretary of the Department of the Interior and Local Government, the Vice Chairperson for Disaster Preparedness;
- 2) Secretary of the Department of Social Welfare and Development, the Vice Chairperson for Disaster Response;
- 3) Secretary of the Department of Science and Technology, the Vice Chairperson for Disaster Prevention and Mitigation; and
- 4) Director-General of the National Economic and Development Authority, the Vice Chairperson for Disaster Rehabilitation and Recovery.

The National Council has its regional counterpart up until the municipal, city, and barangay levels. Its counterpart in the barangay level is called Barangay Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Committee.

One salient point in the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act (Official Gazette, 2010) that is specific to EWS is stipulated in Section 12.c which states that part of the functions of the Local Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Officers is to “operate a multi-hazard early warning system linked to disaster risk reduction to provide accurate and timely advice to national or local emergency response organizations to the public...”

The establishment and improvement of the EWS falls under the Disaster Prevention and Mitigation Thematic Area, specifically under the responsibility of the Department of Science and Technology (DOST) based on the National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Plan 2020-2030 (NDRRMC, 2020). While the task of establishing the EWS is under the DOST, the monitoring of it is assigned to another National Government Agency (NGA), the Department of Interior and Local Government (DILG).

As the vice chairperson for Disaster Preparedness Thematic Area, the DILG published the Local Government Unit Disaster Preparedness Manual for City and Municipal LGUs under their Operations L1sto Program. On the Typhoon Edition v3 of the said manual (p. 134), the DILG identified EWS as one of the projects and activities for disaster preparedness. However, the said manual is silent on how the LGUs should communicate their EWS, it only sets the guidelines in monitoring alerts and reviewing hazard and risk maps, the supplies needed in communicating these early warnings, and the installation of signage as stated in the DENR-DILG-DND-DPWH-DOST Joint Memorandum Circular No. 2014-01 among others.

The creation and utilization of EWS is already embedded in local governance however, not everybody has fully realized this.

In a study by Aguirre-Ayerbe et al (2020, p. 9), they noted that MHEWS was well developed and operational but it was found out that there was a lower level of implementation to the Dissemination and Communication aspect of EWS. Reportedly, 48% of the responses expressed that this element was partially developed, specifically on the establishment of communication systems and equipment and it being

operationalized. Another raised concern centered on the effectiveness of the communicated early warnings to prompt action by target groups.

One of the best illustrations where EWS is best tested and realized is the case of Super Typhoon Haiyan (with local name Yolanda). In a study by Ocon and Neussner (2015, p. 10) titled “Assessing early warning efforts for Typhoon Haiyan in Leyte”, they pointed out that there was a lack of effective dissemination and communication of warning warnings. Some of the identified issues were the following:

- 1.) No clear communication of critical information to those who needed it
- 2.) The public were unaware or did not understand the severity of the hazard

In addition, having an established EWS is one thing but its consistent implementation is another matter of concern. In the paper entitled “Community-Based Early Warning System: Learning from Saint Bernard, Southern Leyte” by the Assistance and Cooperation for Community Resilience and Development Inc., they claimed that the technical capacity of the concerned personnel in the mentioned locality was still considerably limited. Aside from this, maintaining several hazard-specific EWS to account for multiple hazards frequently affecting the towns was also complex (ACCORD, 2020, p.5).

Another area of concern in the operationalization of EWS is the communication of it among the Persons with Disabilities (PWDs). In a policy brief published by Oscar M. Lopez Center for Climate Change Adaptation and Disaster Risk Management Foundation, Inc. (2024, p. 3), it was found out that critical information like early warnings is not yet accessible to the deaf who have unique communication needs in the Philippines.

With the increasing hazards as exacerbated by climate change, an effective, inclusive, and innovative EWS is necessary to protect lives and properties. EWS should be inclusive to ensure that no one is left behind, most especially the vulnerable sectors.

While there are some constraints in the communication of EWS, some Local Government Units have started to effectively use risk communication in the context of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management. In the case of the Municipality of Caramoan in Camarines Sur, they primarily anchored on and put emphasis on building community awareness, involvement, and resilience.

In the study Risk Communication in Disaster-Prone Areas in Caramoan, Camarines Sur, Philippines by Fullero et al. (2024, p. 780), they found out that the Information, Education, and Communication materials of the said LGU such as flyers, leaflets, and posters were updated and localized so that all the barangays can use it. In addition, face-to-face chat or conversation with neighbors was the most preferred risk communication strategy before, during, and after the onslaught of a disaster.

Communicating EWS is not just about the message, every element of the communication process is integral such as the technical capacity of the sender to deliver reliable, accurate, and fast information using the medium that is the most accessible and convenient among the target audience.

With these experiences and realities amidst the need to establish a multi-hazard EWS, the UN is advocating for a people-centered approach. In doing so, individuals who are threatened by hazards are empowered to act accordingly and appropriately. This can be achieved if the early warning messages are timely, inclusive, clear, and are coming from a trusted source. People-centered EWS is

focused on the empowerment of the public for them to act on time and in an appropriate manner to mitigate the potential negative impact of any disaster (UNDRR, 2023, p. 21).

In the report *People Centered Early Warning Systems: Learning from National Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies* by the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (2020), they presented several countries that observed and implemented a people-centered early warning system, one of these is Vanuatu in the Pacific Region.

Reportedly, the National Society in the said country, in collaboration with CARE International and the National and Local Governments worked together to establish community-based disaster risk management committees. In partnership with the Red Cross Climate Centre, Vanuatu Red Cross and Vanuatu Met Service, they also developed early warning messages that provide visual and impact descriptions of the different cyclone categories for the communities (2020, p. 32).

In the case of Malawi, their Early Warning System is incorporated in the Malawi Red Cross' standard community-based disaster risk management and climate change adaptation programming. Reportedly, early warning messages are shared through cell phones, megaphones, community meetings, door-to-door, community radios and even through the playing of radio jingles using multiple languages (IFRC, 2020, p. 39).

For the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (2020), people-centered approaches in EWS are essential to ensure that the information and warnings reach the most vulnerable communities, for them to later on act on them as well.

People-centered EWS has four major elements namely: Risk Knowledge, Monitoring & Warning Service, Dissemination & Communication, and Response Capability (UNISDR, 2006).

This was later on updated and considered as the four pillars of the Early Warning Systems for All Initiative. EWS is now composed of 1.) Disaster Risk Knowledge, 2.) Observations and Forecasting 3.) Dissemination & Communication, and 4.) Preparedness & Response (UN Global Early Warning Initiative for the Implementation of Climate Adaptation, 2023, p. 6).

Communication and information play a vital role in all of these areas, and in all of its processes.

The Body of the Review

Effective and efficient communication is fundamental and critical especially during disasters. One area that specializes in this is risk communication.

As pointed out by Fakhruddin et al. (2020, p. 1), risk communication is a critical component in disaster risk reduction, especially in designing and implementing the Early Warning System.

According to the World Health Organization (n.d.), risk communication is the real-time exchange of information, advice and opinions between experts or officials

and people who face a hazard or threat to their survival, health, or economic or social wellbeing.

In the context of disaster risk communication, Stewart (2024, p. 12) posits that it offers a coherent continuum of practice that progresses from seeing at-risk communities as a problem to be overcome through education. Apart from this, it cultivates these concerned communities as a resource to be motivated and persuaded, ultimately empowering them to achieve long-term and strategic disaster risk reduction goals.

The role of communication in DRRM is significant in all levels of governance. On the national scale, the Philippine Government through the Presidential Communications Office committed to improve their communication protocols. According to PNA (2024), this is to ensure a faster and more efficient information dissemination during disasters and other calamities.

One of the many ways to improve disaster risk communication is the localization and translation of data to the local dialects and languages. With the devastating experience with STS Kristine, Civil Defense Administrator Usec. Ariel Nepomuceno admitted that there is a gap in the local dissemination of important information during disasters. The official said that it is practical and meaningful to translate important information to local dialects and languages because it is more understandable to the public. In addition, it is not only beneficial to the communities but also among LGUs (OCD, n.d.).

In the “Early Warning for Early Action: Toward More Behaviorally Informed Early Warning Systems” by Akerkar et al (2020, pp. 10-11), an effective People-

Centered Early Warning System is considered to have incorporated local knowledge and expertise.

Akerkar et al (2020, p. 11) further highlighted the translation of highly technical scientific and professional language and information used by Early Warning practitioners to a practical and contextually relevant information. They posited that it is critical for facilitating local action of the end users or target audience.

Even before the call to develop and implement MHEWS, some organizations have been actively promoting the localization of EWS, the best illustration of this is the project by Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) GmbH entitled “Local Flood Early Warning System” or LFEWS (2012). LFEWS established and institutionalized collaborations between the national meteorological authority, local government units, and the communities to develop a robust and cost-effective local early warning system.

On the other hand, the contextualization of the early warnings is being done by providing impact-based forecasts and advisories. In 2023, the Department of Science and Technology – Philippine Atmospheric Geophysical, Astronomical Services Administration (DOST-PAGASA) launched the multi-hazard impact-based forecasting and early warning system (PAGASA, 2023). With a budget of 22 million USD, this project aims to develop a nationwide system and implement a pro-active government approach that is focused on the preventive aspects of disaster management. The approach of this project is more on forecasting what the weather “will do” instead of what it “will be”.

While there is some research that explores the communication of early warning messages as a tool for DRRM, this is yet to be determined in the locale of this study.

Theoretical Framework

This research is primarily anchored in the frameworks of participatory communication and social mobilization. The theory of participatory communication illustrates the participation of various sectors in the communication of the Early Warning System in the locality. On the other hand, the social mobilization framework explains the relationship of these sectors to achieve a common goal — to build community resilience. These frameworks highlight the importance of all who are involved in the communication process, emphasizing that they are not just the receivers or end-users but are active members who contribute to its development and implementation.

According to Jacobson et al., (1999), as cited by Prakash Subedi (2022), participatory communication is about involving all the stakeholders in the development activity. The ultimate goal of it is to achieve social change and to empower them. Tufle and Mefalopulos (2009) further emphasized that communication, in participatory communication, should take place among all parties who are affected to ensure that everybody has the similar opportunity to influence the outcome of their initiative. Moreover, it is part of the whole process from the beginning to the end of it.

The salient principles of Participatory Communication are (1) *Dialogue*, (2) *Voice*, (3) *Liberating Pedagogy*, and (4) *Action-Reflection-Action*.

According to Tufle and Mefalopulos (2009), educator Paulo Freire defined *dialogue* as “the encounter between men in order to name the world...” Generally, it pertains to defining what the problem is.

On the other hand, *voice* is attributed to the marginalized group for them to articulate their concerns, to define their problems, to formulate solutions, and to act on them (Tufle and Mefalopulos, 2009).

Liberating Pedagogy, as a principle of participatory communication employs dialogic (two-way) communication, and for it to take place, there must be someone or something that will serve as the “catalyst” to articulate the process. The “catalyst” would articulate a *dialogue* which would result in a collective problem identification and the implementation of the solution (Freire, 1970; Tufle and Mefalopulos, 2009). Moreover, the *liberating pedagogy* will occur if anchored on these four pillars; love, humility, faith, and hope. This would ultimately result in action-oriented awareness raising.

Lastly is the *Action-Reflection-Action*. Participatory communication would take place if there is an integration of action after the dialogue and reflection. The ultimate goal is to act collectively to address or respond to the identified problem.

A complementary framework to the theory of participatory communication is the concept of social mobilization. According to McKee (1992), as cited by Velasco et al. (1999), social mobilization is the process of bringing together all feasible and practical inter-sectoral and social allies to raise people’s awareness of the demand for a particular development program. Furthermore, he noted that this to assist in the delivery of resources and services as well as strengthen the participation of the community for its sustainability and their self-reliance.

Social mobilization has strategic elements and can be classified through inputs, process, outcomes, and impact (Ling, 1992; Ling, 2007). Reportedly, the inputs are the ones that serve as the partners in social mobilization such as the politicians,

corporations, religious leaders, Non Governmental Organizations, People’s Organization, Civil Society Organizations, women’s groups, and cooperatives among others. On the other hand, the process pertains to information collection/analysis, advocacy, marketing, media outreach, technical assistance, training, communication and education, community organization, behavior/action, and alliance building. Next is the outcome which can transcend from the individual or family, the “grassroots”, the community, the bureau level, and the national or international levels. In the context of policy making, outcomes should be a supportive framework for decision making and resource allocation to empower the communities to act (Ling, 2009). At the grassroots level, Ling (2009) emphasized that the outcomes should have people’s active participation in achieving their desired development. Lastly, for the impact, some of its reported elements pertain to increased choice, enhanced skills and capacities, improved information flow and meaningful interaction between societal levels, and improved individual and community ability to manage efforts to improve their own situation.

Figure 1.

Framework of Social Mobilization Continuum

Note. Adapted from *Communication and Social Marketing*, by Ling (1991) as cited by Velasco et al.,(1999). UP Open University

Chapter III

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized a qualitative case study design to explore how the City Government communicates its Early Warning System. Generally, qualitative research explores and understands the meaning individuals or groups attribute to a social or human problem. It is largely an investigative process where the researcher gradually makes sense of a social phenomenon by contrasting, comparing, replicating, cataloguing and classifying the object of study (Miles & Huberman, 1984; Cresswell, 2009).

The subject of this research is a compelling ‘case’ for this specific study because it is a multi-awarded Local Government Unit in the context of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management. In addition, it is considered as the regional hub in Western Visayas. Its role in the region and its dynamics make it a worthy subject for this research. .

Case study, as a specific research design, is an in-depth study of a particular phenomenon or real-life scenario (Yin, 2009). Cresswell (2009) emphasized that it involved a detailed description of the setting or individuals, followed by analysis of the data to explore and understand its themes or issues. According to Yin (2018), case study research answers the “how” and “why” questions. Case study research is also best utilized if the researcher also has little or no control over the behavioral events surrounding the research subject and if its focus is more on exploring a contemporary phenomena.

Since the primary objective of this study is to explore how the City Government communicates its Early Warning System, a qualitative case study is the most suited approach. It investigates the City Government’s communication process of its EWS to understand how it works.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in a Highly Urbanized City (HUC) in Western Visayas. Iloilo City. According to the Philippines Statistics Authority (2020), the subject Local Government Unit for this research has seven districts and 180 barangays has a dense population of 457,626 as of 1st quarter this year.

As the center of trade and commerce in the region, most of the regional offices of the National Government Agencies are located in the locality. Major economic, academic, and transportation infrastructures are also constructed in this HUC.

Participants of the Study

The participants in the KII are the individuals who have essential roles in the development and communication of the Early Warning System. The following are the identified participants for KII:

- 1) The Head of the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office
- 2) The Head of the Information and Publication Office
- 3) The President of the Liga ng mga Barangay or his/her representative
- 4) The Iloilo City DILG officer (DILG as the chairperson of the preparedness thematic area in DRRM)
- 5) The president of the City Press Corps
- 6) Representative of Academe (partner academic institution of the City Government and a member as well of the City DRRM Council)

Selection of the Participants

The participants for this research were identified using purposive selection. This is primarily based on the relationship of their work to the City Government's communication of its Early Warning System. The heads of the concerned offices were the top priority to serve as participants.

Research Instrument

An Interview Guide was developed to ensure the flow of discussion and relevance of information in the Key Informants Interview. This was also validated through an expert review to ensure that the research questions and the study's objectives were aligned and covered.

The Interview Guide was divided into three parts: 1.) Profile of the participant and the role of his/her/their institution in the communication of EWS 2.) Strategies Employed in the Communication of EWS and 3.) Challenges Experienced in the City Government's communication of its EWS.

Data Gathering Procedures

The proponent conducted the key informant interviews to the pre-identified participants. These were done separately and in the most convenient approach and time of the participants.

The researcher initially prepared a letter addressed to the Local Chief Executive to inform him about the research and ask for his approval for the conduct of the interview to the head or representative of the City Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office and the Public Information Office.

Separate letters were also sent to the DILG, the Office of the President of the Liga ng mga Barangay, the president of the City Hall Press Corps, and the representative of the partner academic institution.

Before the data collection, the participants were informed about the research, its purpose, and its methods, assuring them of the confidentiality of data recorded.

The CDRRMO, PIO, and Office of the Liga ng mga Barangay were the primary sources of information in the City Government's communication of its Early Warning System. The CDRRMO and IPO are the specific offices/units of the Local Government

Unit that communicates its Early Warning System. On the other hand, the Office of the President of the Liga ng mga Barangay is part of the communication and implementation of the EWS of the mentioned LGU.

As a triangulation method, key informant interviews were also conducted to the representatives of DILG, City Press Corps, and the partner academic institution to validate the pieces of information which were initially gathered. The DILG is the vice-chairperson in the Preparedness Thematic Area of the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management and as mandated under the Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act, part of its role is to monitor the communication of early warnings of the LGUs when there is a hazard or disaster.

The recordings from these interviews were transcribed and organized to facilitate coding and thematic analysis. The English translation of the specific information from these interviews were also provided.

Data Analysis

The data from the KIIs were analyzed based on the emerging themes. According to Dawadi (2020), thematic analysis is a qualitative research method that is used to systematically organize and analyze complex data sets. Braun & Clarke's (2006) six-step thematic analysis was also employed to organize the data, this consist of the following: (1) becoming familiar with the data, (2) generating initial codes, (3) identifying themes, (4) reviewing themes, (5) defining themes, (6) writing the narrative.

Moreover, inductive analysis was observed in analyzing the data from the KII.

In inductive analysis, the themes emerge through the data itself. According to Brown & Clarc (2006); Dawadi (2020), the data is coded in inductive analysis without

trying to fit the themes into a pre-existing coding scheme or the researcher's preconceptions about the research.

Ethical Considerations

An informed consent was considered for the Key Informants Interview. The participants verbally agreed to an informed consent before the data gathering. The participants were also fully informed about the research, its purpose, and the methods used. The primary considerations were the following:

- 1.) Voluntary participation of the participants and respondents
- 2.) Confidentiality of the data of the participants and the data that they will give

Moreover, the potential risks such as emotional distress to the participants were also considered. Aside from ensuring that the venue for the interview is well-lighted, well-ventilated, and generally safe, the researcher also carefully prepared the guide questions considering the sensitive nature of the topic. In addition, the participants were advised to inform the researcher if they are not comfortable answering the question or continuing the interview as it may trigger a traumatic experience or cause emotional distress.

Research Propositions

The study aims to test the following propositions:

Proposition 1: The City Government localizes the communication of its Early Warning System

Proposition 2: The localization of Early Warning System empowers the various stakeholders by building their community resilience

CHAPTER IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The participants for this study were individuals whose functions are related to the City Government's communication of its Early Warning System. The following table shows the profile of the participants who were part of the key informant interviews.

Table 1.

Profile of participants in the Key Informants Interview

Participants	Office	Designation	Age	Civil	Role in the
--------------	--------	-------------	-----	-------	-------------

				Status	Communication of EWS
1	Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office	City Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Officer Department Head 2 (overall head of the office)	48	Single	Their office is the overall in charge of the DRRM activities
2	Public Information Office	Supervising Administrative Officer (overall head of the office)	47	Married	Their office is the in-charge in the Information, Communication, and Education (IEC) Campaigns of the city government
3	Liga ng mga Barangay/ Association of Barangay Captains	Punong barangay	48		They serve as the bridge in the communication of EWS from the city government to their barangay
4	DILG	City Director	53	Married	They monitor the preparedness of the LGU in times of disasters
5	City Hall Press Corps	President/ Reporter	50	Married	They help in the information dissemination of EWS
6	Academic Institution	Academic Assessment Head/Safety Officer/	34	Married	They are part of the CDRRM Council

		DRRM Coordinator			
--	--	---------------------	--	--	--

Based on Table 1, the participants' ages ranged from 34 to 50 and the majority of them are married. All of them have a direct role in the communication of EWS in the city as it is part of their role, functions, and responsibilities.

Communicating the Early Warning System

The communication of early warning messages comes from the City Government, through the City Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office and the Public Information Office, to the public through the use of various channels such as their official communication platforms on social media, messaging applications, and even partner institutions like the media, academe, punong barangay, and other sectors.

1.) Source of information

The City Government, through the CDRRMO and PIO, is the source of early warning messages that are being communicated to the public. They utilize various channels in their information dissemination. Aside from information generated by their

office, they also utilize other information from other sources like the Philippine Atmospheric, Geophysical, and Astronomical Services Administration (PAGASA) and the Philippine Institute of Volcanology and Seismology (PHIVOLCS) among others.

So it is the role of the OpCen to communicate the risk pero ang channel where you will throw all those information ginapaagi kay BDRRMS namon kay at the barangay level, ang gina-obra namon sir, di ba RA 10121 says that barangay should organize its own Barangay DRRM Committee. So in every barangay, nag-establish man kami sang barangay Operation Center. So from the city level, amo na siya manaog ina siya deretso sa barangay.

(Participant 1, personal communication, April 4, 2025)

English Translation: So it is the role of the OpCen (Operations Center of the CDRRMO) to communicate the risk and the channel that we use to throw those information is through the Barangay Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Section (BDRRMS) because it is on the barangay level. Under the RA 10121, every barangay should establish their own Barangay OpCen. So from the city level, it reaches down to the barangay.

This was supported by the head of the PIO and expressed that they tailor-fit the information dissemination depending on the medium that they are using. Some of the messages that they disseminate are in the form of an announcement, press release, and media advisory among others.

Yes for information dissemination for example pwede siya namon himuon nga daw public advisory or just an announcement. We can make it into a press release or a media advisory for sila na mismo, sa media directly namon nga ginahaboy.

(Participant 2, personal communication, April 8, 2025)

English Translation: Yes for the information dissemination, we can make a public advisory or an announcement. We can also make a press release or a media advisory so that the media can directly disseminate it.

The media also play a vital role in the communication of early warning messages. The president of the City Hall Press Corps (2025) emphasized that the media is the partner of the City Government in communicating the early warnings:

Oftentimes, always gid na nga gina-channel nila sa amon ang ila nga communication pakadto sa amon mga networks tapos ginahaboy man ina namon sa amon nga mga networks ang information nga ginahatag nila sa amon galing kay te bal-an mo naman subong iya with the advent sang social media sometimes una nila post sa ila nga page kag ipasa sa amon for wider dissemination.

(Participant 5, personal communication, April 22, 2025)

English Translation: Oftentimes, they use us to channel the information. We course through that information to our own network. You know, at present, in the advent of social media, sometimes, we post it first in their own social media account then share it to us for a wider information dissemination.

This information dissemination ultimately reached the barangays to the punong barangays. There are existing mechanisms in place to disseminate the early warnings from the CDRRMO until the barangay level.

Bali ano si City, si OpCen, Operation Center na ga-send sang message sa akon diri tapos ako, ang message na halin nana sa ila. Tapos ako tungod kay may pito nga kagawad, may group chat kami, i-send ko na sa council nga group chat. Tapos si kagawad in-charge, ang kada zone na bal-an sir, may group chat mana, i-send yaman na didto.

(Participant 3, personal communication, April 8, 2025)

English Translation: The City Government through the Operations Center sends a message to me, that message is also being shared to my 7 barangay kagawads, in our group chat. Every barangay kagawad has his/her assigned zone, and that kagawad also shares that message to their own group chat in that area.

After the early warnings are disseminated in the barangay, it is the barangay officials who communicate these messages to their populace using the most appropriate medium. Aside from using interpersonal communication by conducting home visitation, they are also using the new media (social messaging application) and the non-mainstream and popular medium like the use of the Public Address System (PAS).

“May ara kami pito ka kagawad...tapos ang kagawad namon sir may partner na nga BHW (Barangay Health Worker), amo na ang upod niya nga nagalibot, kag si BHW

amo na siya, sa mga recordings, sila na ang naga-obra.” (Participant 3, personal communication, April 8, 2025)

English Translation: We have seven barangay kagawads...each kagawad has his/her partner BHW (Barangay Health Worker), together they go around (to disseminate the information), they also do the recordings.

Since the information from the city is being cascaded down to the barangays and eventually to the households, the public has become more knowledgeable about the hazards that they are facing. In addition, they are also guided on what to do should a need arise.

Dako gid sir ang nabulig sina, ang pumuluyo namon aware nga mag-abot ang amo sina, bal-an nila kon ang ila himuon kag ang mga kagawad mismo kag BHW bal-an na nila ang ila nga himuon kumbaga mahapos na bala sa ila, mahapos man para sa akon, te kay may PA (Public Address) System man ini na mabudlay nga kumbaga ara na sa sistema namon nga kon mag-abot ang amo ni nga kalamidad, bal-an na namon kon ang himuon kag bal-an na kon diin makadto. Amo na bala, bal-an namon dayon kon ano ang amon obligasyon maglab-ot sa evacuation center.

(Participant 3, personal communication, April 8, 2025)

English Translation: It really helped us a lot, the residents have become aware and knowledgeable about this and that, they know what to do for the kagawads and BHWs (Barangay Health Workers). It is easier for me and for them because we have the PA System. We already have a system if a disaster

strikes. We know what to do and where to go. Like in the evacuation centers, we already know our responsibilities there if ever an incident will transpire.

With the early warnings disseminated up until the last mile, the public is informed and guided to take the right actions as well to mitigate or prevent the possible negative impacts of a disaster.

To illustrate this point, the participant who is the punong barangay expressed that the residents have become more vigilant and alert in the monitoring of the level of water in the creek especially when there are typhoons. If the water keeps on increasing and approaching the danger level, the residents inform their barangay officials about it and even observe preemptive evacuation to protect themselves.

“Sila mismo bal-an nila, sila mismo nagaarak ang message sa kagawad kag sa BHW, sa akon gaarak na iya, “kap gataas ang tubig”, sige mahambal ko na nga mabakwit na, kadto na diri”. Ga-monitor man kami sa ila sir.”

(Participant 3, personal communication, April 8, 2025)

English Translation: They send us a lot of messages, even among the barangay kagawads and the BHWs, I myself have experienced that. They would inform me that the level of the water is increasing. That is the time that I tell them to evacuate and go here. We monitor them as well.

2.) Processing of information

The City Government does not just disseminate any generated information or share the information cascaded by monitoring and forecasting institutions, they process it by analyzing its content and tailor-fitting it to what is applicable,

understandable, and relatable to the public, considering the socio, economic, cultural, and even educational status of the populace. In addition, the City Government has employed a resident meteorologist to ensure that the pieces of information that they gathered and received are grounded on Science and analyzed by an expert. This makes the scientific and technical information objective and specific to the locality.

Okay sigé, so risk communication tama? If we have to communicate the risk, again ma build on ka sa risk knowledge mo right? but to analyze the data, may bagyo ka di ba, they have the scientific information from PAGASA, Manila Observatory, other available data from the different websites. Once they have that, it is the role of the OpCen to analyze what does it mean for the barangays of Iloilo City. So kon amo ni kabaskog, amo ni ang time nga maabot, diri nga direction, ano nga mga barangays ang high risk? So it is the role of the OpCen to communicate the risk...

(Participant 1, personal communication, April 4, 2025)

English Translation: In risk communication, when we communicate the risk, it should be built on from the risk knowledge. But we need to analyze the data. For example, there is a typhoon, they have scientific information from PAGASA, Manila Observatory, and other available data from other websites. Once they have it, it is the role of the OpCen to analyze what it means for the barangays in Iloilo City.

The participant from the PIO also shared that they process the specific type of information depending on the prevailing situation:

Yes sa risks, for now be taas ang heat index so we have to tell the people ano ang dapat nila himuon, tuman ka init, tuman ka paang. Things like that and also dengue, ang mga infectious diseases especially nga summer, pag-abot sa tingulan ano naman ang ila atubangon, so mga amo sina

(Participant 2, personal communication, April 8, 2025)

English Translation: yes for the risks, for example at present the heat index is high, so we tell the public the things that they should do. Other examples are for dengue, or infectious diseases during summer or rainy days

For the media, the members of the City Hall Press Corps underwent various training so that the information dissemination will be easier.

Before sina may ara kami gin-conduct nga daw training with CDRRMO, ginistoryahan namon ang mga protocol sa declaration sang suspension sang face to face classes, option nga kon madeclare ang eskwelahan ukon indi. Ginistoryahan namon with CDRRMO with Mr Darwin Papa, then nag-follow na ina dayon ang EO ni mayor kon paano ina i-execute. So since may prior na kami nga training dira so ang communication na lang is constant feeding of data kay te nabal-an naman namon kon ano ang himuon. Kon amo ni ka Celsius ang heat index ano ang himuon so easy na lang ang pagcommunicate namon kay prior dira nakatraining kami, naka seminar kami. So ang pag-cascade sang information sige-sige na. Nahatag na sa amon ang information.

(Participant 5, personal communication, April 22, 2025)

English Translation: the CDRRMO conducted a training with us before, in that training we discussed the protocols in the declaration of the suspension of face-to-face classes, there we discussed the options if there will be a declaration of class suspensions. We discuss that with CDRRMO through Mr. Darwin Papa, then followed by an EO of the mayor as to how it will be executed. Since we already have prior training about it, we just need constant feeding of data because we already know what to do. For example, if this is the number in Celsius of the heat index, what should we do? Communicating it is easy because we have a training about it, we had a seminar. The communication and cascading of information is also constant. We just give the information.

3.) Non-Linear Communication

It is also not just about the Iloilo City Government sending these early warning messages to the public through their partner institutions and sectors, they also enabled a mechanism where their partners are also empowered to communicate to them these pieces of information. This illustrates a non-linear model of communication in disseminating information related to the Early Warning System.

...kag indi lang na sir si CDRRMO ang ginahaboyan namon pati si CSWDO si pulis, kaisa si pulis nagapamangkot man ina, nagamonitor mana, nagalibot sa amon diri sa mga affected areas tapos mamangkot ina sa amon kap. Te ang ano na lang namon para isa na lang, kon ano ang nahimo namon, kon ano ang ginhaboy ni kagawad nga data sa akon kag mga pictures, haboy ko na sa CDRRMO, kag CSWDO, sa BFP, kag sa pulis

(Participant 3, personal communication, April 8, 2025)

English Translation: It is not only the CDRRMO which we share these pieces of information with, we also report it to the CSWDO, and even among the police because they are also asking. Whatever information that my kagawad is giving me, I am also reporting it to personnel of the CDRRMO, CSWDO, BFP, and even the police officers.

The participant representing the partner academic institution of the city government emphasized that there is an open line between them and the CDRRMO, as well as the barangays adjacent to where their university is situated:

“We could call them (CDRRMO), and then ang amon nga barangay upod mana sir mo, we could call them kon ano ang hazard dira...”(Participant 6, Personal Communication, April 29, 2025)

English Translation: “We call them (CDRRMO) and also the barangay officials. We call them if there is a hazard in our area...”

This open communication line is also evident between the CDRRMO and the media.

...kon may ara te gina-feed namon halimbawa may mga instances sang nagligad nga grabe ang hangin, natumba ang nga kahoy kay te indi man sa tanan nga oras makita nila no so kon kay te bal-an dasig magpadala sa mga media outlets so kami mismo nagapadala snag information, natumba nga poste, nabugto nga kuryente mga kahoy. Kami mismo nagabulig kami share sang information sa ila kag sometimes, kon i-ano mo bala imatch mo sa ila data

mahambal sila nga tapos na pero kon kaisa maoverlook na so gabulig kami sa pagremind sa ila which is good man kay partnership man kita...

(Participant 5, personal communication, April 22, 2025)

English Translation: When there is information, we also feed it to them (CDRRMO). For example, there were instances before that there were strong winds which resulted in an uprooted tree. Since they cannot monitor it at all times and some opt to share this information among the media, so we just send it also to them. Other examples include fallen posts, dangling electrical wires, and others. We help them by sharing these pieces of information. Sometimes, they will say that it is already managed but sometimes it gets overlooked. So we remind them about it, this is good because we have a partnership.

The CDRRMO has received various reports and information from the barangay about their situation, especially about the hazards present or imminent in their area. The medium they utilized to disseminate early warnings to the barangays are the same platforms that they may use to report or share any information:

...email, same thing kon ano ang channel. Sa radyo or kis-a sa text messages or Viber group with matching pictures kay nagapangayo bulig. Nakibot gani ko sa area ni kap Barbie, sa diin na area ni kap, diri sa Nabitasan. Te kay ginapadala mana namon kay mayor. Mayor amo ni ang mga ginabaha, amo ni ang mga pictures. The following day, ginapada-an ni city engineers. So nagbalik si kap Barbie, siling ya maam thank you gid kay ginpalab-ot niyo. So bisan sila kaisa nagaka-amazae kay dasig ang action ni city government. So we encourage them that you report. We share information, indi ka magsiling

nga wala man ina gihapon kay you can never tell. Lantawa kay gin-aksyonan ni Mayor kundi lipay sila may drainage sila... nami pa gid ang role of the media, ang baha diri sa Calubijan, nabatian ko lang sa radyo. Tapos sige ka istorya nagtawag ko kap, ano to kap kay nag-anticipate na ko, siling ko wala ka dayon nagreport. Te gi-ubrahan namon sulat, hatag kay city engineer sa DPWH...

(Participant 1, personal communication, April 4, 2025)

English Translation: ...through emails, and the same channels that we use such as radio, text messaging or Viber and with matching photos. I was shocked before in the area of Punong Barangay Barbie (Aroza) in Nabitasan, Lapaz. We shared it to the mayor as a flooded area. The next day the mayor sent city engineers to manage the situation...The role of the media is also vital. There was this instance in Calubihan, Jaro, I just heard it over the radio. I called the punong barangay regarding it...

4.) Use of social media and non-mainstream popular medium

The Iloilo City Government utilizes both the social media and non-mainstream popular medium in the communication of early warning messages. The top social media platforms that they use are Facebook and Viber. For the non-mainstream popular medium, printed materials, Public Address System (PAS) and *rikorida* are also used. The PAS is installed in the barangays. On the other hand, *rikorida* is a culturally relevant method in the locality that integrates the PAS in a vehicle to disseminate the information to the barangays on mobile

I think on Viber but I am not yet connected right now we have this council of different HEIs same on the different councils because may council man sa anti-smoking...on that Viber they usually send the memos and if it has conditional things that you need to process with the administrators then it is up to them to decide but most likely on the memos coming from the CDRRMO through Viber and I think social media they also have social media posting...

(Participant 6, personal communication, April 29, 2025)

English Translation: They send the early warnings usually on Viber, we have this council of different HEIs in the locality like a council for anti-smoking. They usually send the memorandum or additional information through that Viber. It is up to the administrators to decide on it. I think they also post on social media..."

Aside from the use of new media technology, traditional media like through the use of printed materials is also observed.

"...we have printed (materials) so ginahatag ta sa barangay, sa mga schools, kag government agencies. And ang IEC namon through our Facebook page, the Iloilo City Government and of course gina-tap namon ang amon partners sa media"(Participant 2, personal communication, April 8, 2025)

English Translation: we have printed (materials) that we share in the barangays, schools, and government agencies. We also post our IEC materials in our Facebook page, the Iloilo City Government and through our media partners.

This was also evident in the practice of the CDRRMO. Magno (2025) emphasized that as long as traditional media, new media, and mediated communication like the use of handheld radio are prevalent, early warnings could reach up to the last mile of the barangays:

Ang tricky na prime dira is from us going to the barangays. As long as naga-work ang Viber, ang radyo, ang handheld radios, ang mga Messenger nila nga groups, makalab-ot gid ina up to the last mile kay amo ina siya ang mga barangays naton, they have this Public Address System nga once mabaton nila, ang iba na gina-announce nila. So amo ina siya, amo pa ina ang gusto namon i-establish man. We want to see kon how active ang mga kabarangayan nga once they receive that information, makalab-ot.

(Participant 1, personal communication, April 4, 2025)

English Translation: The tricky part is how the information is cascaded in the barangays. As long as our Viber groups are working, our handheld radios, and the Messenger groups, these pieces of information will reach up to the last mile in the barangays. They also have their Public Address System (PSA). When they reach this information, they announce it through their PSA.

The significance of popular and non-mainstream media was also highlighted by the other participants. Reportedly, a lot of punong barangays have expressed that the most effective way to communicate in their respective barangays is still the use of 'rikorida' and Public Address System (PSA):

ako okay lang, I like it better nga in Hiligaynon, like pareho sang 'rikorida', we do it in Hiligaynon kay di ba the common tao can relate, maintindihan nila... yes

we do the script for rikorida, for sunog. For example, si Bureau of Fire, tapos during dengue time, tapos sa mga tyempo nga wala sang tubig...when we had the BNEO (Barangay Newly Elected Officials) last year, ang pinaka-effective daw sa ila is ang “rikorida” or ang Public Address System so ang mga materials namon nga ginpanghatag sa ila ginagamit nila, maglawag-lawag.

(Participant 2, personal communication, April 8, 2025)

English Translation: we use the Hiligaynon language in our ‘rikorida’ because it is easier to understand. For example, we provide the script for fire safety in our collaboration with the Bureau of Fire Protection. When there is a water shortage or surge of dengue, we also do it. When we had our Barangay Newly Elected Officials (BNEO) last year, the most effective means to communicate in the barangay was through “rikorida” or Public Address System (PSA). So we just provide them with materials which they use to announce in the PSA.

The use of popular and non-mainstream media is indeed prevalent in the locality. The participant who is also a punong barangay confirmed that they are using popular and non-mainstream platforms such as the trumpa or Public Address System. Reportedly, the majority of the their land area can be reached by their PSA:

before nga mag-abot kon ano mana da, kinahanglan mapaguwa kana da sang imo nga communication sa mga tawo te ang amon diri may ari kami diri nga trumpa, ginapaandar na siya namon. Amo na gani sir nagapangayo gid ako sa city nga para daw , indi para nga kinahanglan kami mahambal, mahambal man kami sa microphone para sa trumpa kag gusto ko ya tani ya, kapila na ko maghambal kay maam Donna ina bala nga padala kamo sa kada barangay kay

total istandardize niyo malang, ipadala niyo kon ano ang dapat nga ihambal kay total patukaron malang ina sa amon nga trampa nga gina-ano na be ang tanan gina-aligmat...kaisa gani sa megaphone nagalibot ang patrol (sang barangay). (Participant 3, personal communication, April 8, 2025)

English Translation: when there is a hazard, we communicate to the public through our “trumpa” as part of our Public Address System. What I ask from the CDRRMO through maam Donna (Magno), is for them to standardize the material so that we will just play it. There is no need for us to announce, we can just play it to alert them...we also use megaphones to remind the public, it roamed around the barangay.

To better understand the process how the City Government communicates its Early Warning System, the researcher developed the illustration below:

Figure 2.

Graphic representation on how the Local Government Unit communicates its Early Warning System.

Note. Own Work

The City Government, as the institution responsible to operationalize and communicate its Early Warning System, utilizes the scientific and technical information from partner institutions like Governmental Organizations such as PAGASA , PHIVOLCS, and MGB. Their other sources of information includes the other Monitoring Institutions like Manila Observatory and the online weather application Windy, the community itself through the various sectors, and others.

These pieces of information are being processed by the City Government through the Operations Center of the City Disaster Risk Reduction and Management. With their own analysis with the aid of their in-house expert meteorologist, they collaborate with the Public Information Office for its information dissemination using various channels.

The major channels that the City Government utilizes are the (1) traditional media, specifically television, radio, and printed publications like newsletter, guidebook, and comics; (2) new media through their respective official Facebook accounts; (3) non-mainstream media such as the Public Address System and rikorida installed and utilized in the barangays; (4) Interpersonal Communication during dialogues, meetings, and general assemblies in the barangay; and (5) Mediated Communication which includes the use of text messaging, call, and the two-way radio communication.

These early warnings are being communicated using the mentioned channels whichever is applicable, faster, and convenient. Redundancy of the information

dissemination is not an issue instead encouraged to ensure that the message is delivered to the audience.

For the audience, the early warnings are primarily communicated to the general public but the crafting of the message that is specific for certain sectors are also practiced. The ultimate goal of the early warnings are to inform and guide the public, encouraging them to also do early action to mitigate the possible negative impact of an imminent disaster.

In this framework and as reflected in the practice in the locality, the audience, regardless of their sector, contributes and actively participates in the implementation of their EWS. They are not just beneficiaries or end-users of this vital information because they also serve as the source of information of the Iloilo City Government in the development, implementation, and communication of their EWS.

Applying the Theory of Participatory Communication on this framework, the City Government through the ICDRRMO and PIO serve as the *catalyst*. They are the ones initiating and leading the implementation of the localization of the EWS through their various strategies. The dialogue took place in the various interactions of the City Government to the public, and the various sectors to empower them in building and strengthening their community resilience. The voice is the actual voices of these sectors such as the barangay officials, academe, media, CSO, and business sector among others who express their concern and support in the implementation of the program. On the other hand, the Liberating Pedagogy is achieved through the CDRRMO and PIO. As pointed out, they serve as the *catalysts* which facilitates the dialogue and tries to respond to the identified problem through collaboration and active engagement. Ultimately, the Action-Reflection-Action transpires if the public and the various sectors are part of the communication of the early warnings and are influenced

by it to do early action, mitigating the possible negative impact of any imminent disaster.

Moreover, incorporating the framework of social mobilization makes the communication process of the City Government more inclusive and sustainable. The inputs in the communication of a localized EWS are the various stakeholders involved in the development and implementation of the EWS such as the barangay officials, media, academe, CSO, women's group, PWDs, business group, and LGBTQ+ among others. All of these stakeholders do not just receive the early warnings and disseminate to their respective communities, they also have an active role in the overall process. They can also share information and feedback to the City Government to strengthen their EWS. The process primarily centers on information collection/analysis, communication and education, and community organization. These processes are done by the City Government to and through the various stakeholders.

An analogy to support this illustration is the conduct of the UnRISK training to the various stakeholders. The Unpacking Resilience Inclusive and Innovative Strategies for Knowledge or UnRISK is a capacity building activity to empower the various stakeholders by letting them understand the basic concepts of DRRM and enabling them to conduct their own risk assessment to their locality. Part of their activities is to identify what they can do and what needs to be done to decrease their risks. Using the same analogy, the outcome is the updated risk assessments and recalibrated DRRM plans and strategies of the barangay to strengthen their community resilience. Ultimately, the impact of using this communication process is realized if the early warnings are translated into early actions.

To further illustrate this point is this analogy: if the barangay officials have determined in their risk assessment that their primary hazard is flooding, and they properly and periodically inform and educate the public about it, the affected community will have anticipatory actions whenever there is an imminent threat of the rising level of the water. The preemptive evacuation would result in the lesser probability of the occurrence of casualty, injured individuals, and damage to properties.

It is also worth noting that the communication process of the City Government of its EWS is cyclical and multi-modal. While the City Government is the *catalyst* of the actions, they employ non-linear communication. The various stakeholders to include the community do not just receive early warnings, they may also share or report any similar or related information to the City Government for their appropriate action if warranted. Various channels are also in-place ensuring the reporting mechanism, the community may send this directly to the City Government or through their sectoral representation. The City Government also utilizes a multi-modal approach in communicating EWS. Redundancy of information dissemination is not an issue, instead it is encouraged to ensure that the message is received by the target audience.

Common Communicated Hazards

Most of the participants expressed that the City Government communicates hazards especially before the onslaught of a disaster. However, it is worth noting that the most common hazards being communicated are only focused on natural hazards like typhoons, flooding, earthquake, and volcanic eruption among others. According to UNDRR (n.d.) hazards can be a process, phenomenon, or human activity that may cause loss of life, injury, or other health impacts as well as damage to property, social

and economic disruption or degradation of the environment. It can also be caused by natural factors, anthropogenic or human-induced, or socionatural in origin.

“Ang common related to typhoon sa flooding, sunog kay amo ini siya ang mga hazards nga gina-atubang kag frequent, kag amo ni ang sa init.” (Participant 1, personal communication, April 4, 2025)

English Translation: The common (early warnings) that we are communicating are related to typhoons, flooding, and fire. These are the hazards that we frequently face, and of course at present, we have extreme heat.

The participant from the PIO also expressed that the most common hazard that they are communicating is about heat index:

Yes sa risks, for now be taas ang heat index so we have to tell the people ano ang dapat nila himuon, tuman ka init, tuman ka paang. Things like that and also dengue, ang mga infectious diseases especially nga summer, pag-abot sa tingulan ano naman ang ila atubangon, so mga amo sina...

(Participant 2, personal communication, April 8, 2025)

English Translation: For the risks, right now we have the heat index (because of the extreme heat). So we have to tell the people what they should do. It is so hot and humid. We also have dengue, or any infectious diseases especially this summer or during the rainy season.

For the punong barangays, the primary hazard that they are communicating with is related to typhoons.

“Bagyo lang gid, baha wala. Tapos ayawan pana kami kaisa...ano ang iya sang city nga early advisory nga ginahambal.” (Participant 3, personal communication, April 8, 2025)

English Translation: Only for typhoons, there is none for flooding. We have some difficulties in the audio of the advisory that the city is sharing to us.

Another participant highlighted that the most common hazard communicated by the City Government is related to the typhoon but he emphasized that there are also other hazards which can be attributed to typhoons such as flooding.

ang for baha, ang sa mga low-lying areas pero we do it generally para nga daw massive ang information dissemination nga malab-ot sa public...once nga may bagyo activated ang ila nga Emergency Response Center, so kami on our own, nagakadto kami dira sometime nagatambay kami agud nga mag ano dira magmonitor para nga dasig lang ang delivery sang information.

(Participant 6, personal communication, April 22, 2025)

English Translation: The most common is for flooding, it is for the low-lying areas and we communicate it massively so that it will reach the public...once there is a typhoon, the Emergency Response Center is also activated. We go there to monitor and to easily deliver any information.

Only one participant noted that anthropogenic activity like the conduct of rallies, can also be a possible hazard. While it is not an actual hazard, it can become as such due to the possible eventualities that may occur.

During summer, heat index tapos kun may typhoon warning usually they have that one ah indi taman mahambal nga si CDRRMO ang nagahambal sang pag may rally, si mayor naman na, pero we share since wala man siya hazard but part na siya sa management.

(Participant 6, personal communication, April 29, 2025)

English Translation: During summer, they are communicating heat index, there is also for typhoons. We cannot really say that CDRRMO has a say when there are rallies because there is no actual hazard but it can be considered for its management.

It is vital that the public is aware of the hazards that are present or can occur in their area for them to prepare for it. If they are familiar and knowledgeable about it, they can do necessary measures to lessen their overall risk. Moreover, it is equally important that the Local Government Unit not only emphasize natural hazards in their IEC Campaigns but also focus on human-induced hazards. In doing so, all possible eventualities are being covered to strengthen further the community resilience.

Strategies in the Communication of EWS

The strategies that the City Government employs in the communication of the Early Warning System is explored through its various elements:

A. Risk Knowledge

In this research, risk knowledge pertains to the understanding of the public to the hazards, threats, and risks in their locality and their vulnerability to it. This is measured through risk assessments conducted to, with, and by the community.

Last year, the City Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office implemented the project “UnRISK” (Unpacking Resilience Inclusive and Innovative Strategies for Knowledge Building Capacity Building). The said activity empowers the various stakeholders to understand the risks in their areas using systems thinking and applying foresight and future design thinking in risk analysis (ICDRRMO, 2024).

In the said training, the concepts of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management, and Climate Change Adaptation among others were discussed. In addition, the participants conducted hazard analysis and risk assessment in their localities under the supervision of the CDRRMO and other experts.

The CDRRMO explained that they are employing a participatory approach to come up with a solid risk assessment through key informant interviews and focus group discussions. Moreover, they are implementing it through a sectoral approach and as of April this year, the CDRRMO has implemented this to the barangay officials, media, and the academe. Through this activity, the various stakeholders are the one who will identify the risks in their areas as well as the actions that can be taken to manage it and mitigate its possible negative impacts.

UnRISK gani, part na siya ang risk assessment. Ang title sadto UnRISK. So subong nag-evolve na siya, we do UnRISK sessions para sa academe, next namon nga ubrahon is sa private sector kay what we realize is that “we cannot work with these sectors kon ang imo partner wala nakaintindi kon ano ang risks”. So even with the documents in the UNDRR, it all starts with understanding the risks. So that is why na-conceptualize ina siya ang UnRISK. (Participant 1, personal communication, April 4, 2025)

English Translation: The project UnRISK is part of risk assessment. We are holding the UnRISK session per sector and our next target after the academe is the business sector. We cannot work with these sectors if they do not understand their risks. So with all the documents in the UNDRR, it all starts with understanding the risks that is why we have conceptualized their project UnRISK.

Aside from their experts and invited resource personnel, the CDRRMO also partnered with the City DILG in the conduct of the said program among the barangay officials. As the National Government Agency responsible for the supervision of the Local Government Units, the role of DILG especially in disaster preparedness is vital in building and strengthening community resilience.

Sa Boracay kami sina nag-obra, gin-assist namon ang barangay together with CDRRMO, nag-obra sila sang DRRM plan which ultimately nagamit ni CDRRMO ang data kay sila man ang naga-facilitate... plus ang data gani nga

gin-obra ni barangay sa risk assessment nila magamit man ni CDRRMO sa response.

(Participant 4, personal communication, April 2, 2025)

English Translation: We conducted that in Boracay, we assisted the barangay together with the CDRRMO in the creation of their DRRM plan. The data from these can be utilized by the CDRRMO since they are the facilitators, they can utilize the data from the barangay risk assessment in the response.

For the City Hall Press Corps which was one of the sectors who underwent the said training, its president expressed that what he liked about the training was the discussion about the true meanings of the various terminologies.

The president of the City Hall Press Corps admitted that the majority of the media practitioners are still confused and because of this, some fail to deliver the right information. He also extended his appreciation to the CDRRMO for the conduct of the said training because they were made aware of the precise word or terminology in reporting.

Some of the concepts discussed were the following: hazard (katalagman), exposure (kahayag), vulnerability (kahuyang), risk (risgo), and disaster (kalalat-an). These concepts in DRRM were discussed and explained using its translation or equivalence in the local language. In doing so, the media practitioners are able to better understand the concept and the easier it will be for the audience to understand it as well because they are able to relate to it.

Ang pagpaintindi sa matuod-tuod nga kahulugan sang tagsa-tagsa nga term nga ginagamit, kon ano ang kahayag. Confused pa kami mo , indi lang ako, all

of us were confused kon diin ang kahayag, kon diin ang mga amo na bala. Siling ko amo gali ini dapat. Oftentimes we fail to delivery sang information kay kita mismo sometimes may confusion pa sa ginagamit nga term. Which is good na subong kay ginabuligan na kita sang LGU nga mas makagamit kita sang precise nga term sa pagdeliver sa publiko.

(Participant 4, personal communication, April 22, 2025)

English Translation: What I like in that training is the discussion about the true meaning of the words like 'kahayag'. Some of us are also confused, not only me, and oftentimes we fail to deliver the information because there is still confusion in the usage of the words. Oftentimes we fail to deliver the information because we ourselves have confusion on the usage of the words. The Local Government Unit is helping us to be more precise in reporting.

The participant representing the punong barangays also underscored the importance of the project UnRISK. However, she expressed that it can still be simplified because it was still too technical.

Importante man pero ang na-mean ko bala tani ginaspimple lang example ko lang ang sa Boracay tam-an ka technical . Nag-attend kami sa Takas para sa paghimo sang BDRRM Plan, biskan ano ka training sa Boracay...karun gin-coaching nila kami sa Takas ginsimplify pa gid nila sa Takas amo to ya ang pinakanami ...ang nag-attend to kapitan, kagawad kag treasurer...

(Participant 3, personal communication, April 8, 2025)

English Translation: It is important but I think they can make it more simple because the activity in Boracay was too technical. There was an instance where we attended training for the BDRRM Plan in Barangay Tacas, Jaro. They coached us there using a simplified approach, that was great.

Aside from conducting training, the CDRRMO also organized webinars to various sectors in the community. Their personnel primarily served as resource persons for this activity but they also taped with other experts like from the academe and media to also share their best practices in DRRM and CCA.

“Webinars kay kaisa na naga go-online kami kon dasigay kay it is quite difficult na nga tipunon sa isa ka lugar so we utilize the online platform like Zoom.”
(Participant 1, personal communication, April 4, 2025)

English Translation: We organize webinars. We go online because sometimes it is hard to gather the public. We use the online platform Zoom for it.

These webinars were called KABALAKA Zoom webinars wherein the media practitioners also served as the resource persons.

Actually ako personally oftentimes pila na ko kajoin sa KABALAKA Zoom webinar and training sila kag ginashare ko lang ang role sang media . Gusto ko ipaintindi ang role sa publiko nga media is not enemy ang media is partner sa information dissemination...

(Participant 5, personal communication, April 22, 2025)

English Translation: I often join the KABALAKA Zoom webinar and training. In there, I just share the role of the media. I want to explain to them the important role of the media, we are not your enemy, we are your partner in information dissemination.

B. Monitoring Services

The CDRRMO has installed monitoring devices in various parts in the locality. Reportedly, there were devices installed to monitor the heat index, rainfall, water level, and the intensity of earthquakes.

In partnership with Manila Observatory and Shell AWS, the CDRRMO is monitoring the heat index in the four areas in the city namely: Shell Diversion, Shell Ungka, Shell Villa Arevalo, and Shell Lapuz.

In the case of the river monitoring sensor installed in various areas in the city, the CDRRMO expressed that they installed an alert system that automatically plays a recorded audio to alert the residents. When a certain water level is reached, the device automatically plays an audio recording that corresponds to the prescribed action depending on the situation.

That particular nga sensor is in Calubihan, ang determination of the flood height sila na ang naghatag because you cannot develop alert signals without discussing that sa public. Kay kon indi nila maintindihan how can they take actions. That is the purpose of the early warning system for you to warn the people earlier so that they can also take early action. So ang pag-determine sina sila, halin sa ila, upod sa ila... amo to gani ang istorya ko, “maam nagtunog na siya, nagtunog na”. Naga-inform sila...

(Participant 1, personal communication, April 4, 2025)

English Translation: That particular sensor in Calubihan, the determination of the flood height there is by the residents there. You cannot develop alert signals without discussing it with the locals. When the device was alerted, they informed us about it.

For the monitoring of earthquakes and rainfall, one of the devices of the City Government was installed in a partner academic institution which has a standing Memorandum of Agreement with the city government. Aside from housing the early warning device, they also serve as the official evacuation center of the coastal barangays adjacent to their university.

“...we are the home of one of the sensors of the CDRRMO so we home their early warning device in the school, and we are also an official evacuation center in Arevalo...it is for earthquakes and has a rain gauge” (Participant 6, personal communication, April 29, 2025)

Aside from these technologies and hardware devices, the CDRRMO also has an assigned coordinator per district in the city. These personnel are in-charge for monitoring the barangays under their jurisdiction in the context of DRRM. Aside from cascading information from the city down to the barangay levels, the barangay officials also course through them any information for the reporting.

...ang kada district may focal person so may ano na sila, may chat group. So whatever happens, “maam, grabe na gid ang balod diri”.So gapadala na sila sang videos sang coastal tapos ginahaboy na sang amon barangay (focal) diri sa OpCen or sa viber may ara man kami natawag man nga virtual OpCen. So

si OpCen na diri kag tanan nga mga barangays namon, whatever information nga nagather sa barangay amo man ina ang ginapost namon or ang ginahaboy kanday mayor kag sa council members.

(Participant 1, personal communication, April 4, 2025)

English Translation: Every district has a focal person (coordinator), they also have their own chat groups. So for example there are strong waves, they share videos about it through our focal persons. Then it is shared in the OpCen and ultimately reported to the mayor and the council members.

The deployment of DRRM coordinators per district is also attested by Hosenilla (2025):

“Ma-message kami sa Balantang namon nga focal person sang disaster...”

(Participant 3, personal communication, April 8, 2025)

English Translation: We just message the focal person for the disaster assigned to us, she is situated in (Barangay) Balantang.

C. Dissemination and Communication

The City Government utilizes various strategies to disseminate the early warning messages.

1. Simplification and Contextualization

The role of PAGASA is to look at the hazard profile of a certain area but it is the LGU to tell its constituents about its impact to them.

nga it is the role of PAGASA to look at the hazard profile but it is the role of the Local Government Unit to tell the people what does it mean for you. Te kon taga coastal ka, te evacuate kamo, pre-emptive, daw amo bala ina... sometimes di ba ginapost lang nila pero it should include information on what you will do because this is the status right now of the typhoon or whatever. Remember si Mt. Kanlaon paglupok niya, nagsala tana, kitaon ang fumes di ba. Tapos paglupok sala na tanan ma-post, siling ko Darwin paguwa na kamo sang warning kay damo ang nagasala-sala. What does it mean for us? Ang information nga volcanic ash, te daw indi kita malab-ot? So ano ang pinakaposible, malab-ot kita? So kay may in-house meteorologist kami, what we did kay we let him study the wind direction. Tapos they came up with this narrative, so part of the narrative "given the current wind direction, volcanic ash is expected to fall in the north and northeast direction". Siling ko de**** kamo, north and northeast sa diin ina? Kay kon ako ordinaryo nga tawo, duuuu, indi mo ko ma-warn, indo ko mag-take action kay wala ko kaintindi. Liwata! Pagliwat nila, diin ang areas? "Maam somewhere sa Miagao...gin-studihan nila liwat. Abi mo pagka gab-i, pagpaguwa ni PHIVOLCS sang information, amo gid to nga mga areas kondi nalipay kami. Oh di ba, that is what we are saying to communicate the risk. Simplify it so that ordinary people can understand it and take early action kay naintindihan ko ang ginpalab-ot mo...pareho na sang una di ba, siya man ina ang nag-istorya. When you explain, ano ina siya kabaskog si 120 km/h nga hangin haw? Di bala, so ano ang palahambingan nila. Daw parehos bala kon magsakay ka sa jeep, ang speed ya sina 120 so amo ina kabaskog ang hangin then people will understand, ah amo ina siya

kabaskog...Give an example nga related sa day-to-day nga experience sang tawo then they will come to understand.

(Participant 1, personal communication, April 4, 2025)

English Translation: It is PAGASA's role to look at the hazard profile but it is the role of the Local Government Unit to tell the people what it means for them. For example they are from the coastal community, thus they must evacuate or do preemptive evacuation...sometimes they just post it but it should include the information about what to do because of the status of the typhoon or whatever for example. Remember the eruption of Mt. Kanlaon, everybody was worried because the fumes were visible. After the eruption, everybody wanted to post on social media. Then I instructed Darwin (CDRRMO personnel) to release a warning about it. What does it mean for us? Since there was volcanic ash, will it reach us? Fortunately we have an in-house meteorologist so he studied the wind direction. In their narrative report, they first stated that the volcanic ash will go in the north and northeast direction. I told them to specify the location because ordinary citizens will not understand it...Simplify it so that ordinary people can understand it and take early action, they were able to understand what you communicated...When you explain how strong is 120 km/h wind? We can compare it when we ride a jeepney. In doing this, the people will understand it... Give an example that is related to their day-to-day experience so that they will better understand it.

Another strategy employed by the City Government is the contextualization of the information. Aside from reporting the hazard experienced by the locality, it also

provides additional information or explanation about what to do to mitigate its negative impact.

...for now be taas ang heat index so we have to tell the people ano ang dapat nila himuon, tuman ka init, tuman ka paang. Things like that and also dengue, ang mga infectious diseases especially nga summer, pag-abot sa tingulan ano naman ang ila atubangon, so mga amo sina...

(Participant 2, personal communication, April 8, 2025)

English Translation: For example, presently the heat index is high so we tell the people what they should do because it is so hot and humid. Things like that and also dengue, other infectious diseases especially during summer, also during rainy season, things like that.

This strategy enables the public to better understand the hazards and risks that they are facing. Franco (2025) also pointed out the need to provide illustrations or additional information in reporting a particular hazard so that the public will easily understand it.

“...mas madali maintidihan sang publiko plus updan mo ina sang concrete example mahambala ka abi nga storm surge, ano gid ina nag storm surge. Mahambal ka abi nga kon may storm surge, ano kadako ang halit niya maintidihan sang tawo...(J. Franco, personal communication, April 22, 2025)

English Translation: The public will easily understand it because you provided concrete examples. For example when you say storm surge, what does storm

surge mean? You can say that storm surge is like this and it can impact us up to this extent. In doing so, it will be understood by the public.

This was also observed by the partner academic institution. Reportedly, the CDRRMO utilizes a certain code to categorize the situation and the necessary actions for it. Moreover, these are cascaded in the local DRRMs in the barangay so that everybody will understand it and eventually use it.

May strategy sila sir nga ginaobra nga daw gina hambal siya nga code, may code nga ginagamit especially sa typhoon kag rain level may code na sila nga ginagamit dsi CDRRMO kag ginatudlo na nila sa local nga DRRM sa barangay. For example ginahambal nila sa responder, amo na ini siya ang sitwasyon, may ara nana nga automatic nga ubrahon nila pero kon sa community medyo dira ang struggle...

(Participant 6, personal communication, April 29, 2025)

English Translation: They (CDRRMO) have a strategy sir like for example they have specific codes being utilized when there is a typhoon. Every rain level has a corresponding code and this is being taught in the local DRRM in the barangays. For example they were told that this is already the situation, there is an automatic equivalency of what they should do. However, the struggle is on its implementation in the community.

2. Localization

Localization is the processing of the information so that the public will better understand it. Some of these localization efforts that the Iloilo City Government

employs are the translation of the concept to the local language, the provision of an explanation or additional information to provide more context, and the simplification of the information dissemination among others.

“...we do understand that critical info like this, kinahanglan naka-Hiligaynon so sometimes kon indi kami mag-post sang written, kon nagafollow ka sa Facebook namun...salang to ang video para maintindihan ang Hiligaynon or ang OpCen staff ang nagatudlo-tudlo.” (Participant 1, personal communication, April 4, 2025)

English Translation: we do understand that critical information like this should be in Hiligaynon. Sometimes in our Facebook postings we post videos in Hiligaynon language. There were instances where our staff were the ones explaining it using the Hiligaynon language.

The localization of the language through translation is also observed and employed by the media. The participant representing the City Hall Press Corps explained that there is a need to do it so that the public will easily understand the scientific and technical information:

kay syempre para hapos maintindihan sang mga pumuluyo kay very technical abi pati gani ako kon kaisa no. We have to learn kon ano ang Hiligaynon sina nga mga terms kay it is so technical, so ano ang hazards sa Hiligaynon, ano ang vulnerability, ano ang exposure, ano ang mga capacities, What do we call them in Hiligaynon? So para hapos magrasp bala sang ordinary nga tawo. Ano nga katalagman ang gina-atubang mo? Ah katalagman gali ina, so mabal-an

niya eh nga amo gali ina. Easily ma-identify niya...kun kinahangan nga English te English pero kon pwede mo siya translate into Hiligaynon nga indi man maguba ang meaning niya, pwede siya matranslate.

(Participant 5, personal communication, April 22, 2025)

English Translation: Of course it will be easily understood by the public because sometimes it is very technical. I even have some issues with it sometimes. We have to learn the Hiligaynon of the terms because it is so technical for example hazards, vulnerability, exposure, and capability. What do we call them in Hiligaynon? It is really for the easy understanding of the public. What hazards are they facing? So they will know that that is the hazard, they can easily identify it...If it is needed to be in g English then we use English but if it can be translated in Hiligaynon without destroying its meaning, it can really be done.

The PIO also highlighted the usage of the local language Hiligaynon in information dissemination:

te very important gid ya nag Hiligaynon kay aton gid iya lenguahe kag maintindihan snag tawo sometimes kun ay Tagalog bala nga ginadownload sa amon especially from the national government kay usually garequest sila mo nga paki-share, ginatranslate ina namon John kay te kita nga daan nabudlayan kita magTagalog di ba so mas hapos kon i-translate in Hiligaynon

(Participant 2, personal communication, April 8, 2025)

English Translation: It is important to communicate it in Hiligaynon because that is the language that we use and easily understood by the public. Sometimes there are materials that we are downloading from the national government because they ask us to help them in its dissemination. What we usually do is translate it in Hiligaynon.

The localization of the communication of the early warnings is also not limited to the language, it also pertains to the institutionalization of a localized mechanism to disseminate the information, and this is through the Barangay Information Officers (BIO).

...because of our partnerships with the City DRRMC kag syempre naga-evolve man ang PIO mo, sa functions, so indi siya enough eh nga walo lang katawo kay te aside from your regular job tapos ma amo kapa na, ma DRR work kapa. So medyo mabudlay that is why together with the CDRRMO, gina-ano namon tani nga the barangays will also step up so may ara kami actually ginhimo nga kon magsubmit ang barangay sang ila BDRRM plan, ibutang nila to nga there is an executive order designating sang Barangay Public Information Office which gin-obra man ina sang 180 barangays. So this year ang target namon i-mobilize ang 180 ka mga barangays, BIO tawag namon, Barangay Information Officers...in all 180 barangays per the document that we got from the CDRRMO. So amo ina nag gina-target namon mobilize this year kay para nga mapuslan sila for the community works

(Participant 2, personal communication, April 8,2025)

English Translation: because of our partnerships with the City DRRMC and of course because our functions in the PIO are also evolving, our number of personnel is not enough. We are only eight here and aside from our regular job, we also do DRRM work. It is kind of difficult that is why we partner with the CDRRMO, we are collaborating with the barangays. For example in their BDRRM plan, they should indicate there an executive order designating a Barangay Information Officer. This was complied with by all 180 barangays. This year we are targeting to mobilize all of them for community work.

In the case of one barangay in the city, the designated Barangay Information Officer is the barangay kagawad. According to the participant who is also the punong barangay who appointed the said BIO, the said barangay official is well versed in the use of technology and is also fast in processing information, thus she is the perfect fit for the role.

“Siya ang chairman sa (Committee on) Health, ang amon nga Barangay Information Officer, and (in-charge) for the Solid Waste Management...ikay mahilig siya sa technology kag madasig. (Participant 3, personal communication, April 8, 2025).

English Translation: She is the chairman for the Committee on Health and also serves as our Barangay Information Officer, solid waste management is also under her. I identified her because she is well versed in the use of technology and is also fast in processing information.

While all barangays have their assigned BIOs who will be the partner of the City Government in information dissemination, their maximum potential is yet to be explored and determined this year. According to the PIO, the BIOs will undergo the UnRISK training for them to understand DRRM and their role on it especially in the Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) Campaigns.

4.) Response Capability

For the response capability, the City Government has constructed six ICARE (Iloilo City Action and Response) Centers in strategic areas in the locality. As of 2024, there are six operational ICARE Centers and these are located in various districts in the city.

The ICARE Centers house emergency frontline offices like the Public Safety and Management Office (PSTMO), Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP), Philippine National Police, and the CDRRMO. The rationale of the facility is to bring the various services close to the communities. Under the Response Division of the CDRRMO, there are also two units namely: Iloilo City Emergency Responders (ICER) and the Urban Search and Rescue (USAR) Team.

Sa communication, OpCen sila na gihapon kag balik gid kita sa barangay sang amon nga I-CARE (Iloilo City Action and Response Centers). So amo ina siya. Dayun sa response capability, under the Response Division sa gihapon amo na ina ang ICER, USAR, as you can see indi lang ni isa ka section.

(Participant 1, personal communication, April 4, 2025)

English Translation: In the communication, the OpCen is in-charge and we go back to the barangay through our I-CARE. And under the response

capability, we have the Response Division, that is where the ICER and USAR falls under. So you see, it is not just one section

The I-CARE Centers localize the response capability of the Iloilo City Government. The near proximity of these centers to the strategic areas in the city would translate to faster response should a need arise.

The CDRRMO is also utilizing the ICARE for their KABALAKA Tour in the city. KABALAKA or “Kahublagan sa BARangay para sa LAPnagon nga KAhandaan sa KAlamidad” serves as a vital educational resource for the residents (Daily Guardian, 2024).

According to CDRRMO (2025), this program is an offshoot of their previous program and it is to show compassion or “kabalaka” to the public by educating and informing them about disaster resiliency. Through this program, they aim to develop a culture of safety and resilience so that they know what to do when faced with a particular situation.

KABALAKA Program has three sub programs: tour, gallery, and camp. For the KABALAKA Tour, the CDRRMO is facilitating tours to the I-CARE and other institutions in the city to highlight the various DRRM strategies. On the other hand, the KABALAKA gallery showcases various IEC materials and artworks that depict stories of resilience. Lastly, the KABALAKA camp is for children to be familiar with various hazards and what they can do to mitigate its negative impact.

In addition, they also have KABALAKA sa barangay where they assist the barangays in understanding their risks and introducing risk governance.

So amo ina siya ang idea sa KABALAKA program naton. So to develop that culture of safety, may KABALAKA tour kita, may KABALAKA gallery, may

KABALAKA camp. All of these are meant to educate people. Ano ang risks nga gina-atubang naton and what can you do. Amo ina siya. May KABALAKA sa barangay kita , we assist ang mga barangays in understanding their risks to governance. So amo man ina siya ang sa may city level, so we invest in their education. By education we mean learning visits and then can we use the whole of the society approach as a strategy so we try to reach out to as many stakeholders as possible kay ngaa risk reduction, climate and disaster resilience, it is a business of everyone hindi bala from what you do as an individual as an organization, it contributes to the greater good sang syudad so amo ina ang gusto naton matabo from my level ano ang pwede ko mahimo, so amo ina siya ang sa may KABALAKA nga ano program naton.

(Participant 1, personal communication, April 4, 2025)

English Translation: So the idea in our KABALAKA Program is to develop a culture of safety through our KABALAK tours, KABALAKA gallery, and KABALAKA camps. All of these are meant to educate people about the risks that we are facing and what we can do about it...we also have KABALAKA sa barangay where we assist the barangays for them to understand their risks as well as risk governance...We invest in education. By education we mean learning visits and then can we use the whole of the society approach as a strategy so we try to reach out to as many stakeholders as possible because risk reduction, climate and disaster resilience, is a business of everyone. It contributes to the greater good that is why we want that to happen, that is why we have the KABALAKA program.

The media is one of the participants in the KABALA Tour. This activity is essential because it enables them to be familiarized with the processes, services, and even equipment. Through this, they are more confident in reporting because they are familiar with it.

huo several times na nagtour kami, may tour ina siya kag sort of a little training like nagligad nag tour kami gintudlan kami dira sa Bureau of Fire sang basic paano mag-evacuate paano magdala sang tawo nga injured, gintudluan kami. Nagkadto man kami sa PAGASA, sa radar station, nakita naton nga problema gid, kulang...mas maayo pa ang ICARE Center sang city kay kumpleto ang mga gamit.

(Participant 5, personal communication, April 22, 20225)

English Translation: yes we had tours at the ICARE and there was a sort of a training. The personnel from the Bureau of Fire Protection taught us the basics in evacuation, and responding to an injured person. We also visited the radar station of PAGASA. There we see the problems, their limitations. You know our ICARE Center is even better than theirs, the equipment is more complete.

The various activities under the KABALAKA Program falls both under building the risk knowledge and response capability of the various sectors in the community. In its sense, response is about knowing what to do when there is a situation, and this is built on the risk knowledge of the individual.

Part of building the response capability in the locality is the institutionalization of the DRRM Council per district. This is an innovation and is beyond the provisions of the Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act. Under the said law, the LGUs should create and operate a DRRM council from the regional down to the

provincial, municipal, and city level. In the case of the barangays, a DRRM Committee should be established.

The City Government created a district level DRRM with the recognition of the peculiarities and uniqueness of every district. This was institutionalized through an Executive Order issued by the Local Chief Executive.

The creation of district nga clustering of the barangays no is something nga I do not know sa history sini, something nga daw pang mas management nga strategy. This is not created by a particular ordinansa. Wala ini siya nga naga-create so wala ini siya sang political nga division, recognition lang ini siya. So that is why it is not covered by RA 10121 nga ginasing nga dapat may district level. So this is just an initiative sang CDRRMC naton kay again because of the localization efforts naton sa DRR, nakita anton nga it is quite difficult to work sa 180 barangays. And since naga-exist ang clustering of the barangays per district, and there is a recognition nga again ang kada district lain-lain ang timpla, lain-lain ang gina-atubang nga mga hazards. They have their own peculiarities, uniqueness so ang mga local leaders diri they are used in working together as part of the district so siling namon why don't we try this one but we just have to be clear on the functions sini and ang sa role...

(Participant 1, personal communication, April 4, 2025)

English Translation: the creation of the district (DRRM) is based on the clustering of the barangays and is more of a management strategy. This is not created through a particular ordinance and does not create a political division. It is because we recognize that the district level is not covered by RA 10121. This is just an initiative by the CDRRMC because of our localization efforts in

DRR. We know that it is difficult to work with 180 barangays. Since there is a clustering of the barangays per district, we recognize that every district has different hazards, realities, peculiarities, and uniqueness. The punong barangays are already working with other barangay officials, we just need to define their role.

This initiative is supported by DILG which supervises the LGUs and serves as the chairperson for the Disaster Preparedness Thematic Area in DRRM. The City DILG also emphasized that the District DRRM Councils has no funding allocation because it will just serve as a policymaking body:

Actually, wala siya funding kay policymaking body lang siya, ma-assist lang siya. Kon lantawon ta si DRRM Council, magobra siya hazard, iprioritize ni city so kaisa may mga lugar nga ma-miss , indi siya mamention, pagbotobotohay wala siya namention, indi siya priority pero kon siya ara didto, nag-obra sila policy kag ginpasa nila diri so for that district amo ini ang policy kag amo ini ang hazard didto which was identified by the residents mismo

(Participant 4, personal communication, April 2, 2025)

English Translation: The DRRM District Council has no funding because it is just a policymaking body, it will just assist. If we look at the DRRM (District) Council, it will identify the hazards in their area. Sometimes the city (LGU) missed some areas because it was not mentioned. However, if they have a policy (or recommendation) from their district about it, they will just submit it to the city level, and the hazards are identified by the residents themselves.

The institutionalization of the District DRRM in the city has been cemented through the passing of a resolution of the City Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council. At their 2nd Quarter Meeting, the CDRRMC approved a resolution establishing a District-level DRRM Councils in all seven districts in the city. These District-level DRRM Councils, which will be chaired by the president of the Association of Barangay Captains per district, will serve as the local extensions of the CDRRMC. They will lead the real-time coordination and rapid response during emergencies in their areas of jurisdiction. The full potential of this new undertaking is yet to be determined upon its full implementation within the year.

The institutionalization of the DRRM Council is the City Government's initiative to localize as well its mechanism. It is employed to decentralize and streamline the overall process to include the communication of the EWS.

Challenges in Communicating EWS

While the City Government has been implementing innovative strategies in communicating its Early Warning System, it cannot be denied that it is also experiencing some challenges. It can be classified according to the following; 1.) Political Dynamics 2.) Functionality of the EWS 3.) Constraints in resources 4.) Capacity Building

1.) Political Dynamics

Based on the Philippines Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act of 2010, the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Councils in the province, city, and municipal, and the Barangay Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Committee, shall perform various functions to mitigate the negative impacts of a disaster. This includes the operationalization of a multi-hazard early warning system

to provide accurate and timely advice to national or local emergency response organizations and to the general public (Official Gazette, 2010).

The development and implementation of the early warning system on a locality depends on the appreciation and prioritization of the Local Chief Executives (LCEs) as the chairperson of the provincial/city/municipal/city/barangay DRRMC.

In the Philippines where barangay chairman seats in office for every six years (Batas Pambansa Bilang 222, 1982; Supreme Court E-Library, n.d.) while the mayor serves for four years (Republic Act No. 1236, 1955; Supreme Court E-Library, n.d.), the role of the LCEs is crucial and fundamental.

The development and implementation of the EWS in the city is institutionalized, however, the operationalization of it in the whole 180 barangays under its jurisdiction is relative.

Ang tricky na prime dira is from us going to the barangays. As long as naga-work ang Viber, ang radyo, ang handheld radios, ang mga Messenger nila nga groups, makalab-ot gid ina up to the last mile kay amo ina siya ang mga barangays naton, they have this Public Address System nga once mabaton nila, ang iba na gina-announce nila. So amo ina siya, amo pa ina ang gusto namon i-establish man. We want to see kon how active ang mga kabarangayan nga once they receive that information, makalab-ot.

(Participant 1, personal communication, April 4, 2025)

English Translation: The tricky part is always in the communication down to the barangays. As long as Viber is working, as well as the handheld radios, and the Messenger group chats, these pieces of information can reach up to the last mile. In the barangays, we have a Public Address System that once they

receive an information, they announce it to the public. That is what we want to establish. We want to see how active the barangays are when they receive the information.

The political realities and dynamics in the barangay is also one area that affects the operationalization and communication of the EWS on their level. The participant representing Association of Punong Barangays in the city expressed that the short-term of the barangay officials and the subjective priority in governance affect the consistent implementation of the various DRRM efforts.

...Ang isa pa gid dira naton nga lantawon may eleksyon. Syempre kon lain naman nga set sang officer syempre matraining kana naman to ang ginbayaan, for example kami ha pilot barangay ang Buntatala sa CBARAD, dapat kuntani nag nagbulos ang time nga to nga nagpilot barangay si Lovejoy to ang kapitan, dapat ang nagbulos kay Lovejoy continue niya para may sustainability kaso ang training niya indi parehas sa previous kag basi lain iya priority...lain-lain man abi kon ano ang sa amon, basi indi man applicable sa iban daw amo na bala, te waay man ta kabalo kon ano ang ano ni kap sa ila...

(Participant 3, personal communication, April 8, 2025)

English Translation: One thing that we need to look at is the election. Of course, if we have a new set of officials, they need to be trained. For example, we are a pilot barangay for CBARAD (Community-Based Adaptation and Resilience Against Disaster), supposedly, the new officials, when it was piloted it was Lovejoy (Hosenilla) who was the punong barngay, supposedly, the new officials should have implemented it for its sustainability. However, her training

was different, her priority might be different. Moreover, we have different realities in the barangay, some might not be applicable to other barangay. We do not know the strategies of the other barangays in their respective areas.

2.) Functionality of the EWS

Aside from the role of the Local Government Units, the role of the National Government Agencies in the development and implementation of the Early Warning System is also critical.

Under the Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act of 2010 (Official Gazette, 2010), the Department of Science and Technology is the Vice-Chairperson for the Disaster Prevention and Mitigation Thematic Area. As the Vice-Chair, they are responsible for the establishment and/or improvement of the end-to-end monitoring (monitoring and response, forecasting, and early warning systems (NDRRMC, 2020). However, it is worth noting that their services only centered on the development of the EWS, specifically in the installation of various monitoring technologies for various hazards. The institutionalization and functionality of the EWS among LGUs in various levels, especially its communication to the general public is not covered.

According to DOST (n.d.), they implemented the project Deployment of Early Warning System in Disaster-prone Areas (DEWS) which aims to install a granular system of hydrometeorological devices(hydromet) and warning stations in selected hazard areas in the country. This is done to collect weather risk data which will be used to have informed and guided decision-making especially in mitigating the negative impacts of disasters. Undoubtedly, the DOST pioneered the establishment

of various devices, however the monitoring of the functionality of the EWS as a system is usually overlooked.

...there was no agency. I do not know lang basi may ara walang lang ko naka-reach out sa ila or wala lang nakalab-ot sa akon but I would like to think nga wala may nagtudlo sang concept of early warning system except for NTC (National Telecommunications Commission) kay Engr Monroy gani kag prime ko man ini siya nabatian kay DOST because they are the lead but I do not think, naistoryahan na nila...but how you see this being operated on the ground it is left to the discretion of the LGU, kon paano mag-interpet, paano mag-obra.

(Participant 1, personal communication, April 4, 2025)

English Translation: There was no agency (monitoring the EWS). I do not know if there is one and I am just not aware but I think there is no agency that teaches us about the concept of the early warning system except with NTC (National Telecommunications Commission), with Engr. Monroy. I often heard it with DOST because they are the lead but I do not think that they talk it out with others. How you see this being operated on the ground is left to the discretion of the LGU like how they interpret and how to work on it.

The Department of the Interior and Local Government (DILG) developed a manual called “Operation L!sto for the barangays to have a Barangay DRRM Plan Template in which the EWS is also part of. However, their means of assessment to the EWS is only limited to the following: 1.) availability of early warnings that are posted in the designated areas, 2.) presence of batingaw “Public Address System”, 3.) presence of early warnings for the Persons with Disabilities, and 4.) presence of

hazard-specific early warnings. They only check if the LGUs have the necessary early warning equipment, its implementation and functionality, especially its communication is not monitored and evaluated.

So if you look at sa system, ang role, especially kun mapa-guwa si OCD (Office of Civil Defense). Si OCD will send a communication to DILG Region VI, then they will download the communication to us, for example mga weather disturbance or what then amo ina nag ipasa namon sa LGU (Local Government Unit). Kon need nga magpasaka sang alert level so abay naman ina sa advisory. The i-check namon una-una sa checklist namon “ is the chief executive on station?” or diri siya sa area niya, kay bal-an ta nga damo mga banwa bala kis-a nga kon mag-abot ang bagyo, may emergency, wala ang mayor. So number 1 na sa checklist.

(Participant 4, personal communication, April 2, 2025)

English Translation: So if you look at the system, the Office of Civil Defense will send communication to DILG Region VI, then it will be downloaded to us. For example if there is a weather disturbance, then we will send it to the LGU. If there is a need to raise the alert level, we issue an advisory. Then we have a checklist like “is the chief executive on station?”, because you know sometimes if there is a typhoon or emergency, sometimes the mayor is not around. That is the number 1 in our checklist.

3.) Constraints in Resources

While the City Government has implemented various innovative strategies to communicate its EWS, it also faced various challenges which affect the realization of its maximum potential and impact because of the constraints in their resources.

For the human resource in the case of the Publication and Information Office, they only have eight (8) personnel in their office, DRRM is also just one of the many areas that they cover.

Diri sa PIO, may News Team kami mo so basically sa team na, walo kami. So sa social media may nagahandle may content manager, si Gian ang naga-supervise, tapos may duha, one makes the pubmat ang isa sa videos then si LM for the IEC materials, Glenda for the press release, and then I just check the outputs...amo na bala ang akon misgivings gid nga dapat ang PIO nagakadto, nagapanaug, te because amo lang kami ni, with the limited resources, we do not go down to that level in the barangay gid. Amo na that is why we are going to have the Barangay Information Officers.

(Participant 2, personal communication, April 8, 2025)

English Translation: Here in the PIO, we have our News Team that is composed of 8 personnel. We have a content manager who handles our social media, Gian supervises that. Another one makes the publication material and the other one is for the videos. LM is for the IEC materials, Glenda for the press release, and I just check the outputs...One of my misgivings is that the PIO should go down to the barangays. However, because of our limited resources, we cannot do that. That is why we have the Barangay Information Officers.

For the City Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office (CDRRMO), additional personnel who are experts in their respective fields such as in hydrology, video editing, etc. will be an advantage in their aspiration to deliver an informed decision through relatable communication channels.

there was a time nga medyo ano lang be siya trabahoso, may PWD man kami mo, so may inset (video for Facebook) kami na last time, tingala kami nga that particular video nga may bagyo, damo-damo shares. Kag gali imo sa network sang mga deaf and mute, nalipay sila kay for the first time baw nabal-an ta man kon ang ang sitwasyon because we did something like that. So indi lang siya about sa written, about localizing sa aton nga dialect, but even sa language sang iban nga sectors...medyo trabahoso lang siya kay they have to edit... yes, in-house expert sa mga videography...We already have a meteorologist, we also need a hydrologist... kay we are prone to flooding para studihan kay even ang drainage again using systems thinking kay indi man ini pwede nga individual like right now may masterplan sa pagobra sang drainage so we need a hydrologist, we do have knowledge where flooding happens pero mas nami tani kon may in-house kami nga amo na siya, then they can tell us nga amo ina ang bagyo...

(Participant 1, personal communication, April 8, 2025)

English Translation: there was a time that we posted a video (on Facebook) about a typhoon, and it had an inset video for PWDs. We were shocked that that particular video had a lot of shares, it turned out that it was shared among the network of the deaf and mute. They were happy because for the first time, they knew what was happening. So it is not just about the written, about the

localization of our language, but also about the language of the other sectors. However, it is quite challenging because we have to edit, maybe an in-house expert in videography would be a big help... We already have a meteorologist, we also need a hydrologist because we are prone to flooding. He can study the drainage system...we need a hydrologist, while we have the knowledge where the flooding occurs, if we have an in-house (hydrologist) he can tell us more about the situation.

Aside from the human resource, there is also an issue in the quality and consistency of early warning messages being shared to the public through the barangay.

(may ara sang para sa) bagyo lang gid, baha wala . tapos ayawan pana kami kaisa...ano ang iya sang city nga early advisory nga ginahambal. Ang gusto ko tani ang daw catchy man para mamati man ang tawo, daw parehas sa Bombo Radyo nga sa tion sang amo ni, kita mag amo ni...may pwera...may ara sir sang sample galing daw kaluya bala nagreklamo ako kay daw k boring kag tapos damo sonata. Damo pa ang sonata sang sa hambal sang tawo te paano na be macatch ang attention sang tawo. Te nagreklamo gid ko na kay maam Dona...

(Participant 3, personal communication, April 8, 2025)

English Translation: We were given an audio recording for our Public Address System but it is only for a typhoon, there is nothing for flooding. Sometimes we had some difficulty in the advisories that the city shared with us. What I want is a catchy one so that the public will listen similar with Bombo Radyo Iloilo,there

is power...they gave us before but it was boring and was full of songs. The songs are lengthier than the advisory. I complained to ma'am Donna (CDRRM Officer) about that particular incident.

Aside from producing the audio materials, the PIO also collaborates with other institutions like the Bureau of Fire Protection in the production of audio materials for their Public Address System. They prepare the script and sometimes record it and their partner institution just utilized it in their information dissemination.

The participant representing the PIO pointed out that they do not have their own budget for their IEC Campaigns, they utilize instead the LDRRM Fund through the CDRRMC.

May process kami iya nga amon for example sina te gadevelop kami sang mga hazard specific or sector specific tapos ginapa-approve namon sa OpCen, sa CDRRMO, sa council kay sila ang gabudget for the funding...We do not have our own budget sa IEC, we tap the CDRRMC dira kami nagakuha sa LDDRM fund.

(Participant 2, personal communication, April 8, 2025)

English Translation: We have a process for example when we develop a hazard-specific or sector-specific IEC campaign, we let it approved by the Operation Center in the CDRRMO, and then the CRRMC, the council because they are the ones funding it...we do not have our own budget for the IEC campaign, we tap the CDRRMC to utilize the LDRRM fund.

4.) Capacity Building

The CDRRMO has collaborated with various sectors in the locality to strengthen their capacity and capability in disaster preparedness and climate resiliency. Some of the sectors that have existing partnerships to increase their risk knowledge includes the barangay officials, academe, and media.

The CDRRMO intends to partner with other sectors like the private sector, the Civil Society Organizations, and Women's Organizations among others to also strengthen their resilience. They are yet to partner with these sectors as part of their aspiration of building a disaster resilient community. This endeavor has started and the realization of its full potential and impact is yet to be determined.

Sectoral tapos later kay naka-mention man ko sa staff, siling ko lantawa bala it was Women's Month, siling ko wala gid kita ya activity para sa women. Siling ko kon gintipon niyo be ang mga kababaihan ta kag we start talking about disasters and how it affects women. Siling ya maam, desidido ko ya, ang next naton nga i-UnRISK si women. Siling ko indi anay ubosa ang private sector, CSOs, kag tanan nga mga kababaihan dira pangkuhaa para may ara na bala sang understanding...subong naintindihan niyo na ang konsepto, how does it affects women and start there...Strengthen mo ang council strengthen mo ang academe, CSOs, PWDs, kita mo nag-work...ang ending we want to see the barangays nga naka-intindi sang risk knowledge nila, they come up with their solutions, with the understanding of climate and disaster risks...kami ang taga-trigger, we provide the platform, provide the avenue for discussions, hulag kita tanan...

(Participant 1, personal communication, April 8, 2025)

English Translation: Our approach is sectoral, I actually have mentioned in my staff that we have no activity for women this Women's Month. They could have gathered the women and discussed disasters and how it affects them. The staff was positive to do it through the UnRISK program. I then advised her to finish first the private sector and CSOs...After strengthening the council, we also strengthened the academe, CSOs, PWDs, etc. Ultimately, what we want to see is the barangays that understand their risk knowledge and they are the ones coming up with their solutions, with their understanding of climate and disaster risks. We just trigger and provide the platform.

In the case of the PIO and other sectors such as the barangay officials, media, and academe, they recognized their limitations and expressed their willingness to participate in other capacity building activities like training and simulation exercises.

I think may mga needs improvement pa man kami indi man kami perfect...di ba kinahanglan pa gid namon ang more capacity building pa gid siguro and more knowledge man on DRR works, kay ang amon leaning daw dira mo...kag ang sa crisis comm daw sa amon man ginahaboy so we need more trainings siguro and competency-based trainings...especially with the technologies no whether we like it or not gobyerno ini ang amon nga equipment nga ginagamit are old, daan na. We also need to keep up with the times...

(Participant 2, personal communication, April 8, 2025)

English Translation: I think there are still areas for improvement for us because we are not perfect. We need more capacity building and knowledge about Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) works. Besides, our work is leaning

towards that. Moreover, we also need training for crisis communication, more competency-based training especially with the use of technology. Because we are a government unit, our equipment are quite outdated, we also need to keep up with the times.

The City Hall Press Corps is also reportedly lacking on training and seminars related to DRRM. The participant representing the City Hall Press Corps admitted that despite being part of the media for quite a long time, he still needs to learn a lot especially in disaster reporting.

...actually amo na ang isa sa mahambal ko nga medyo may kulang sa mga katapo sang media siguro indi lang man ako pero amo gid ina ang isa sa mga pinakakulang which we strive sa amon sa press corps amo na nga nagaayo gid gaayo kami sa PIO nga magconduct sang trainings, seminars para nga ma-enhance man ang amon nga ideas pero te bisan papaano we can communicate kon ano man ang gusto namon ipalab-ot nga information sa city hall sa public...ang mga challenges, sometimes ma interchange ang mga term disaster, calamity. Indi ta kaisa ma distinguish ang disaster, indi ta madistinguish ang calamity. Mga limitations nga naandan naton sang una pa bala sa initial reporting naton nga daw ginapareho lang naton ang disaster kag calamity. Te amo na ang gusto namon matun-an, as a matter of fact nagaplan kami nga mag-work with CDRRMO nga maubra kami sang glossary of terms sang disaster kag calamity, disaster preparedness and calamity para sa disaster reporting para nga amo man ang magamit namon eh kag mangin bible namon sa pagubra sang balita. Indi mo manmalikaan ang interchanging of

words kag sa publiko daw naandan naman nila ina pero we need to change ang perception para effective delivery man sang information...

(Participant 5, personal communication, April 22, 2025)

English Translation: Actually I can really say that that area (training) is lacking among members of the media. It is not just me that is why we have appealed to the PIO to conduct training and seminars so that our knowledge will be increased. In doing so, we can communicate better what they want to communicate to the public through us as well...one of our challenges is the interchanging of the terms like disaster and calamity. We have limitations because we are accustomed to use these terms interchangeably. So that is what we want to be knowledgeable about, as a matter of fact we are planning to work with CDRRMO to create a glossary of terms for disaster and calamity, disaster preparedness, this is for disaster reporting which we can utilize in writing our news. We cannot deny the fact that we might interchange the words plus the fact that the public is used to it, however, we need to change the perception of the public to effectively deliver the information.

For the punong barangays, it is not just about conducting training but ensuring that these are tailored-fit for a specific audience and is simplified so that the barangay officials would easily understand and appreciate it.

Mas mahapos sa mga kapitan sa kagawad kag kinahanglan may training simplified training bala kon paano i-address ang calamity. Daw kadamolang ngatraining ngatechnical daw indi mo man ma ano sa barangay, daw amo na bala simplified lang nga kami nga barnagay officials kay indi man tanan mga

kapitan wala man may tinapusan or may pagintindi nga amo na kaano, i simplify nga para deliver nila sa tawo nila nga amo lang na kasimple oh...

(Participant 3, personal communication, April 8, 2025)

English Translation: It would be easier for the punong barangay and barangay kagawad (if they understand Disaster Risk Reduction), and they need a simplified training on how to address these calamities. We have a lot of training but these were technical and cannot be appreciated down in the barangay level. Not all barangay officials have finished our studies or might have limited understanding. It needs to be simplified for us to also deliver it to the public in a simple manner.

Another challenge pointed out by the partner academic institution is the lack of training and simulation exercise of the total black-out system. He also noted that we have become too dependent on the use of cellphones. While there are handheld radios, they need to be strategically distributed in various areas like barangays and schools and not everybody has the technical knowledge on how to use them.

“kon sa early warning system, wala ko pa nakita ang sa black-out system...for example very dependable kita kay cellphone, may ara man sila radyo pero kon may strategic ka nga mga areas like si barangay, si school...”(Participant 6, personal communication, April 29, 2025)

English Translation: If we talk about the Early Warning System, I think I have not observed our capacity in a situation like there is a total black-out system (no power/electricity). For example, we have become too dependent on the use of

cellphones. We have radios but it needs to be distributed in strategic areas like barangay schools.

While the CDRRMO has two-way communication through the use of handheld radios, it is not the primary means to communicate or disseminate information. In addition, some barangays have their own units of handheld radio but they are not using it consistently.

In communicating that to the public, we post ang advisories, tapos may (radio) frequency kita nga dedicated sa mga barangays. Tikal ko lang pero I do not think kon gina-practice nila kay kon kaisa gina-monitor ko sila, siling ko “wala na kamo naga-announce”. Kay tani kada guwa sina, gina-radyo man nila. Sa start eh ginaradyo nila so kinahanglan gid i-eksido.

(D. Magno, personal communication, April 8, 2025)

English Translation: In communicating the early warnings to the public, we post our advisories. We also have our radio frequency dedicated for the barangays. However, I do not think they are really practicing it because sometimes when I monitor, it seems like they are not using it anymore. Supposedly, when there is information, we use the radio. During the early beginning, they were using the radio. It needs to be consistent and certain.

The punong barangay confirmed that they have a two-way radio for faster communication; however, they are not using it consistently.

“kaagi mana sir nga kada adlaw ginarequire nga i-open namon galing may beses gid kaisa nga kagahod gid pamatian. Damo bal-an mo, nagamonitor dira

si pulis,BFP, sa liga, ang kada barangay pa gid” (Participant 3, personal communication, April 8, 2025)

English Translation: There was a time that we required the use of radio frequency but there are times that it becomes too loud (that is why we turn it off). A lot of institutions like the police, the BFP, the liga (ng mga barangay), and then every barangay use it to monitor.

Emerging Themes

To explain the localization of the Early Warning System in Iloilo City through the use of participatory communication and social mobilization, Braun & Clarke’s (2006) six-step thematic analysis was employed. This includes (1) becoming familiar with the data, (2) generating initial codes, (3) identifying themes, (4) reviewing themes, (5) defining themes, and (6) writing the narrative.

As a result, four themes were identified namely: (1) localization of the mechanism, (2) localization of the language, (3) inclusive Early Warning System, and (4) Strengthened Community Resilience.

Table 2.

Emerging Themes in the Localization of Early Warning System in Iloilo City

Themes	Codes
Localization of the Mechanism	Organizational approach (DRRM coordinator/district, ICARE, communication strategies such as the use of radio frequency and the Public Address System)
	Institutional approach (DRRM Council and BIO)
	Sectoral approach (UnRISK)
Localization of the language	Translation to the local language
	Contextualization or giving additional information/explanation
	Simplification
Inclusive Early Warning System	Early warnings for the visually-impaired
	Early warnings for those who have hearing impairment
	IEC material for specific sectors
	Multimodal communication
Strengthened Community Resilience	Increased risk knowledge
	Streamlined and Coordinated Monitoring Services
	Effective Risk Communication
	Early Response Time

A. Localization of the Mechanism

The first theme, Localization of the Mechanism, refers to the institutionalization of the Early Warning System in various levels of governance and sectors. It has subcategories namely (1) organizational approach, (2) institutional approach, and (3) the sectoral approach. Using this approach, the development, implementation, and communication of EWS, as a system, is institutionalized at various levels. It ensures the harmonization and synchronization of the efforts through the alignment of the frameworks and strategies from the city down to the barangay level and vice versa.

The Organizational Approach refers to the programs and projects implemented by the City Government through the City Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office (CDRRMO) to localize its EWS. Examples to this are the deployment of DRRM coordinator per district, the construction of ICARE per district, and the use of the radio frequency and Public Address System down to the barangays as a communication strategy.

For the Institutional Approach, the City Government localizes its EWS through the creation of District DRRM Councils and the deployment of the Barangay Information Officers (BIOs). The DRRM Councils and BIOs are independent institutions which serve as the bridge between the Iloilo City Government and the barangays.

Lastly, the Sectoral Approach in the localization of the EWS is practiced through the UnRISK program. While this is also primarily implemented by the CDRRMO, the focus is not on them as its implementers but to the participants to the program who are the various stakeholders in the locality.

The City Government's localization of its mechanism to communicate its EWS streamline the overall communication process. It institutionalizes the initiative in various levels, encompassing as well the four elements of the EWS. Since the goal to

build community resilience involves all sectors of the community, the institutionalization of a localized mechanism is necessary and instrumental.

Table 3.

Localization of the Mechanism in the Communication of Early Warning System in Iloilo City

Response	Code	Theme
<p>“Ma-message kami sa Balantang namon nga focal person sang disaster...kada district may ara sang focal person halin sa CDRRMO” (We message the focal person for disaster in our area, in the Balantang, she is the focal person from the CDRRMO)</p>	Organization Approach	Localization of the Mechanism
<p>“So in every district, we have a focal person. If we do the risk assessment, we have to go down to the barangay level. So sila ni siya ang ga-take charge and putting together all, you have the city level na perspective when it comes to the risk knowledge of the city” (So in every district, we have a focal person. If we do the risk assessment, we have to go down to the barangay level. So they (Barangay DRRM Services Division) are the ones who are in-charge and putting together all the information. You have then the city level perspective when it comes to risk knowledge.)</p>		
<p>“Under sa LGU, may DRR officer, may ara sila per district man nga naga-assign</p>		
<p>kag may ara man assigned nga coordinator per district” (Unde the LGU, there is a DRR Officer, then they have an assigned coordinator/focal per district)</p>		
<p>“kag subong ang sa pinakalatest naton ang District DRRM Council, so amo man ina siya we strengthen their capabilities man and competencies” (and now our latest innovation is the District DRRM Council. This is to strengthen the capabilities and competencies in the district level)</p>	Institutional Approach	
<p>“kag last nga CDRRMC Meeting, ginresolutionan na ina plus ang functions nga i-establish ang district DRR councils nga ang role nila mag-recommend policies, mag-identify sang hazards nila sa ila area...”</p>		

<p>(during the last CDRRMC Meeting, we passed a resolution about the institutionalization of the District DRR Council. Its role is to recommend policies and identify the hazards in their area</p>		
<p>“we have this new program with CDRRMO wherein we make this cluster of disaster council per district so we are really indulge in that one”</p>		
<p>“gina-ano namon tani nga the barangays will also step up so may ara kami actually ginhimo nga kon magsubmit ang barangay sang ila BDRRM plan, ibutang nila to nga there is an executive order designating sang Barangay Public Information Office which gin-obra man ina sang 180 barangays. So this year ang target namon i-mobilize ang 180 ka mga barangays, BIO tawag namon, Barangay Information Officers” (We are aspiring that the barangays will also step up in the information dissemination. We have this program where the barangay officials issue an executive order designating their Barangay Public Information Officer, that needs to be part of their DRRM Plan. All the 180 barangays are doing it, our plan this year is to mobilize them. We call them BIO, the Barangay Information Officers)</p>		
<p>If we have the BDRRMC, within the BDRRMC, we included the participation sang Barangay IO. So ang role ni BIO, naka-angot kay PIO. So amo ina siya, what I would like to think nga kon ano ang sa city level , masustain ina sa barangay levels through the BIOs as part sang redundancy naton. (If we have the BDRRMC, within the BDRRMC, we have included the participation of the Barangay IO. Their role is connected with the PIO. We would like to think that all information from the city level will be cascaded to the barangay level through the BIOs as part of our redundancy efforts)</p>		
<p>Siya ang chairman sa Health, ang amon nga barangya information officer, solid waste... (she is the chairman for the Committee on Health and the Solid Waste Management, she is also our Barangay Information Officer)</p>		
<p>“UnRISK gani, part na siya ang risk assessment. Ang title sadto UnRISK. So subong nag-evolve na siya, we do UnRISK sessions para sa academe, next namon nga ubrahon is sa private sector kay what we realize is that we cannot work with these sectors kon ang imo partner wala nakaintindi kon ano ang risks” (the UnRISK project is part of the risk assessment. Right now, it has evolved, we do UnRISK sessions for the academe and our next target is the private sector. What we have realized is that we cannot work with these sectors if they do not know their risks.)</p>	<p>Sectoral Approach</p>	

<p>involved gid kami dira kay because ang isa sa mga gin-UnRISK ang mga members san Iloilo City Hall Press Corps, so nangin part sila sang aton nga UnRISK tapos amo na ang next plan siguro by June or July ang aton na nga mga barangay information officers. (We are involved in the UnRISK program because part of the participants were the members of the Iloilo City Hall Press Corps. Our plan by June or July is to conduct it for the Barangay Information Officers.)</p>		
<p>“(sa UnRISK project) actually ako nakita ko dapat pa ako gali dapat matun-an, sa disaster risk reporting. Kadugay na sa akon sa media pero I need to learn a lot pa.” (After attending the UnRISK project, I actually realized that I still need to learn a lot, especially about disaster risk reporting. I have been part of the media industry for quite some time but I still need to learn more.)</p>		

Table 3 highlighted the localization of the mechanism in communicating the Early Warning System as experienced and observed by the participants.

B. Localization of the Language

The second theme is the localization of the language which revolves around the various strategies being employed by the Iloilo City Government to ensure that the early warning messages that they are communicating are understood by the public. Iloilo City, being a melting pot of culture and center of economic development, the residents use various languages. Aside from the locals, the local and foreign tourists who also use other languages and dialects is also worth noting. The literacy of the public and the socio-economic status are also a matter of consideration.

To respond to this gap, the Iloilo City Government translates the information to the local language, Hiligaynon. It is observed that the Government Agencies that are tasked for monitoring and forecasting like PAGASA and PHIVOLCS, commonly use English and Filipino languages in their advisories. To ensure that these pieces of

information are understood by the public in the locality, the Iloilo City Government translates these in the local language, as much as possible.

The other strategies that they employ to localize the language is the contextualization and simplification. Contextualization is providing additional context about the information by illustrations or additional explanation. On the other hand, simplification is simplifying the information in a manner that is easily understood by the audience; this is achieved through the use of simple and relatable words.

Table 4.

Localization of the Language in the Communication of Early Warning System in Iloilo City

Response	Code	Theme
<p>“Kon mag amo ina siya, still we will rely sa technical person kay te di bala kami nana ang bahala sa pag-simplify, indi lang nga i-translate mo lang in the local language. Kundi iintindihon pa gid, ang tawag ni nila Science Communication” (If that is the case we rely on technical person but we are the ones who simplify it. It is not just about translating it to the local language. We need to understand it, they call it Science Communication)</p>	<p>Translation to the local language</p>	<p>Localization of the language</p>
<p>“I like it better nga in Hiligaynon, like pareho sang rikorida, we do it in Hiligaynon kay di ba the common tao can relate, maintindihan nila”</p>		

<p>(I like it better that it is in Hiligaynon just like for the rikorida (Public Address System). The general public can understand it.)</p>		
<p>“kun kinahangan nga English te English pero kon pwede mo siya translate into Hiligaynon nga indi man maguba ang meaning niya, pwede siya matranslate” (If it needs to be in English, I use English but if it can be translated in Hiligaynon without jeopardizing its meaning, it would be better)</p>		
<p>“When you explain, ano ina siya kabaskog si 120 km/h nga hangin haw? Di bala, so ano ang palahambingan nila. Daw parehos bala kon magsakay ka sa jeep, ang speed ya sina 120 so amo ina kabaskog ang hangin then people will understand, ah amo ina siya kabaskog...contextualization or association, I do not know how you will call it. Give an example nga related sa day-to-day nga experience sang tawo then they will come to understand” (When we explain how strong 120 km/h is, we can use an analogy like we compare it when we ride a jeepney. In doing so, the public will easily understand...contextualization or association, I do not know what you call it. You just give an example that is related to the day-to-day experiences of the public so that they will understand it.)</p>	<p>Contextualization</p>	
<p>“may mga words nga maintindihan mo siya in English pero kinahanglan mo siya i-contextualize para mas mahangpan sang tawo may mga words abi, kita abi ang Hiligaynon abi nga kataga kabudlay, not sa English nga specific. Kaisa ang isa ka word sa English, duwa or tatlo ka words sa Hiligaynon daw kabudlay siya, lain lain pa ang meaning sina. Contextualize lang ang tinaga” (There are words that we understand in English but we need to contextualize it so that the public will better understand it. In the Hiligaynon language, there are some words that are difficult because they are not specific in English. Sometimes a word in English has two or three equivalent words in Hiligaynon with different meanings. We just need to contextualize the word.)</p>		
<p>“I think it is the role of the CDRRMO OpCen nga intindihon ina siya ang Science and then simplify that information kay again if we are tasked to communicate that information and we do not understand that information, how can you expect the public nga intindihon siya and to take action.” (I think the role of the CDRRMO OpCen is to understand the Science behind it and simplify that information. If we are tasked to communicate that information and we do not understand it, how much more is the public?)</p>	<p>Simplification</p>	
<p>“ang pagsimplify gid siguro sang messaging” (It is really about the simplification of the messaging.)</p>		

<p>“Karun gin-coaching nila kami sa Takas, ginsimplify pa gid nila sa Takas amo to ya ang pinakanami ...ang nag-attend to kapitan, kagawad kag treasurer” (They coached us in Baragay Takas, they simplified it and that is what I like. The punong barangay, barangay kagawad, and treasurer attended that training)</p>		

Table 4 illustrates the various strategies employed by the Iloilo City Government in localizing the language in their communication of its Early Warning System.

C. Inclusive Early Warning System

The third theme is the Inclusive Early Warning System. While the primary target audience of Iloilo City Government in their communication of their EWS is the general public, they also have developed various IEC materials that fosters inclusivity and diversity.

Reportedly, the primary target audience of the PIO is the general population. If there is a hazard or disaster, the practice is that they are the ones aiding the vulnerable sectors like the senior citizens and Persons with Disability. The strategies implemented by Iloilo City Government in their aspiration to achieve an inclusive Early Warning System are the following:

(1) Use of early warnings for the visually impaired such as the creation of the communication board for the deaf and mute, and the integration of a sign interpreter in their early warning message;

(2) Use of early warning for those who have hearing impairment. The communication strategies under this include the use of Public Address System, *rikorida*, and the audio recordings for the alert system for flooding;

(3) Development of IEC materials for specific sectors, and;

(4) Use of multimodal communication (social media, traditional media, non-mainstream popular media, and interpersonal communication).

Table 5.

Inclusive Early Warning System in the Localization of Early Warning System in Iloilo City

Response	Code	Theme
“ang pinaka-latest namon nga gin-obra ang communication boards...knowing nga ang mga responders naton cannot communicate with the mute and there is a recognition nga emergency situation ini siya. We based on the experience with Japan, nakita sang mga PWDs naton, it might work nga kon indi ka kabalo sang sign languages naton. Tudlo-tudlo ka nalang.”	Early Warnings for the visually-impaired (Use of	Inclusive Early Warning System

<p>(The latest innovation that we have is the creation of the communication boards. Knowing that the responders cannot communicate with the deaf and mute and there is a recognition that they might also be in an emergency situation. Based on our experience with Japan, we have a PWD staff who went there. So if you do not know how to sign language, you can just use the communication board)</p>	<p>communication board and sign interpreter)</p>	
<p>“so subong may ara sila sintra board, communication board for the deaf and mute, itudlo niya lang kon ano, is he bleeding, hungry, ukon ano.” (So right now we have this sintra board, a communication board for the deaf and mute. They will just point the words on the board such as if they are feeling hungry or experiencing bleeding)</p>		
<p>“Pero that particular video, nalipay kami ah it works. So kon indi man siya mga advisories, may iban kami, ginabutangan namon sang sign language interpreter” (That particular video was posted on our Facebook page about a typhoon, we were happy because it works. If we cannot integrate it in our advisories, there are some where we integrate a sign language interpreter.)</p>		
<p>“Huo, amo to gani ang istorya ko, “maam nagtunog na siya, nagtunog na”. Naga-inform sila kag not just in Calubijan ha, sa tanan nga kabarangayan kay again ang kada district may focal person so may ano na sila, may chatgroup.” (That is what I am talking about, “maam, it sounded already (flood monitoring system in Barangay Calubijan, Jaro). They are informing us and this is not just in Calubihan, but all the barangays because again in every district, we have our own focal person. They also have a chatgroup)</p>	<p>Early warnings for those who have hearing impairment (Use of audio materials for the alert warnings)</p>	
<p>“malab-ot siya sang PA namon” (It can be reached by our Public Address System)</p>		
<p>“galing kay ang tumpa na namon general man mo...before nga mag-abot kon ano mana da, kinahanglan mapaguwa kana da sang imo nga communication sa mga tawo te ang amon diri may ari kami diri nga trumpa, ginapaandar na siya namon.” (We have our trumpa but we are using it for general information...before a disaster occurs, we have to release information to the public. We are using our trumpa for that)</p>		
<p>“yes, sila ang nagagamit sa barangay, when we had the BNEO (Barangay Newly Elected Officials) last year, ang pinaka-effective daw sa ila is ang rikorida or ang Public</p>		

<p>Address System so ang mga materials namon nga ginpanghatag sa ila ginagamit nila, maglwag-lawag”</p> <p>(When we had the Barangay Newly Elected Officials meeting last year, they expressed that the most effective means to communication is through the rikorida or the Public Address System. So we just give them the materials and they are the ones disseminating it)</p>		
<p>“specific kon ano ang ubrahon sang mga tigulang” (We produced IEC materials for senior citizens, these are specific to what they need to do during disasters)</p>	<p>IEC materials for a specific sector</p>	
<p>“As long as naga-work ang Viber, ang radyo, ang handheld radios, ang mga Messenger nila nga groups, makalab-ot gid ina up to the last mile kay amo ina siya ang mga barangays naton, they have this Public Address System nga once mabaton nila, ang iba na gina-announce nila.” (As long as the Viber is working as well as the radio frequency, the Messenger group chats, the information can reach up to the last mile of the barangays. And they also have the Public Address System, once they receive the information, they announce it.)</p>	<p>Use of multimodal communication</p>	
<p>“We evolved from pure texts nag-include na kami sang mga drawings , sang mga cartoons, kag komiks nga approach para maintindihan nila. For example sang una bullets lang ini tanan subong ginhimo namon checklist box. Para interactive ang unod sang libro and this was designed actually nga pwede mo ini pukSION in the middle kag itapik sa dingding” (We evolved from pure texts, we now include drawings, cartoons, and even comics. This approach is for them to understand it. For example before, we were just using bullets, now we have integrated the checklist box so that it will be interactive. For example in a guidebook, it is designed in a way that you can just pull the middle sheet and post it on your wall. This sheet of paper contains the checklist during a typhoon.)</p>		
<p>“Bali ano si City, si OpCen, Operation Center na ga-send sang message sa akon diri tapos ako, ang message na halin nana sa ila. Tapos ako tungod kay may pito nga kagawad, may group chat kami, i-send ko na sa council nga group chat. Tapos si kagawad in-charge, ang kada zone na bal-an sir, may group chat mana, i-send yaman na didto” (The City through the OpCen or Operation Center sends me the message then I just send it to our group chat with my seven barangay kagawads, then I will call the kagawad-in-charge per zone, they also have their own group chat.)</p>		
<p>“Oftentimes, always gid na nga gina-channel nila sa amon ang ila nga communication pakadto sa amon mga networks tapos</p>		

<p>ginahaboy man ina namon sa amon nga mga networks ang information nga ginahatag nila sa amon galing kay te bal-an mo naman subong iya with the advent sang social media sometimes una nila post sa ila nga page kag ipasa sa amon for wider dissemination”</p> <p>(Oftentime, the Iloilo City Government sends us the information for our report in our respective networks. We share it to our networks however with the advent of social media, sometimes they post it first on their social media account than tap us for information dissemination)</p>		
---	--	--

Table 5 presents the various strategies of Iloilo City to develop and implement an inclusive Early Warning System. These strategies are either directed to the general population or to the concerned specific sector.

D. Strengthened Community Resilience

The fourth and last theme is the Strengthened Community Resilience. This is anchored on the four elements of the Early Warning System. With Iloilo City Government’s localization of its EWS, their common goal of strengthening their community resilience is achieved through the following:

(1)**Increased Risk Knowledge** of the community through the various sectors part of the communication of the EWS. Their participation especially in the activities related to Risk Knowledge increases their knowledge and understanding about the hazards in their area and what they can do to mitigate its possible negative impact;

(2)**Streamlined and Coordinated Monitoring Services.** Because the communication of EWS does not only fall under the responsibility of the Iloilo City Government, the institutionalization of a localized EWS sets the overall framework and ensures that everybody is involved in the process. It is established at various levels and with the use of various platforms to ensure the redundancy of the delivery of the early warnings;

(3) Effective Risk Communication. In localizing the communication of the EWS, a better risk communication is observed. In the recent Global Platform for Disaster Risk Reduction by the UNDRR (2025), it was revealed that trust and localization are fundamentals for effective risk communication. It further highlighted that without these, even the most advanced warning systems can fail to translate into early actions. Iloilo City Government’s risk communication is also not just centered around the LGU as the source of the information. The role of the various stakeholders is also highlighted not just as passive receivers of the information; and

(4) Early Response Time. Because the EWS is institutionalized in various levels and is apparent both in the mechanism and the language, the response time needed, should a need arise, is also shortened. Response is done on the onset or while the disaster is already happening. The early warnings as translated in the early actions of the public transpire before a disaster strikes, this results in the prevention and mitigation of the possible negative impact of a disaster.

Table 6.

Strengthened Community Resilience in the Localization of Early Warning System in Iloilo City

Response	Code	Theme
“Again the formula of the disaster risk, hazard + exposure + vulnerabilities. Kay usually ang gina-istoryahan nila hazards, wlaa ni si exposure and vulnerability. So part sang pag-communicate sa ila ang pag-highlight especially sa barangay leaders kon ano ang vulnerability. Nga-a, amo ni ang naga-cause, sila ni exposure, amo ini ang nagadetermine sa level of risk mo sa particular hazard. That is why, if they understand kon ano nag interplay sang tatlo nga ini then they will also understand where you will invest your money. Kay di ba, we have to reduce	Increased risk knowledge	Strengthened Community Resilience

<p>our vulnerabilities. So focus kita sa vulnerability reduction strategies , so that is the secret.” (Again the formula of the disaster risk, hazard + exposure + vulnerabilities because usually in the barangay level, they just talk about the hazards, there is no discussion about the exposure and vulnerability. So part of our communication to them is to highlight especially among the barangay officials about the vulnerability. That this is their hazard, and they are exposed to it, this will determine their risk to that particular hazard. That is why, if they understand the interplay among the three elements, they will know where to invest their money.)</p>		
<p>“Paano siya kaimplement kon ang iya background appreciation indi bala amo na swak dira?” (How can the punong barangay implement the various DRRM strategies of his background and appreciation to it is not enough?)</p>		
<p>“Syempre makahimo ka sang imo nga , makadevice ka sang imo nga plano on how you make yourself safe sa mga hazards...so if everybody nabal-an nila kon ano ang hazards, makabalo sila magprotect sang ila kaugalingon” (Of course you can devise strategies on how to make yourself safe from hazards. So if everybody knows the hazards around them, they would know how to protect themselves as well)</p>		
<p>“di ba RA 10121 says that barangay should organize its own Barangay DRRM Committee. So in every barangay, nag-establish man kami sang barangay Operation Center. So from the city level, amo na siya manaog ina siya deretso sa barangay...kon basehan mo lang kon may bagyo and all, may nagasululod nga mga reports then you would know nga amo ina pero I do not think may consciousness, kamalayan ang mga barangay nga OpCen kami pero gafunction siya as monitoring and relaying the information” (Under the RA 10121, the barangay should organize its own Barangay DRRM Committee. So in every barangay, we have established their barangay Operation Center. So from the city level, it will go down to the barangays. If you will base when there is a typhoon, they are submitting reports but I think that they have the consciousness that what they are doing is part of their barangay OpCen. However, they function already for the monitoring and relaying information)</p>	<p>Streamlined and Coordinated Monitoring Services</p>	
<p>“Tapos amo na be ang message halin sa city kundi ginhaboy sa akon, ginhaboy ko sa council, nagapaaman gid ko na dayon sa council nga monitor ta ang aton nga creek kon nagataas ukon wala, monitor ta ang mga tawo ta kay daw halos sir saulo namon diri sa Buntatala kun diin example abi may ulan may bagyo kita nga paabuton ukon nagaulan na abi. Mahaboy na bi si city sa amon, tapos mahaboy ko na sa council, may paaman gid na</p>		

<p>dayon sa akon nga ulualigmat, monitor ang aton sa masami nga ginabahaan nga pamalay kon nagasaka ang tubi tapos amo na, sila nagahaboy mana sila ara da sa palibot sa mga vulnerable areas na da naton, nagahboy mana sila, naga-monitor mana sila nga mga kagawad”</p> <p>(For example the city will share an information to me, I immediately share it to my council, I advise them as well to monitor our creek and our constituents. I also advise the families who are always the victims of flooding to be prepared and continue to monitor the situation. They monitor and also report to us, the barangay kagawads are also monitoring.)</p>		
<p>“kon may ara te gina-feed namon halimbawa may mga instances sang nagligad nga grabe ang hangin, natumba ang nga kahoy kay te indi man sa tanan nga oras makita nila no so kon kay te bal-an dasig magpadala sa mga media outlets so kami mismo nagapadala sang information, natumba nga poste, nabugto nga kuryente mga kahoy. Kami mismo nagabulig kami share sang information sa ila kag sometimes, kon i-ano mo bala imatch mo sa ila data mahambal sila nga tapos na pero kon kaisa maoverlook na so gabulig kami sa pagremind sa ila which is good man kay partnership man kita”</p> <p>(We also feed the city information for example about a fallen post or an uprooted tree. We help them by sharing these pieces of information. This is to also match their data because sometimes they might overlook some information. Through this, we are reminding them, this is actually good as part of our partnership.)</p>		
<p>“If we have to communicate the risk, again ma build on ka sa risk knowledge mo right?but to analyze the data, may bagyo ka di ba, they have the scientific information from PAGASA, Manila Observatory, other available data from the different websites. Once they have that, it is the role of the OpCen to analyze what does it mean for the barangays of Iloilo City. So kon amo ni kabaskog, amo ni ang time nga maabot, diri nga direction, ano nga mga barangays ang high risk?So it is the role of the OpCen to communicate the risk pero ang channel where you will throw all those information ginapaagi kay BDRRMS namon kay at the barangay level, ang gina-obra namon sir”</p> <p>(If we have to communicate the risk, again that is built on the risk knowledge. We use the scientific information from PAGASA, Manila Observatory and other available sources to analyze the data. Once they have it, it is the role of the OpCen to analyze its implication to the barangays here in Iloilo City. For example, the typhoon would be this strong and it will reach by this time, so these are the barangays that are at-risk.)</p>	<p>Effective risk communication</p>	
<p>“so we cannot influence people to do preemptive evacuation or early action because garbage in and garbage out, we also fail to communicate nga amo sini ang posible matabo. So ang siling ko pirme sa staff. Ang trabaho naton, we are several steps ahead of them. Kon si Sec. Solidom, disaster imagination so creating a</p>		

<p>common operating scenario matters gid ina siya. Kay kon indi mo maimagine ang pwede nga matabo, ano nga actions ang pwede mo maguide sa mga tawo”</p> <p>(So we cannot influence people to do preemptive evacuation or early action because garbage in, garbage out, we fail to communicate the possible scenarios. What I always tell my staff is for them to always be several steps ahead. According to Sec. Solidom, disaster imagination, we need to create a common operating scenario because it matters. If you cannot imagine what might happen, how can you guide the public?)</p>		
<p>“te for IEC sa barangays, siguro mabulig sa pagpaintindi sa mga tawo kon ano ang gina-atubang nila nga mga katalagman...may amo ni gali ang city nga programa, at least it helps, it helps them prepare.”</p> <p>(For our IEC Campaigns in the barangay, we can help for them to understand the hazards that they are facing...these programs help them prepare)</p>		
<p>“actually ako nakita ko dapat pa ako gali dapat matun-an, sa disaster risk reporting. Kadugay na sa akon sa media pero I need to learn a lot pa. Agud nga mangin effective ang reporting kag delivery sang information sa publiko... Amo na nga kinahanglan gid ang effective communicator in terms sa pag-deliver sang preparedness and response sang isa ka LGU”</p> <p>(Actually I have realized that I have to learn a lot about disaster risk reporting. I have been here in the media industry for quite some time but I still need to learn a lot. This is for me to become an effective in reporting and delivering information to the public...an effective communicator is needed in terms of delivering the preparedness and response of an LGU)</p>		
<p>“we want nga Iloilo is a place where everybody feels secured living here I think we can only do that if we develop that culture of safety, resilience, sa tanan indi bala and that can only happen kon ang mga pumuluyo naton nakabalo kon ano ang ubrahon. They know what to do before, during, and after the disaster and at the same time, they do activities to prevent the onset of the disasters.”</p> <p>(We want Iloilo to be a place where everybody feels secure living here. I think we can only do that if we develop that culture of safety, resilience. That can only happen if everybody knows what to do before, during, and after a disaster. At the same time, they also do activities to prevent the onset of the disaster.)</p>	<p>Early response time</p>	
<p>“Sa communication, OpCen sila na gihapon kag balik gid kita sa barangay sang amon nga I-CARE (Iloilo City Action and Response Centers). So amo ina siya. Dayun sa response capability, under the Response Division sa gihapon amo na ina ang ICER, USAR, as you can see indi lang ni isa ka section.”</p>		

<p>(We always go back to the barangays for our I-CARE(Iloilo City Action and Response Centers). For our response capability, under the Response Division, we have the ICER (Iloilo City Emergency Responders), USAR (Urban Search and Rescue Team). As you can see, it is not just one section.)</p>		
<p>“sila mismo bal-an nila, sila mismo nagaarak ang message sa kagawad sa BHW, sa akon gaarak na ya, “kap gataas ang tubig”, Sige na bakwit na, kadto na diri”” (The residents know if they need to evacuate already, messages to me and the barangay kagawad and tanods are just popping, they are informing us that the water in the creek is already high thus they need to evacuate.)</p>		
<p>“for the localization I think ang the best thing that we could do with that is faster response time, and then more there will be more community nga ma-tap since if we put it in a localize nga setting indi lang tanan nga tawo daw wala sila labot because in a localized setting they will be responsible in their areas and then of course smart cities and safety communities will be there” (For the localization, I think the best thing that we could do with that is faster response time, and then, there will be more communities which can be tapped. If we put it in a localized setting, some do not mind this. So in a localized setting, they will be responsible in their areas.)</p>		

Table 6 presents the building and strengthening of community resilience in Iloilo City in the localization of the Early Warning System. The participants expressed that this strategy is reflected and can be measured in the four elements of EWS.

Applying the salient principles of participatory communication in this research, the *dialogue* is what transpires within and among the various stakeholders in the overall operationalization and communication of the EWS in the city. The specific stakeholders that the City Government through the City Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office (CDRRMO) and Public Information Office (PIO) collaborates with are the following: punong barangay, the Department of Interior and Local Government, Civil Society Organizations, academe, and media among others. The *dialogue*

transpires in the overall process, from the development of the EWS until its implementation, and recalibration before, during, and after the onslaught of a disaster.

The *voice* refers to the voices of the various stakeholders as they are involved in the operationalization and communication of the EWS. Since the various stakeholders have a representation in the development and implementation of the EWS, everybody has an equal opportunity to contribute or critique it. These are expressed both in formal and informal engagements of the various stakeholders in the development and implementation of the EWS.

On the other hand, the *Liberating Pedagogy* is observed in the dialogues as all sectors have their voice on the development and communication of the EWS. In addition, the CDRRMO serves as the *catalyst* of the localization efforts. As the *catalyst*, it spearheads the development and implementation of a localized EWS as it is part of their primary responsibilities.

Lastly, the *Action-Reflection-Action* is the ultimate means to measure if the early warnings are translated into the early actions of the public. After the early warnings are properly disseminated through the use of various channels, the public are equipped to have informed and guided actions. The right information delivered correctly, fastly, and with redundancy would eventually translate into the right actions of the populace, mitigating the possible negative effect of a disaster.

For the social mobilization framework, the City Government mobilizes as many stakeholders as possible to localize the communication of its EWS. These various stakeholders have their own specific efforts and initiatives in ensuring that the early warnings are received by the members of their respective communities.

Incorporating the salient principles of the theory of participatory communication to the strategic elements of social mobilization ensures that the communication of a

localized EWS is responsive, inclusive, and sustainable. It is responsive to the specific needs of the public because they are part of the development and implementation of it. The active involvement of the various stakeholders make it also inclusive and diverse, responding to the specific needs as well of the concerned sector. Lastly, it is sustainable because it employs a participatory approach. The active involvement of the public, through the various stakeholders, will make the communication of EWS lasting.

Therefore, based on the results of this study, the researcher develops a modified framework illustrating how the Local Government Units can employ participatory communication and social mobilization in the localization of its Early Warning System. Incorporating the theory of participatory communication in the framework of social mobilization ensures that all stakeholders involved in the communication of EWS are part of the overall process. In addition, it also empowers the stakeholders not only as mere beneficiaries or end-users of the information but as active participants and contributors in the overall development and implementation of the EWS.

Figure 3.

Modified Framework of Theory of Participatory Communication and Social Mobilization in the Communication of a Localized Early Warning System

Note. Based on the *Communication and Social Marketing* by Ling (1991) as cited by Velasco et al., (1999). UP Open University

Based on the results of this study, the following propositions are evaluated:

Proposition 1: The City Government localizes the communication of its Early Warning System

The study revealed that the City Government localizes the communication of its Early Warning System with and through the aid of the various stakeholders inside and outside of the Local Government Unit. This is institutionalized to ensure functionality and sustainability while fostering inclusivity and diversity.

Proposition 2: The localization of the Early Warning System empowers the various stakeholders in the locality by building and strengthening its community resilience.

Results of the study showed that the localization of the Early Warning System strengthens the community resilience as it empowers the various sectors in the society as a sector and as part of the larger community in the context of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management. The strengthened community resilience is achieved because the various sectors have increased risk knowledge, streamlined and coordinated monitoring services, effective risk communication, and early response time. The localization of the EWS enabled the public to have early action, this lessened or mitigated the negative impacts of the disaster or risk to them.

In summary, both propositions are supported by the findings of the study that highlights the role and impact of participatory communication and social mobilization in the localization of EWS in a community. In addition, the findings of the study illustrated the vital role of the Local Government Unit as the lead implementer or the catalyst, and the active support and involvement of the various stakeholders to achieve the common goal.

The public is not just mere beneficiaries or end-users of any development program, they are active agents and great contributors. Their participation makes any program inclusive, diverse, and sustainable.

CHAPTER V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

The question that this qualitative research tries to answer was: How does the City Government communicate its Early Warning System? Its objectives are (1) to describe the City Government's process of communicating its Early Warning System, (2) to determine the most common hazards communicated by the City Government, and (3) to determine the strategies and challenges in communication of the EWS.

This study reveals that the City Government is the source of information in the communication of the early warnings. Aside from their own generated data and analysis, they also utilize the information from various sources such as the Government Agencies, monitoring stations, and the community itself. The information from these institutions are not just disseminated as it is because the City Government, through the City Disaster Risk Reduction and Management and Public Information Office, processes it first to ensure that it is fitting to the locality. It also uses various communication channels to disseminate information depending on the urgency and severity of the matter, and on its practicality. Moreover, the City Government mainly communicates its natural hazards. While the top and imminent hazards in the locality are natural like flooding and typhoons, human-induced hazards such as armed conflict and terrorism must also be considered to prepare for any eventualities. This study also highlights the significance of the various strategies and challenges experienced by the City Government in the localization of the Early Warning System. The City Government, as the institution tasked to develop and operate its Early Warning

System, employs various localization strategies. It did not only rely on the traditional media but also maximized the potential of other channels like the new media and non-mainstream media. It is also worth noting that the interpersonal communication and mediated communication are continued as the most fundamental and dependable means for information dissemination. The key findings of this research revolve around the localization efforts of the City Government in the development and communication of its Early Warning System. These efforts extend beyond language to encompass the intricate mechanisms and multi-level collaborations in place, involving various stakeholders to achieve the common goal of building and strengthening community resilience. The City Government is also employing a responsive, inclusive, and sustainable Early Warning System as the various sectors in the community are actively participating, collaborating, and implementing it. There are challenges in the implementation, especially that most of their strategies are just newly implemented, but these are already considered and the City Government along with the various sectors are trying to respond to it. Other constraints pertaining to the sufficiency of resources, harmonization of efforts, and capacity building among others are also being analyzed and addressed.

Generally, this research underscores the vital role of participatory communication and social mobilization in empowering the community, both in its parts per sector or on its totality as a whole. Through participatory communication and social mobilization, the role of the Local Government Unit as the lead implementer of the project is highlighted. However, aside from the “catalyst” or lead, the success of the project also lies in the active involvement and contribution of the various stakeholders supporting it. This study illustrates the vital role of the various stakeholders because

they are viewed not just as beneficiaries or end users but as an integral part in the development and implementation of it.

Conclusion

The Local Government Units (LGUs) are mandated to operationalize its Early Warning System (EWS), however, due to the multitude of concerns, political dynamics, and subjective priorities of the local leaders, it is often overlooked as revealed by previous researches and the narratives of the participants of this study. In addition, there is no specific National Government Agency that strictly monitors and evaluates the operationalization and communication of EWS. The findings in this qualitative research revealed that City Government has operationalized its EWS and its localization efforts are an innovation as it continues to serve as a trailblazer in Disaster Risk Reduction and Management.

With the increasing hazards as exacerbated by climate change, early warnings play a vital role: early warning could translate to early action. Ultimately, it could mitigate the possible negative impacts, saving lives and properties, and even the environment.

The City Government's localization of its EWS does not only pertain to the language used, it is also integrated in the mechanisms being implemented from the city down to the barangays as well as being linked to other stakeholders. The role of the City Government through the City Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office and the Public Information Office is also vital as it sets the overall strategy and objective. However, it is not just about them but the other stakeholders who actively support and contribute in the development and implementation of it.

Through participatory communication and social mobilization, the City Government institutionalized the vital role of the stakeholders in the localization of the EWS. As active members, they are part of the overall process and their support is fundamental in the materialization of the project. This approach inculcates and ensures inclusivity, diversity, and sustainability of the project. It is inclusive and diverse because it enables and empowers the various stakeholders to be part of the process, their active participation will then make the program sustainable.

The mentioned localization efforts as reflected in the various elements of EWS; (1) increased risk knowledge of the public, (2) streamlined and coordinated monitoring services, (3) effective risk communication, and (4) quick response time — which all geared towards building and strengthening community resilience.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher has the following recommendations:

A.) For the Local Government Unit

1.) Local Chief Executive/s

- to continue supporting the localization of the EWS through the provision of sufficient budget, strict implementation, and strategic monitoring and evaluation of the effectiveness of the localized mechanisms and strategies in communicating the EWS

2.) Policymakers

- to pass ordinances and resolutions that supports the localization of EWS such as the mandatory use of the radio frequency in the barangays to ensure communication even during disasters, and

the mandatory evacuation of the residents if there is an imminent disaster

3.) CDRRMO

- to continue the lead in implementing the localization of the EWS with and through the active support and participation of the other offices and institutions in the Local Government Unit, as well as the external stakeholders
- to consistently implement their innovative strategies like the incorporation of a sign interpreter in an audio-visual output and the use of communication boards for the deaf and mute as it fosters inclusivity, ensuring that no one is left behind in the communication of EWS.

4.) PIO

- to continue implementing their innovative strategies like the use of legacy media, new media, and non-mainstream media in their IEC campaign
- to work closely with the Iloilo City Press Corps, academe, DRRM practitioners, experts, and other stakeholders in the development of a guide for disaster reporting to ensure accuracy and consistency in reporting in a localized level and manner

B.) For the stakeholders

- to adapt the localization efforts of the Iloilo City Government in the operationalization and communication of its EWS

- to recommend other possible interventions to harmonize and standardize the operationalization and communication of EWS by actively participating in the planning sessions in the barangay and the sharing of best practices during stakeholders' dialogue

C.) For DRRM practitioners

- To study and evaluate the localization of EWS in Iloilo City and its applicability in other areas
- To implement the framework of participatory communication and social mobilization in the development and implementation of their program especially on Disaster Risk Reduction and Management

D.) For DILG, DOST, and other concerned NGAs

- To develop a framework and guidelines in the development, implementation, and communication of the LGUs of a responsive, inclusive, and sustainable Early Warning System
- To evaluate the responsiveness, inclusiveness, and sustainability of the Early Warning System of the LGUs and its harmonization in the various levels of governance

E.) For future researchers

- To expand the scope of the research in other LGUs especially in the most-at risk communities, evaluating the similarities and differences in the communication process from the national, regional, municipal, city, and down to the barangay levels
- To also conduct other research that is focused on the public's level of Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice on the

operationalization and communication of Early Warning System. This will capture the baseline data which is crucial for developing and refining strategies in communicating EWS. In addition, it can triangulate the validity of the data which was captured from previous research.

REFERENCES

- Aguirre-Ayerbe, I., Aye, S.L., Dissanayake, R., Lopez, C.M., Merino, M., & Shadiya, F. (2020). *An evaluation of availability and adequacy of multi-hazard early warning systems in Asian countries: A baseline study. International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction, Volume 49, 9-10.*
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2212420920302582>
- Akerkar, S., Ayers, J., Boswell, C., DeCoster, M., Jimerson, A., & Woodside Alegre, L. (2020). *Early Warning for Early Action: Toward More Behaviorally Informed Early Warning Systems.* Washington, DC: Resilience Evaluation, Analysis and Learning (REAL) Associate Award.
https://www.resiliencelinks.org/system/files/documents/2020-11/fh-real_ews_november_2020_final_508_0.pdf
- ASEAN (2022). *ASEAN framework on anticipatory action in disaster management.*
<https://asean.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/ASEAN-Framework-on-Anticipatory-Action-in-Disaster-Management.pdf>
- Asian Development Bank. (2018). *Natural disasters, public spending, and creative destruction: A case study of the Philippines.*
<https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/publication/408351/adbi-wp817.pdf>
- Assistance and Cooperation for Community Resilience and Development. (2020). *Community-Based Early Warning System: Learning from Saint Bernard, Southern Leyte.* https://resilientphilippines.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/Community-Based-Early-Warning-System_Learning-from-Saint-Bernard-Southern-Leyte.pdf

- Balunday, J.B. (2017). *Communicating risks: Factors influencing Filipinos living in high-risk areas to follow pre-emptive evacuation procedures.*
<http://rizalls.lib.admu.edu.ph/#section=resource&resourceid=1397710984¤tIndex=0&view=fullDetailsDetailsTab>
- Canela, JCB., Estrella, M.R., Fullero, KCS., & Valenzuela G.C. (2024). *Risk communication in disaster-prone areas in Caramoan, Camarines Sur, Philippines. International Journal of Research and Review, Volume 11, Issues 6.* https://www.ijrrjournal.com/IJRR_Vol.11_Issue.6_June2024/IJRR84.pdf
- Clark, H., Fakhrudin, B., & Hieber-Girardet, L. (2020). *Should I stay or should I go now? Why risk communication is the critical component in disaster risk reduction.* *Progress in Disaster Science* 8 (2020) 10039.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2590061720300764>
- COP (2023). *UN Climate Change Conference- United Arab Emirates.*
<https://unfccc.int/cop28>
- Daily Guardian (2019). *Iloilo City tops resiliency competitiveness ranking.*
<https://dailyguardian.com.ph/iloilo-city-tops-resiliency-competitiveness-ranking/>
- DILG (2018). *Local Government Unit Disaster Preparedness Manual for City and Municipal LGUs.*
<https://lga.gov.ph/uploads/publication/attachments/1590478478.pdf>
- Domingo, S.D & Manejar, A.J.A. (2018). *Disaster preparedness and local governance in the Philippines.* Discussion Paper Series No. 2018-52.
<https://pidswebs.pids.gov.ph/CDN/PUBLICATIONS/pidsdps1852.pdf>

DOST (2023). *DOST-PAGASA launches the multi-hazard impact-based forecasting and EWS*. <https://www.pagasa.dost.gov.ph/press-release/135>

Flor, A.G. & Smith, R.P. (1997). *Transformational Communication*.
https://www.academia.edu/178960/Transformational_Communication

Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (2021). *Anticipatory action: Changing the way we manage disasters*.
<https://openknowledge.fao.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/3b7726e4-55f7-4d9c-b8e5-b842e12f9a1b/content>

GIZ (2012). *Local Flood Early Warning System*.
https://www.preventionweb.net/files/globalplatform/entry_bg_paper~gizphilippineslocalfloodearlyw.pdf

GSMA (2022). *Early Warning Systems in the Philippines: Building resilience through mobile and digital technologies*.
https://www.gsma.com/mobilefordevelopment/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/PhilippinesEWS_R_Web.pdf

IFRC (2020). *People centered early warning systems: Learning from National Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies*. <https://www.ifrc.org/document/people-centred-early-warning-systems>

Iloilo City Government (2020). *Climate and Disaster Risk Assessment: Iloilo City*.
https://iloilocity.gov.ph/main/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/CDRA-Report_IC-2021-2029.pdf

Iloilo City Government (n.d.). Barangays- Iloilo City.

https://iloilocity.gov.ph/wp_iloilo/barangays/

Iloilo City Government (n.d.). Iloilo Achievements.

https://iloilocity.gov.ph/wp_iloilo/achievements/

Iloilo City Government (n.d.). Learn more about the City of Iloilo.

https://iloilocity.gov.ph/wp_iloilo/the-city/

Iloilo City Population Office (n.d.) *PHILIPPINES: Iloilo City*.

<https://www.citypopulation.de/en/philippines/iloilo/>

Inquirer.net (2024). *NDRRRMC: Reported deaths due to Kristine climb to 146*.

<https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/2000515/ndrrmc-reported-deaths-due-to-kristine-climb-to-146>

Ling, J. (2007). Social Mobilization. A process model based on UNICEF's experience.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/291972880_Social_Mobilization_A_process_model_based_on_UNICEF's_experience

Littlejohn, S.M., Foss, K.A., & Oetzel, J.G. (2017). *Theories of Human Communication* (Eleventh Edition). Waveland Press, Inc.

https://books.google.com.ph/books?id=yJ32DQAAQBAJ&printsec=frontcover&source=gbs_ge_summary_r&cad=0#v=onepage&q&f=false

Mead, L. (2022). *Disaster Risk Reduction in an Unstable World*.

<https://www.iisd.org/system/files/2022-05/still-one-earth-disaster-risk-reduction.pdf>

Mina, K., Shuichi, K. Yasuhito, J. & Yuichi, O. (2015). *Analysis of early warning systems: The case of super-typhoon Haiyan*. International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction.

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2212420915301771>

NDRRMC (2022). *Situational Report for TC Paeng (2022)*. https://monitoring-dashboard.ndrrmc.gov.ph/assets/uploads/situations/Summary_Table1.pdf

NDRRMC (2020). National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Plan (NDRRMP) 2020-2030.

<https://ndrrmc.gov.ph/attachments/article/4147/NDRRMP-Pre-Publication-Copy-v2.pdf>

OCD (n.d.). *Office of Civil Defense order local disaster officials to “localize, laymanize” typhoon data*.

<https://www.facebook.com/share/p/Tr4M6CKJKsg5k6Ly/>

Ocon, G. & Neussner, O. (2015). *Assessing early warning efforts for Typhoon Haiyan in Leyte*. <https://odihpn.org/publication/assessing-early-warning-efforts-for-typhoon-haiyan-in-leyte/>

Official Gazette of the Philippines (2009). *Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act of 2010*.

<https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2010/05/27/republic-act-no-10121/>

Oscar M. Lopez Center for Climate Change Adaptation and Disaster Management Foundation, Inc. (2024). *Policy Brief #5. The climate realities of the deaf: Evidence from a climate vulnerability assessment of the Filipino Deaf Community*.

<https://www.preventionweb.net/media/96046/download?startDownload=20241>

PDC (2022). *New early warning system aids rapid response to life-threatening landslides in Philippines*. <https://www.pdc.org/new-early-warning-system-aids-rapid-response-to-life-threatening-landslides-in-philippines/>

PNA (2024). *PCO works to improve communication protocols during disasters*. <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1231404>

Polman, J.L. & Pea, R.D. (2000). *Transformative communication as a cultural tool for guiding inquiry science*. https://web.stanford.edu/~roypea/RoyPDF%20folder/A104_Polman_Pea_01.pdf

Prakash Subedi, K. (2022). *Participatory Communication for Development and Social Change*. Socio Economy and Policy Studies (SEPS). <http://doi.org/10.26480/seps.02.2022.57.60>

Senate (2017). *Examining the Philippines's Disaster Risk Reduction and Management System*. https://legacy.senate.gov.ph/publications/SEPO/PB_Examining%20PH%20DRR%20System_Revised_27June2017.pdf

Stewart, I.S. (2024). *Advancing disaster risk communications*. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0012825224000047>

Thomson, J. (2019). *The First and Last Mile: Rural communities' management of evolving disaster risk and the implications for preparedness in Disaster Risk Reduction*. <https://opus.lib.uts.edu.au/handle/10453/140908>

Tufte, T. & Mefalolupos, P. (2009). *Participatory Communication: A Practical Guide*.
The World Bank.

https://www.poliokit.org/sites/default/files/migrate/Participatory_communication_a_practical_guide_.pdf

UN (2016). *Report of the open-ended intergovernmental expert working group on indicators and terminology relating to disaster risk reduction*.

https://www.preventionweb.net/files/50683_oiewgreportenglish.pdf?_gl=1*1kwgulo*_ga*MTE5NzkxMTIyOS4xNjk1MzEwMjM0*_ga_D8G5WXP6YM*MTcwMzY5MTIzNi4yLjEuMTcwMzY5MTU4My4wLjAuMA

UN (2022). *Early warnings for all: Executive Action Plan*.

<https://www.preventionweb.net/publication/early-warnings-all-executive-action-plan-2023-2027>

UN (2023). *The Sustainable Development Goals Report Special edition*.

<https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/report/2023/The-Sustainable-Development-Goals-Report-2023.pdf>

UNDRR (2023). *First Report of the advisory panel of the Early Warnings for All Initiative to the United Nations Secretary-General*.

<https://www.undrr.org/media/91943/download?startDownload=true>

UNDRR (2023). *Global Status of Multi-Hazard Early Warning Systems 2023*.

<https://www.undrr.org/media/91954/download?startDownload=true>

UNDRR (n.d.) *Hazard definition*.

<https://www.undrr.org/terminology/hazard#:~:text=A%20process%2C%20phe>

nomenon%20or%20human,anthropogenic%20or%20socionatural%20in%20o
rigin.

UNDRR (n.d.). *Early warning system definition.*

[https://www.undrr.org/terminology/early-warning-
system#:~:text=An%20integrated%20system%20of%20hazard,in%20advanc
e%20of%20hazardous%20events.](https://www.undrr.org/terminology/early-warning-system#:~:text=An%20integrated%20system%20of%20hazard,in%20advance%20of%20hazardous%20events.)

UNDRR(n.d.) *Anticipatory action.* [https://www.preventionweb.net/understanding-
disaster-risk/key-concepts/anticipatory-action](https://www.preventionweb.net/understanding-disaster-risk/key-concepts/anticipatory-action)

UNISDR (2006). *Developing Early Warning Systems: A Checklist.*

<https://www.unisdr.org/2006/ppew/info-resources/ewc3/checklist/English.pdf>

UNISDR (2009). *2009 UNISDR Terminology on Disaster Risk Reduction.*

https://www.preventionweb.net/files/7817_UNISDRTerminologyEnglish.pdf

United Nations (2016). *Report of the open-ended intergovernmental expert working group on indicators and terminologies relating to disaster risk reduction.*

https://www.preventionweb.net/files/50683_oiewgreportenglish.pdf

Velasco, M.T.H., Cadiz, M.C.H., & Lumanta, M.F. (2009). *Communication and Social Marketing.* UP Open University, Diliman, Quezon City

WHO (n.d.) *Risk communication.* [https://www.who.int/emergencies/risk-](https://www.who.int/emergencies/risk-communications#:~:text=Risk%20communication%20is%20the%20real,or%20economic%20or%20social%20wellbeing.)

[communications#:~:text=Risk%20communication%20is%20the%20real,or%20
economic%20or%20social%20wellbeing.](https://www.who.int/emergencies/risk-communications#:~:text=Risk%20communication%20is%20the%20real,or%20economic%20or%20social%20wellbeing.)

WMO(n,d.). *Tackling capacity gaps in Early Warnings for all delivery.*

<https://wmo.int/media/update/tackling-capacity-gaps-early-warnings-all-delivery>

Work Risk Report (2024). *World Risk Report 2024-Focus:Multiple Crises.*

<https://reliefweb.int/report/world/worldriskreport-2024-focus-multiple-crises>

World Risk Report (2022). *World Risk Report 2022.* [https://weltrisikobericht.de/wp-](https://weltrisikobericht.de/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/WorldRiskReport-2022_Online.pdf)

[content/uploads/2022/09/WorldRiskReport-2022_Online.pdf](https://weltrisikobericht.de/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/WorldRiskReport-2022_Online.pdf)

World Risk Report (2023). *World Risk Report 2023.* [https://weltrisikobericht.de/wp-](https://weltrisikobericht.de/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/WRR_2023_english_online161023.pdf)

[content/uploads/2023/10/WRR_2023_english_online161023.pdf](https://weltrisikobericht.de/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/WRR_2023_english_online161023.pdf)

Yin R. (2009). *Case study research: Design and methods* (4th ed.). SAGE

Publications

United Nations University (2021). *Building Local Resilience Platforms for Disaster Risk Reduction.* Policy Brief No. 22, 2021. Bisri, M. Djalante, R., Fernandez, G., Imai, N., Saito, O., and Okazaki, K.

https://www.preventionweb.net/files/76785_buildinglocalresilienceplatformsfor.pdf

UNDRR (2025). *Global Platform elevates risk communication as essential for disaster risk reduction.* <https://globalplatform.undrr.org/news/global-platform-elevates-risk-communication-essential-disaster-risk-reduction>

APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

Request Letters

University of the Philippines
OPEN UNIVERSITY

March 20, 2025

HON. JERRY P. TREÑAS

Mayor, Iloilo City
Iloilo City Hall, Iloilo City

ATTENTION: MS. DONNA P. MAGNO, CDRRMO
MS. MA. LUCY M. SINAY, PIO

Dear Mayor Treñas,

A safe and resilient day!

The undersigned is a full-time faculty member at the Division of Humanities, College of Arts and Sciences, University of the Philippines Visayas. While teaching, I am also pursuing my graduate studies under the Master of Development Communication at the University of the Philippines Open University.

Part of our requirements is to conduct research to apply our learnings. As a Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) advocate and Disaster Communicator, my chosen subject is Iloilo City Government's communication of its Early Warning System (EWS). EWS is an integral component of DRRM. With the right information, the public is guided and are expected to have an informed decision and right action.

This research entitled *Communicating Voices During Crisis: A Qualitative Exploration of Localized Early Warning Systems in Iloilo City* aims to 1.) describe the Local Government Unit's process of communicating its EWS, 2.) determine the strategies and challenges in communicating it, and 3.) develop recommendations for improving the communication of EWS.

Iloilo City is my chosen area because it is the center of economic hub in the region and a trailblazer in DRRM as supported by the many awards and recognition it has garnered over the years.

In line with this, I am respectfully requesting for your permission to conduct the study. Moreover, I would also like to seek assistance to facilitate the interview with the concerned personnel of Iloilo City Government and the representative of the other identified institutions and sectors who are vital in the materialization of this research.

This topic is vital and timely most especially that the Philippines has been considered as the most at-risk country in the world for the past three years according to the World Risk Index. The results of this study will help Iloilo City Government in fostering a responsive, inclusive, and sustainable EWS – to achieve a safer, adaptive, and disaster-resilient community.

University of the Philippines
OPEN UNIVERSITY

Should you have questions or clarifications, please do not hesitate to message me through my email address: attorreta@up.edu.ph/aljohntorreta@gmail.com and my cellphone number: +639106364396.

Looking forward to your positive response.

Thank you!

Respectfully yours,

ALJOHN T. TORRETA

University of the Philippines
OPEN UNIVERSITY

March 20, 2025

HON. MA. IRENE ONG

President, Association of Barangay Captains in Iloilo City
Iloilo City Hall, Iloilo City

Dear Hon. Ong,

A safe and resilient day!

The undersigned is a full-time faculty member at the Division of Humanities, College of Arts and Sciences, University of the Philippines Visayas. While teaching, I am also pursuing my graduate studies under the Master of Development Communication at the University of the Philippines Open University.

Part of our requirements is to conduct research to apply our learnings. As a Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) advocate and Disaster Communicator, my chosen subject is Iloilo City Government's communication of its Early Warning System (EWS). EWS is an integral component of DRRM. With the right information, the public is guided and are expected to have an informed decision and right action.

This research entitled *Communicating Voices During Crisis: A Qualitative Exploration of Localized Early Warning Systems in Iloilo City* aims to 1.) describe the Local Government Unit's process of communicating its EWS, 2.) determine the strategies and challenges in communicating it, and 3.) develop recommendations for improving the communication of EWS.

Iloilo City is my chosen area because it is the center of economic hub in the region and a trailblazer in DRRM as supported by the many awards and recognition it has garnered over the years.

In line with this, I am respectfully requesting to schedule an interview with you or your representative to determine the role of the punong barangays in the communication of EWS in Iloilo City. The role of Local Chief Executives is vital in Disaster Risk Reduction and Management, part of it is to operate EWS as stipulated in the Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act of 2010.

This topic is vital and timely most especially that the Philippines has been considered as the most at-risk country in the world for the past three years according to the World Risk Index. The results of this study will help Iloilo City Government in fostering a responsive, inclusive, and sustainable EWS – to achieve a safer, adaptive, and disaster-resilient community.

University of the Philippines
OPEN UNIVERSITY

Should you have questions or clarifications, please do not hesitate to message me through my email address: attorreta@up.edu.ph/aljohntorreta@gmail.com and my cellphone number: +639106364396.

Looking forward to your positive response.

Thank you!

Respectfully yours,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Aljohn T. Torreta'.

ALJOHN T. TORRETA

March 20, 2025

MR. OSCAR T. LIM, JR. CESO V

Director, DILG- Iloilo City
Iloilo City Hall
Iloilo City

Dear Director Lim,

A safe and resilient day!

The undersigned is a full-time faculty member at the Division of Humanities, College of Arts and Sciences, University of the Philippines Visayas. While teaching, I am also pursuing my graduate studies under the Master of Development Communication at the University of the Philippines Open University.

Part of our requirements is to conduct research to apply our learnings. As a Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) advocate and Disaster Communicator, my chosen subject is Iloilo City Government's communication of its Early Warning System (EWS). EWS is an integral component of DRRM. With the right information, the public is guided and are expected to have an informed decision and right action.

This research entitled *Communicating Voices During Crisis: A Qualitative Exploration of Localized Early Warning Systems in Iloilo City* aims to 1.) describe the Local Government Unit's process of communicating its EWS, 2.) determine the strategies and challenges in communicating it, and 3.) develop recommendations for improving the communication of EWS.

Iloilo City is my chosen area because it is the center of economic hub in the region and a trailblazer in DRRM as supported by the many awards and recognition it has garnered over the years.

The Department of the Interior and Local Government (DILG), as the Vice-Chair for Disaster Preparedness of the National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council, plays a vital role in achieving a safer, adaptive, and disaster-resilient community. The development and operationalization of the EWS is specifically stated in the Disaster Preparedness Manual developed by your good office.

In line with this, I am respectfully requesting to schedule an interview with you or your representative to determine the role of the DILG in the communication of EWS in Iloilo City. With the mandate of providing general supervision over Local Government Units, I firmly believe that your participation will enrich the information in the materialization of this research.

University of the Philippines
OPEN UNIVERSITY

This topic is vital and timely most especially that the Philippines has been considered as the most at-risk country in the world for the past three years according to the World Risk Index. The results of this study will help Iloilo City Government in fostering a responsive, inclusive, and sustainable EWS – to achieve a safer, adaptive, and disaster-resilient community.

Should you have questions or clarifications, please do not hesitate to message me through my email address: attorreta@up.edu.ph/aljohntorreta@gmail.com and my cellphone number: +639106364396.

Looking forward to your positive response.

Thank you!

Respectfully yours,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Aljohn T. Torreta'.

ALJOHN T. TORRETA

April 22, 2025

MR. JOEL FRANCO
Reporter/Anchor, DYRI RMN Iloilo
President, Iloilo City Hall Press Corps
Iloilo City

Dear Mr. Franco,

A safe and resilient day!

The undersigned is a full-time faculty member at the Division of Humanities, College of Arts and Sciences, University of the Philippines Visayas. While teaching, I am also pursuing my graduate studies under the Master of Development Communication at the University of the Philippines Open University.

Part of our requirements is to conduct research to apply our learnings. As a Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) advocate and Disaster Communicator, my chosen subject is Iloilo City Government's communication of its Early Warning System (EWS). EWS is an integral component of DRRM. With the right information, the public is guided and are expected to have an informed decision and right action.

This research entitled *Communicating Voices During Crisis: A Qualitative Exploration of Localized Early Warning Systems in Iloilo City* aims to 1.) describe the Local Government Unit's process of communicating its EWS, 2.) determine the strategies and challenges in communicating it, and 3.) develop recommendations for improving the communication of EWS.

Iloilo City is my chosen area because it is the center of economic hub in the region and a trailblazer in DRRM as supported by the many awards and recognition it has garnered over the years. The media, as one of the integral members in the community, especially in times of crisis, plays a vital role in achieving a resilient community.

In line with this, I am respectfully requesting to schedule an interview with you to determine the role of the Iloilo City Hall Press Corps in the communication of EWS in Iloilo City.

This topic is vital and timely most especially that the Philippines has been considered as the most at-risk country in the world for the past three years according to the World Risk Index. The results of this study will help Iloilo City Government in fostering a responsive, inclusive, and sustainable EWS – to achieve a safer, adaptive, and disaster-resilient community.

Should you have questions or clarifications, please do not hesitate to message me through my email address: attorreata@up.edu.ph/aljohntorreata@gmail.com and my cellphone number: +639106364396.

University of the Philippines
OPEN UNIVERSITY

Looking forward to your positive response.

Thank you!

Respectfully yours,

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads 'Aljohn T. Torreta'.

ALJOHN T. TORRETA

April 21, 2025

MR. KARL SIRA
JBLFMU
Iloilo City

Dear Mr. Sira,

A safe and resilient day!

The undersigned is a full-time faculty member at the Division of Humanities, College of Arts and Sciences, University of the Philippines Visayas. While teaching, I am also pursuing my graduate studies under the Master of Development Communication at the University of the Philippines Open University.

Part of our requirements is to conduct research to apply our learnings. As a Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) advocate and Disaster Communicator, my chosen subject is Iloilo City Government's communication of its Early Warning System (EWS). EWS is an integral component of DRRM. With the right information, the public is guided and are expected to have an informed decision and right action.

This research entitled *Communicating Voices During Crisis: A Qualitative Exploration of Localized Early Warning Systems in Iloilo City* aims to 1.) describe the Local Government Unit's process of communicating its EWS, 2.) determine the strategies and challenges in communicating it, and 3.) develop recommendations for improving the communication of EWS.

Iloilo City is my chosen area because it is the center of economic hub in the region and a trailblazer in DRRM as supported by the many awards and recognition it has garnered over the years. The academe, as one of the integral members, especially in times of crisis, plays a vital role in achieving a resilient community.

In line with this, I am respectfully requesting to schedule an interview with you to determine the role of the academe in the communication of EWS in Iloilo City.

This topic is vital and timely most especially that the Philippines has been considered as the most at-risk country in the world for the past three years according to the World Risk Index. The results of this study will help Iloilo City Government in fostering a responsive, inclusive, and sustainable EWS – to achieve a safer, adaptive, and disaster-resilient community.

Should you have questions or clarifications, please do not hesitate to message me through my email address: attorreta@up.edu.ph/aljohntorreta@gmail.com and my cellphone number: +639106364396.

University of the Philippines
OPEN UNIVERSITY

Looking forward to your positive response.

Thank you!

Respectfully yours,

ALJOHN T. TORRETA

Interview Guide for the Key Informant Interview

QUESTIONNAIRE

I. Participant's Profile

Name:

Age:

Sex:

Civil Status:

Occupation:

Designation:

Affiliation:

II. Guide Questions

A. Role in the Communication of Early Warning System (EWS)

1. What is the role of your office/unit/institution in Iloilo City Government's communication of its EWS?
2. How many personnel does your office/unit/institution have whose primary function is the communication of EWS of Iloilo City Government?
3. Do you have enough personnel with equipped knowledge and skills in the communication of EWS?
4. What are the common early warning messages that Iloilo City Government communicate through or to your office/unit/institution?
5. With 5 as the highest and 1 as the lowest, how familiar are you with the various elements of early warning system?

B. Communicating the EWS

6. How does your office/unit communicate Iloilo City Government's Early Warning System when categorized according to its elements?
 - Risk Knowledge
 - Observation and Forecasting
 - Dissemination and Communication
 - Response Capability
7. What are the various strategies utilized in your office/unit/ institution in the communication of early warning messages?
8. What are the common channels/media utilized by your office/unit in communicating the early warning messages?
9. What is the medium of language used in communicating the early warning messages? Why is that so?
10. Do you have a specific target audience in the communication of early warning messages or it is just for the general population?
11. How do you communicate early warning messages among the members of the vulnerable sectors like the youth, senior citizens, and persons with disabilities among others?
12. What is your process in crafting the content of the early warning messages being communicated?
13. How do you communicate scientific and technical information related to early warning system?

14. Do you consider the public as part of your process in developing and communicating the EWS? If yes, please explain further.
15. How vital is the participation of the public in the development and communication of EWS?

C. Recommendation

16. What are the areas for improvement in Iloilo City Government's communication of EWS?
17. How can Iloilo City Government achieve a responsive, inclusive, and sustainable EWS?

Appendix C

Certificate of Completion on TCPS 2: CORE 2020

Certificate of Completion

This document certifies that

Aljohn Torreta

*successfully completed the Course on Research Ethics based on
the Tri-Council Policy Statement: Ethical Conduct for Research
Involving Humans (TCPS 2: CORE 2022)*

Certificate # 0001376937

11 December, 2024

Appendix D

Transcript of the Interviews

Interview with Maam Lucy Sinay and sir LM Carnaje dated April 8, 2025

Torreta:...maam I will go into the details, this is specific to the communication of Early Warning System of Iloilo City Government, on that aspect, ano ang role ni PIO in collaboration with others or basi may ara man kao specific functions related to that?

Sinay: in terms of the early warning, since ang amon office is part of the working committee of the City Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council, so kita ang ginatugyanan sina especially sa comms aspect sa DRR naton. So tanan before pa maghatag sang example,opr before pa magfinal si mayor sang aton recommendations sa emergency operations center, so naga-agi gid ina anay sa PIO, so pag okay na, that is the time nga ipa-approve namon kay mayor, and then we revert back to the operations center and then hulaton anay ni OpCen nga si PIO mauna release sang whatever advisories then that is the time that OpCen will follow soon

Torreta: so in terms of communicating early warning system as a system kamo ang naga-prepare sang information nga ginapost in collaboration with CDRRMC

Sinay: Yes,actually may recommendations na sila anay nga ginapaguwa then we just tailor-fit it nga ang guwa niya daw advisory or announcement, after the mayor has approved

Torreta: so to my understanding, technical information from OpCen, or CDRRMO especially sa disaster risk context. Their recommendation after the approval of the mayor, that is the time that you process it again for information dissemination

Sinay: Yes for information dissemination for example pwede siya namon himuon nga daw public advisory or just an announcement. We can make it into a press release or a media advisory for sila na mismo, sa media directly namon nga ginahaboy.

Torreta: Sa inyo office maam diri sa PIO, how many personnel do you have whose primary function is related to the communication of early warning system? Or embedded siya technically whatever that is diri sa city government

Sinay: diri sa PIO may news team kami mo so basically sa team na, walo kami. So sa social media may nagahandle may content manager, si Gian ang naga-supervise, tapos may duha, one makes the pubmat ang isa sa videos then si LM for the IEC materials, Glenda for the press release, and then I just check the outputs.

Torreta: so regardless of the information, the same team ang nagaprocess sina?

Sinay: Huo

Torreta: to your experience of course with that number of personnel, enough ba siya for you to communicate or in communicating the EWS. Aside from the number, feeling mo, are you equipped with the skills and knowledge to do it maam?

Sinay: kon sa number, kon regular nga PIO job okay na ako na ugaling because of our partnerships with the City DRRMC kag syempre naga-evolve man ang PIO mo, sa functions, so indi siya enough eh nga walo lang katawo kay te aside from your regular job tapos ma amo kapa na, ma DRR work kapa. So medyo mabudlay that is why together with the CDRRMO, gina-ano namon tani nga the barangays will also step up so may ara kami actually ginhimo nga kon magsubmit ang barangay sang ila BDRRM plan, ibutang nila to nga there is an executive order designating sang Barangay Public Information Office which gin-obra man ina sang 180 barangays. So this year ang target namon i-mobilize ang 180 ka mga barangays, BIO tawag namon, Barangay Information Officers

Torreta: so may ara sang designated barangay information officers in all 180 barangays?

Sinay: Yes, in all 180 barangays per the document that we got from the CDRRMO. So amo ina nag gina-target namon mobilize this year kay para nga mapuslan sila for the community works

Torreta: how will you mobilize them?

Sinay: te for IEC sa barangays, siguro mabulig sa pagpaintindi sa mga tawo kon ano ang gina-atubang nila nga mga katalagman

Torreta: Sila inyob representative in every barangay

Sinay: Yes

Torreta: actually namuno ini ni kap Starlene Hosenilla sa Buntatala, may designated man siya nga kagawad nga IO as well. Anyway I would like to ask additional details on that if it is okay. When you conceived that program or project, ano ang mayor nga tinutuyo? Ano ang purpose and significance of it in relation to the communication of the early warning system.

Sinay: to bring the early warning down to the grassroots kay sila dapat ang una nga makahibalo kon whatever will happen di ba kag it would also be better kon halin mismo sa ila ang communication indi nga si city government lang ang naghaboy so we will also know what is going on in the field so pwede sila makahaboy information sa ibabaw.

Torreta: I see so not only you to them but them to you also

Sinay: Yes

Torreta: I understand may ara na sang existing mechanism sa mga kapitans' monitoring and reporting sa inyo, to OpCen pero this time, specific naman siya to the information officers

Sinay: Yes, hu

Torreta: this is for the redundancy as well

Sinay: yes kay nalearn ta man ina kay maam Donna no sa CDRRMO that redundancy really is, although redundant gani siya pero it is effective so sa sulit-sulit mo bala, masunod sang mga tawo. At least maplastar bala nga may amo sina

Torreta: Correct, because my topic is about early warning system and I understand that PIO has a lot of information nga gina-deal gani, when in terms of early warning system, how familiar are you or your office to the elements of early warning system?

Sinay: te ang amon la g gid iya in terms of communicating eh, communicating the risks of the people, that is aside from the technical nga mga EWS ni maam Donna, ang iya nga mga ano da, ang iya mga rainwater, rain gage niya so for us important ang mga information and education materials kay basically sa amon sa PIO amo ina ang amon nga real early warnings for the people

Torreta: correct and as what you have mentioned, communicating the risks through the IEC materials pero sa diin ninyo ini siya ginapang-share?

Sinay: we have printed (materials) so ginahatag ta sa barangay, sa mga schools, kag government agencies. And ang IEC namon through our Facebook page, the Iloilo City Government and of course gina-tap namon ang amon partners sa media

Torreta: we will go to that later for the specific channels and medium used maam, actually ncover mo naman ini, ang common early warning messages that you communicate, basically it is about the risks maam no?

Sinay: yes sa risks, for now be taas ang heat index so we have to tell the people ano ang dapat nila himuon, tuman ka init, tuman ka paang. Things like that and also dengue, ang mga infectious diseases especially nga summer, pag-abot sa tingulan ano naman ang ila atubangon, so mga amo sina

Torreta: Just this morning, the Kanlaon Volcano erupted as well so that is also covered or part of the risks nga gina-disseminate ninyo?

Sinay: yes so ang amon sina dira kon may mga things abi nga natabo like paglupok sang bulkan, nagaproactive man ang amon nga page, ang social media page, so we post materials related to the use of face masks or ang mga health risks sang ashfall. Amo na so we try to be relevant sa kon ano ang nagakatabo

Torreta: I will go to the specifics maam sa pag-communicate sang early warning system but this time, I will mention specific elements. So if we will categorize early warning system, diri na no sa risk knowledge earlier, so paano ninyo gina-disseminate, you mentioned earlier IECS, distribution of the printed to the concerned institutions and may ara man sa online. Ang UnRISK nga program subong ni city government of course because it talks about the risks sa kada barangay, are you also involved in that and paano ninyo siya gina-implement?

Sinay: involved gid kami dira kay because ang isa sa mga gin-UnRISK ang mga members san Iloilo City Hall Press Corps, so nangin part sila sang aton nga UnRISK tapos amo na ang next plan siguro by June or July ang aton na nga mga barangay information officers.

Torreta: what is good sa UnRISK kay well ginadiscuss ang mga concepts of course through maam Jeck, Prof. Jessica Dator-Bercilla, because kay ti Hiligaynon kita diri, there is this like an equivalency of the terminologies like the risks and hazards. When you conceptualize or develop that program, for it to be implemented as such, ano ang tinutuyo, why is there a need to translate or localize it?

Sinay: kay syempre para hapos maintindihan sang mga pumuluyo kay very technical abi pati gani ako kon kaisa no. We have to learn kon ano ang Hiligaynon sina nga mga terms kay it is so technical, so ano ang hazards sa Hiligaynon, ano ang vulnerability, ano ang exposure, ano ang mga capacities, What do we call them in Hiligaynon? So para hapos magrasp bala sang ordinary nga tawo. Ano nga katalagman ang gina-atubang mo? Ah katalagman gali ina, so mabal-an niya eh nga amo gali ina. Easily maidentify niya

Torreta: okay, sa may observation and forecasting nga element for example weather forecast or typhoon bulletin, in that case paano ninyo siya gina-communicate: Parehos kaina, Kanlaon eruption advisory, paano ninyo siya gina-communicate?

Sinay: the same, posting sa amon nga Facebook page. Kag mga amo sina, ang makauna sina ang OpCen so gina-pick up lang namon si OpCen then haboy sa page and also share sa GC sang media, because we maintain a group chat, Messenger, Viber group. Ang Viber group nila sina kay with the mayor pa gid gani

Torreta: I am a member sa Viber group man maam Lucy, may specific Viber group or GC ang kada sector or everybody is part of that specific Viber group or Messenger GC?

Sinay: May isa ka nga gincreate si CDDMO which I am also part of, ang Resilient Iloilo City nga Viber group, so tanan may sa barangay ara da, ang academe ara da, business sector maya ra da. But may per sector man kami nga group chat nga gincreate sa Viber. DDRM for Schools and Universities, transport lain man, religious lain man...sectoral siya

Torreta: so functional siya, ginagamit until now?

Sinay: Huo, ginagamit namon sa paghaboy sang mga information, advisories, para hapos na lang especially class suspensions so hapos na lang, isa na lang

Torreta: and parang tailor-fit mana ng information to the specific sector, maam sa may response capability for example bagyo so after some time, base on the monitoring and forecast ang ini nga area magbaha pa gid so kinahanglan na mag-evacuate so how do you inform the affected population that they need to evacuate already? Nagasulod kamo sina or gina-refer ninyo sa barangay?

Sinay: ginarefer namon ina sa barangay actually nagakuha gid kami always cue from the OpCen kon ano ang ipaguwa nila, what needs to be shared sa public or sa media, for the people to know. So ang amon nga cue always comes from the OpCen and with the approval of the mayor

Torreta: Okay, in terms of the mechanism sa pag-communicate sina nga mga hazards, communication and dissemination, you mentioned may mga GCs na gani kita no. Actually nacovert naman naton kaina but after you communicate ni sa ila using the GCs as what you have mentioned earlier, what comes after that? I mean may feedback from them? Or do they also share information to you? Especially sa monitoring for example sa mga coastal barangays naton, nagtaas ang level snag tubig, sa rivers, sa creek naton. Kon magtaas ang level sang tubig, do they also inform you about it?

Sinay: yes actually sang una wala gid na movement ang GC namon, parang sa amon lang nagahalin ang tanan. Ang GCs sang universities be, let me cite that, may active dira ya nga member. Like kon may ma-agan siya nga vehicular accident or may nagaluyloy nga mga wirings, so nagareport sila, nagafeedback sila. Another form of feedback mechanism namon sa Facebook page, so nagamonitor si Gian ina ya ang may task, so sa mga inbox. Kon may mga concerns ginarefer namon sa appropriate office kon indi namon masabat in our level, ginahimuoan namon referral tapos ginacheck eh kon nasaab ang concern, ginamessage ang department nga amo ni may mag message

Torreta: so ang information you process it and you share it to them but they are also empowered to share and be part of the dialogue

Sinay: yes, huo. So kon sa comments section for example sa isa be ka post, kon necessary nga magreply ka te we reply. If not, we private message the person nga amo ni ang sabat sa imo nga pamangkot.

Torreta: maam diri kita masulod sa strategies, I think amo ini ang maunod gid siguro nga part of the interview. What are the strategies utilized by your office or in your office in the communication of warning messages earlier we discussed UnRISK ano gid siya kay te may sectoral na approach for us to be aware of these things

Sinay: ang pagsimplify gid siguro sang messaging

Torreta: aside from that maam, ano pa gid ang mga strategies ninyo ni PIO as in institution or in collaboration with CDRMO in communicating early warning messages to the public?

Sinay: siguro ang regular nga mga meetings with the concerned sectors parehas sang natabo sa dengue last year, nangin involved kita didto sa pagpatawag sa nagkalain-lain nga sector sa barangay para nga ipabalo sa ila ang about sa dengue. We mentioned the Facebook page isa ina sa mga strategies naton. Ang paggamit naton sang partnership with the media, ang aton nga newsletter because we have a quarterly newsletter man nga ginapaguwa. Butang ta bi ang newsletter nagakadelay publish pero the people see nga may amo ni gali ang city nga programa, at least it helps, it helps them prepare.

Torreta: okay ang sa IECs ninyo as what you have mentioned earlier, nakit ako man gani sa barangay kaina, may mga posters for baha, tsunami, sunog, linog, and these are in Hiligaynon nga language so that is a strategy man...

Sinay: actually we have a partnership with PHIVOLCS man gani, LM imo na ini, may ara sila sang book kag brochure kon gaano ka handa ang imo balay, something like that. IN Hiligaynon, it is the first in the Philippines nga nagtranslate kita sang Hiligaynon version sina. How safe is my house?

Torreta: so ini, ang initiative is from PHIVOLCS or sa inyo?

Sinay: Sa PHIVOLCS, nag-partner sa aton, actually ang gusto nila mga partner sini ang Office of the Building Official pero sa amon natupa, gin-career na lang namon

Torreta: so basically this is about safety, structural integrity sa mga balay

Sinay: huo

Torreta: pero ang in Hiligaynon ninyo nga mga posters and materials

Carnaje: in partnerships with USAID

Sinay: In Hiligaynon ini siya

Torreta: using parang komiks

Sinay: huo

Carnaje: we shifted sa komiks approach kay we find out nga before we made these, gintestangan namon sa mga barnagay, most of them gusto nila komiks kay may ginabasa sila, may story and sa mga teenagers ang colors and visuals sa mga kids... amo ni before we print it, gin-test anay sa mga subjects sa community

Torreta: when was this developed and implemented sir?

Carnaje: last year pa

Sinay: a product of a seminar nga gin-attendan with the USAID

Torreta: In partnership ini siya with USAID

Carnaje: subong we are doing new design para naman sa sunog kag linog. Again the approach right now that we are using is in Hiligaynon and English, in komiks approach. So ang komiks we realized nga damo gusto magbasa...ari ang sa sunog ag linog, mga draft palang ini siya nad we are in the process of creating the new ones, may QR code, sadto small bigger na subong ang QR code

Sinay: amo na ang nalearn namon from CDRRMO, the use of CQ codes

Torreta: to access the materials

Sinay: yes, nga sila makapa-print

Carnaje: kag ang unod, not just this komiks but all other materials for linog and other disasters

Sinay: so on their own pwede sila makapa print...

Carnaje: we added COVID na ang dengue and of course when this was made wala pa ang volcanic kay wala man bulkan sa iloilo but we plan to add ang mga volcanic eruption. We give these sa mga schools and may mga sintra board pa gid ini siya

Torreta: so sa IECs , posters, the strategy now is in komiks, and the use of Hiligaynon language, but there is also in English version. Is this for whom, tourists? Bakit may English version pa din?

Carnaje: we have to admit no, konti na lang nag gumagamit ng local language but for the sake of SGLG, ang requirements dira under RA 10121, everything should be translated in the local language for DRR. So ginapangita nila ang mga LGUs sang local languages. Few years ago, wlaa pa ang COVID, ginpangita gid sang validated, although we have English translation, sa ila principle dapat kuno maintindihan so para maintindihan

Torreta: I discussed this with Director Oscar Lim and I checked as well the operation L!sto Manual of DILG, the arly warnings no masulod siya dira but I cannot see a specific provision that mentions the translation, in Hiligaynon no, in the local language. Siing ni DILG, kinahanglan sang local translation but I cannot see a specific provision or memorandum nga dapat translated siya, parang verbal lang ba?

Sinay: huo, parang amo na ang innovation

Carnaje: that is true

Torreta: correct. What is your appreciation to that maam?

Sinay: ako okay lang, I like it better nga in Hiligaynon, like pareho sang rikorida, we do it in Hiligaynon kay di ba the common tao can relate, maintindihan nila

Torreata: so you also do rikorida?

Sinay: yes we do the script for rikorida, for sunog

Torreata: pero sin-o ang naga rikorida?

Sinay: for example, si Bureau of Fire, tapos during dengue time, tapos sa mga tyempo nga wala sang tubig

Torreata: ang Public Address System sa kada barangay, do you also utilize that?

Sinay: yes, sila ang nagagamit sa barangay, when we had the BNEO (Barangay Newly Elected Officials) last year, ang pinaka-effective daw sa ila is ang rikorida or ang Public Address System so ang mga materials namon nga ginanghatag sa ila ginagamit nila, maglwag-lawag

Torreata: I understand that diri sa coastal barangays

Sinay: daw halos tanan may ara nga public address kag amo na kuno nag effective especially during COVID, nga ginapanawagan lang

Torreata: so unti now ginagamit ta pa ina nga strategy?

Sinay: huo

Torreata: pero indi ni ya kamo directly ang may control

Sinay: no, sila

Torreata: but in collaboration with the kapitans. So sa IECs maam no guidebook, building inspections na posters, ano pa gid sir?

Sinay: stickers may stickers kami

Torreata: ano nga mga stickers?

Sinay: may mga hotline numbers

Torreata: and recently ang DANAS project man with PHIVOLCS sir LM di bala ?

Carnaje: yes

Torreata: can you share sir LM...?

Carnaje: we are actually in the process of including it, this is in English version, ginpa Hiligaynon nila, and we are happy nga it complements the existing project with DOST-PHIVOLCS, this one is History di ba

Torreata: yes real experience nila

Carnaje: so we feel nga dapat ireprint man siya so as requested this will be reprinted by the city government but ma-add lang kita sang logo sa kilid para indi kita ma-flag sang COA...

Torreata: pero same content

Carnaje: huo kay bali we wanted nga, we talk ni maam Mati, dapat ang mga city library kay because it contains history kag mga interview

Torreta: so maprovide kamo copies sa mga city libraries?

Carnaje: yes aside sa mga city libraries, ang mga ano pa gid, mga partner agencies like for example this one, nakalista na kai sang mga universities nga naga-teach sang Engineering and Architecture so pwede na sila mag-base sang ila designs but this one for the city libraries especially for the young ones para mabasahan nila ang history for example sang Lady Caycay sang 1948, wala pa kita nabata

Torreta: correct but this is yet to be implemented, for this year maybe?

Carnaje: yes actually ginatapos ko ang amun documentation requirements for this to be printed within the year and we wanted it to be given sa mga tawo nga, sa mga city libraries, kag kopya man sa mga barangay para mabasahan nila. And isa man sa mga feature o projects ni maam Maki sa city library ang pagbutang bala sang nook sa mga plazas, so gina-explore pa nga dapat may mga hawid sini. And of course we wanted to have nga the more people will know about this the more makaprepare. And we feel nga kulang ang mga literature sa mga disasters diri sa aton sa local, so we are doing this right now

Torreta: yeah of course this was part of the DANAS Project and they documented the lived experiences of those who experienced earthquakes back then...and what is good about this kay in the local language and the photos as well, and may participation ang locals sa aton

Carnaje: yes sa communities, they were interviewed gin-double check nila ang literature for this one and right now...ang HR bag-o lang nagcall because sa onboarding sa new employees...ang every new employee will not receive a copy of this, para basahon. Para as a new employee he will know kon ano ang himuon niya in times of disasters... and in the future, each family, each head of the family should have a copy of this para malearn nila kon ano nag himuon...ari may checklist man kami is your house fireproof, last year pa ini. And anfg latest, to be launched and KTV

Torreta: ano ang KTV?

Sinay: KTV is KABALAKA TV...partnership with the Iloilo City Hall Press Corps para at least may ownership man sila, part man sang UnRISK eh naton nga program. So we are going to have experts on DRR there, mga heads sang different clusters sang CDRMC nga guests and sila man makasaysay sang ila expertise, preparedness or whatever or strategies that the people can do and we will feature best practices sang mga tawo sa barangay

Torreta: correct and what is good kay this is in partnership with the Local Press Corps they are the one who will facilitate the discussion

Sinay: yes, sila mafacilitate sang discussion kag maayo na kay sila mismo bala makaintindi. If you empower them, if you give them the right information, ta hapos nalang magtalakay sina sa imo nga programa

Torreta: they have following as well, may mga supporters...sa channel sa media nga gianagit natin to communicate these, you mentioned this earlier, GCs, Viber Groups, socmed, Facebook, emails...you have mentioned that may partnership man with media, ang partnership with media ano ni siya for example , press con, press release?

Sinay: yeah press conference, ang mayor may regular siya nga press conference but if the need arises we also call for press conferences with the various departments sa city government like the city health so naka schedule sila for example every Friday amo na bala. So gina-tap man namon sila especially kon may mga programs man sila nga gusto ipromote. Press releases we do that

Carnaje: KABALAKA tours with the media we do that

Torreta: KABALAKA tours and the art galleries?

Sinay: yes

Torreta: ang sa may media maam, ano ang specific, I mean may specific nga legacy media kamo nga gina-partner or encompassing ini sa traditional media and even to online personalities or practitioners doing freelance...?

Sinay: yeah we also tap the bloggers in particular Iloilo Bloggers Society, ginaupod namon ina sila kon may mga events

Torreta: okay, so ginagamit niyo man sila for the information dissemination

Sinay: yeah, Iloilo Bloggers Society and sa Iloilo Press Corps may online man sila nga membership mo, may mga upod sila nga sa online

Torreta: maam gakadto pa kamo sa community level para mag-communicate?

Sinay: amo na bala ang akon misgivings gid nga dapat ang PIO nagakadto, nagapanaug, te because amo lang kami ni, with the limited resources, we do not go down to that level in the barangay gid. Amo na that is why we are going to have the barangay information officers

Torreta: diri ni sila masulod?

Sinay: huo, kay indi man namon malibot ang bilog nga 180

Torreta: in some area,s I read some articles and researches as well wherein some prefer sang face-to-face or interpersonal communication especially for early warning. Diri sa aton, are we also doing that or in a way nakita niyo man sa field nga they prefer that?

Sinay: bal-an mo ang problema bal-an kis-a kon naga-field ka gidang mobilization sang tawo tapos you have to find the right time nga ra da sila tanan kay ti mon matag-adlaw puro na nanay bilin, sa diin ang mga tatay, nagaulubra. So amo na nag drawback if we really go to the community level nga makadto ka gid kag face-to-face pero ang sa barangay sang nabal-an namon sang nag-BNEO kami ang hambal sang mga kagawad mas effective actually amo na, rikorida, PA System, kag face-to-face nga nagahouse-to-house. So amo na if we will really activate ang barnagay information officers armed with all the IECs that we have, pwede gid na sila kapamalay balay and the learning nils sa UnRISK, pwede gid

Torreta: and ma-institutionalize pa dason and process mismo kay te equip na sila of course supervise lang ninyo for the monitoring

Sinay: huo, correct

Torreta:... maam sa medium of language nga ginagamit naton, earlier we discussed may Hiligaynon, may English, what else? Why are we using these languages?

Sinay: te very important gid ya nag Hiligaynon kay aton gid iya languahe kag maintindihan snag tawo sometimes kun ay Tagalog bala nga ginadownload sa amon especially from the national government kay usually garequest sila mo nga paki-share, ginatranslate ina namon John kay te kita nga daan nabudlayan kita magTagalog di ba so mas hapos kon itranslate in Hiligaynon

Torreta: nakamuno ni si kapitan Hosenilla, one time, I do not know if your office or OpCen ang nagahtag sang audio materials nga gin-share nila for the rikorida (PA)

Sinay: huo, diri na halin. Ano to gin-produce namon man, I think dengue, gin-agi namon sa OpCen kay sila ang may ano, si hambal namon kamo nalang bahala feed sa barangay

Torreta: so you do that sa barangay

Sinay: huo, gina-produce na lang namon

Carnaje: ...and we have a communication chart, it was designed and ginpa-check sa mga deaf community ato ang nag-obra because ihatag sa mga ambulance and partner agencies nga gavolunteer

during ano kay ano there was a case before ng deaf gali ang pasyente, indi kabati...so subong may ara sila sintra board, communication board for the deaf and mute, itudlo niya lang kon ano, is he bleeding, hungry, ukon ano. Naprint na, nahatag na CDRRMO, gina-identify na nila ang mga partner agencies nga nagakinahanglanon gid

Torreta: actually I will go to that later maam kay te sa marginalized sector naton..that it is some of the areas that needs to be looked at and consider gid.. Maam when you process this information, do you do it bearing in mind na may specific audience kamo or general population?

Sinay:sometimes, general, more on general kami kay akuon ta man ukon indi, kinahanglan na ini subong, kinahanglan na ini mapaguwa subong so kis-a indi na kami makaproces bala nga si amo lang ini ang target ta. Ginahimo nalang namon general na lang and then later on pag may time , amo nalang na pagbato-bato mo per sector. Pero most of the time daw gina general nalang namon

Torreta: kay applicable man siya across all sectors

Sinay: yes

Carnaje: that is why ginseparete na lang gid naon ang for PWDs and elderlies because as required by law

Sinay: ginhimuan ta na sila IECs di bala, ang mga PWDs

Carnaje: huo pero diri sa family preparedness guide may ara kami nga para lang sa head of the family, kon ano ang ubrahon sang head of the family. Kay may ara man for children diri and i-add namon later on ang para sa women

Torreta: ang sa checklist to?

Carnaje: yes kag ang sa ano gid eh , may part ini siya kon ano ang ubrahon sang mga babaye sa evacuation center. For example, family leaders guide para ni sa father. May checklist pa gid for women and children in the evacuation centers. This was designed included atong may mga cases sang rape, VAWC, os gin-add namon siya diri...actually wala pa gani na-include diri ang para sa mga deaf community man when this was made so amo na ang ginahcekc namon for the revisions or version 2

Sinay: si OSCA ginhimuan ta di ba sang separate nga ila gid

Torreta: ano siya printed?

Sinay: huo printed, posters

Carnaje: kag sintra board

Torreta: ano ang kinalain sang ila IECs?

Sinay: specific kon ano ang ubrahon sang mga tigulang

Torreta: sila gid ya nag subject and characters

Sinay: yes

Carnaje: para indi nila mafeel nga left sila

Torreta:...how do you communicate early warning messages among the members of the vulnerable sectors like the youth, senior citizens, and persons with disabilities, and children? So sa senior citizens, may specific

Sinay: may specific gid ya nga IECs for them, si PWDs may specific man nga sa ila

Torreta: ano ang sa PWDs?

Sinay: amo to ang comm board

Carnaje: for example, COVID time, COVID lang gid ya for senior, may for PWDs man..ang didto kay Ann naga-obra kami nga ang goal sang KTV kon ano ang lecture dira, dapat may signger dira sa kilid. For the senior , sang una may programa kami nga KABALAKA for the seniors, ginakadtuan gid sila iya nga mhga seniors kag gintudlan paano sila maghimo sang ila Go Bag, pangtigulang gid ya nga level of understanding te medyo makulit sila kis-a. Ngaa makulit, lain ya nag level of concept nila sa situation...

Torreta: so we are doing a specialized na communication campaigns man para sa ila. Sa PWDs very interesting because this is very applicable gid during response but that can also be used for example in the evacuation centers

Carnaje: kag nag-abot kami sa punto nga pati ang mga fisherfolks gin-intrahan na namon, may IEC man sila ya nga ila

Sinay: Yes, iya sang Coast Guard

Carnaje: May Bureau of Fire pa gid kami. Sang una may fire prevention for school, so for children. Ang amon naubra subong is office edition kay bal-an mo laina ng context sang sunog kon sa office ka. Tapos na ang school, ang home edition, and office edition gina-finalize...

Torreta: what is the process in crafting the content of the early warning messages being communicated? So for example from OpCen, di ba scientific sila, ila ginalaymanize man nila form their end. After them may another process kamo diri?

Sinay: may process kami iya nga amon for examplesina te gadevelop kami sang mga hazard specific or sector specific tapos ginapa-approve namon sa OpCen, sa CDRRMO, sa council kay sila ang gabudget for the funding

Torreta: so ang inyo processing is analyzing as well the data and translating it?

Sinay: hu0

Carnaje: and we prioritize the IEC according to the data sang CDRRMO kun ano ang mga key gid bala nga mga needs

Sinay: hu0 ang relevant, ano na...

Torreta: maam ncover ta ini kaina, how do you communicate scientific and technical information related to early warning. So we are doing translation

Sinay: translation, hu0

Carnaje: and also before giving it to the public gina-laymanzie namon kay kaisa tuma ka technical

Torreta: so by laymanizing are we translating it or may iban pa gid?

Carnaje: aside from translating, interviews, naga-ask kami sa mga experts kon paano namon ni siya ipa-simplify ang meaning bala. Kami mismo sa PIO kaisa sabog man kami because we are not scientists, indi man kami weatherman, background namon ya is different

Sinay: so ang ginakwan namon, naga-ano kami sa department kon pwede kita makapa-press con para ma-explain bala, so indi lang sa amon pati sa media mabuligan kami explain. Amo na

Torreta: of course si Secretary Solidom is advocating naman sang impact-based forecasting, are you also observing that?...

Carnaje: we are trying to do that man sa IEC

Torreta: maam do you consider the public as part of your process in developing and communicating the EWS?

Carnaje: before mga sang 2016 to 2018, generic na lang but later on as we evolve , ginaconsider na namon not ang generic but nag specific needs sang PWDs, sang seior, sang children, sang women, kag sang men later on. So there was a time nga wala kami pakialam basta makaprint lang kami iya but later on dapat gali icoconsider mo kaya we evolve from pure texts nag-include na kami sang mga drawings , sang mga cartoons, kag komiks nga approach para maintindihan nila. For example sang una bullets lang ini tanan subong ginhimo namon checklist box. Para interactive ang unod sang libro and this was designed actually nga pwede mo ini puksion in the middle kag itapik sa dingding...and ang second design nga ini this was made by the interns...

Torreta: ad you mentioned earlier nagpre-test pa kamo sa barangay for the komiks, I think that is an indicator nga part gid sila iya sang development

Carnaje: sang nagprest kami ni snag komiks naghambal nag iban nga mga tigulang nga daw ka law-ay so we have to consider. Pati ang color ginsuyaang so we consider so sa final nga result sila ang nag-design indi kami. And we found out man sa mga pre-test sa mga communities, damo man sila sang gusto nga insert nga ila man gusot but we have to be pragmatic man ano...we feel nga dapat kabalo gid ya nag community kon ano ang ibutang mo sa IEC kay sila mana ang magamit mo

Torreta: correct ang tong sa communication board for the PWDs...

Carnaje: ang nag-obra to kay deaf man

Torreta: okay

Carnaje: kay si Ann is also a signer, nahappy ag deaf community kay first time kuno nga may amo sina. Gin-pick up man to gani sang Philippine News Agency kay hambal nila parang never pa sila nakakita sang amo na nga concept. We have been doing it pero dapat iupod mo siya sa mga ambulansiya...

Sinay: gusto ko lang gali ishare kon paano ang nangin part sang public sa pagdevelop sang early warning. Kay sa amon Facebook page di bala,we also check sa mga metrics sa engagements sa mga reacts amo na. SO if we see nga ang amon pubmats is gamay ang engagement, ay basi kinahanglan ta kayuhon basi it needs improvement, basi need sang new design, bais tama ka laba sang text, kinahanglan ta liputon ukon basi taman ka lip-ot kinahanglan ta labaon para maintindihan amo na bala, kon ano ang illustration nga nabutang so we also analyze kon ano ang amon nga content based on the engagement and the feedback

Torreta: ang OpCen they have this radio frequency utilized by the barangays and among responders, are you also part of that?

Sinay: wala ila ina...

Torreta: how vital is the participation of the public in the development and communication of EWS?

Sinay: important gid eh just like sa other development plans ni city nga gina-involve ang public, mga CSO, mga NGO, POs nga ina kay important man nga sila ang mabatian kon ano ang ila nga thoughts on the development of the early warning

Torreta: and most especially because they are the pens using it

Sinay: huo, sila man ang benefit in the end, sila man ang affected

Carnaje: nami gid ya kon grassroots level ang feedback kay kita in the office or working on the technical side, gakaalipatan ta...iba ang ila suggestion. One time with thedesign sang komiks, siling ya kanami sang design no pero wala na ya sa amon nga barangay so gin-islan namon kay indi sila maka-relate

Sinay: and I think daw nag evolve naman gid nag governance sa Iloilo City nga sang una daw top-down subong ya naga bottom-up approach na, participatory governance

Torreta: ...maam what are the areas that need improvement if ever may ara pa nga pwede naton mas mapa-strengthen?

Carnaje: ownership, of whatever nga may EWS kita...kon may ownership kita ginaproteksyonan mo siya you know what it is for kag gaparticipate ka

Torreta: pero how can we let them feel that they own it? That EWS is not jus being implemented by the LGU

Carnaje: dapat implement dapat naconsult gid nag community, nakahibalo ang community, ang every sector...kag gusot namon nga kon ano man ang specific nga EWS dapat ang specific man nga sector ang malead...it should be all sectors involve

Torreta: in terms of the technical aspect maam sa pag-communicate for example translating scientific and technical info, laymanizing it, to popularize it as well, so far makaya naton ina ya diri? You have been doing that so far okay man or do you feel like may mga area son that aspect nga we can also strengthen and improve pa?

Sinay: I think may mga needs improvement pa man kami indi man kami perfect...di ba kinahanglan p agid namon ang more capacity building pa gid siguro and more knowledge man on DRR works, kay ang amon leaning daw dira mo...kag ang sa crisis comm daw sa amon man ginahaboy so we need more trainings siguro and competency-based trainings...especially with the technologies no whether we like it or not gobyerno ini ang amon nga equipment nga ginagamit are old, daan na. We also need to keep up with the times. Sa manpower, huo madugang dugangan...

Torreta: is there a need for additional capabilities sa resources

Sinay: huo agree, and institutionalization of the barangay information officers. We do not have our own budget sa IEC, we tap the CDRMC dira kami nagakuha sa LDDRM fund

Torreta: pero in terms of the community, in the communication in the community level, I think diri na masulod ang pag-institutionalize sang BIO

Sinay: we also tap the liga ng mga baragay

Torreta: maam last question, how can Iloilo City Government achieve a more responsive, inclusive, and sustainable EWS?

Sinay: it is part of the vision of the city gid man to be more inclusive, to be more responsive to the needs of the community of course ang resiliency and sustainability amo gid ina ang aton nga vision and hopefully by 2029 malab-ot na naton ina

Torreta: so how can we achieve that?

Sinay: important siguro ang systems thinking sangt anan diri sa city government. Indi lang man ini ubra snag isa ka tawo, we do not work in silos...ari naman kabit-kabit bituka, indi man ni namon maubra sa PIO lang, we need other departments and other departments also need us. Isa pa gid ina sa mga misgivings ko, kay sometimes when they plan they forget ang communication part, so ulihi na ang tanan for example nagkarambola ang program, dira na sila mangayo bulig. Siling ko sa planning niyo palang dapat ginplug in na ninyo ang communication part..it doe snot happened all the times, but sometimes. Important siguro nga mabutang naton sa thinking sang iban naton nga mga upod nga communication is very important especially sa EWS.

END

Interview with Ms. Donna Magno, CDRRM Officer of Iloilo City Government dated April 4, 2025

Torreta: Ano ang imo role and your office in Iloilo City Government's communication of its EWS?

Magno: well, I am sure you are familiar with that, under RA 10121, it enumerated the mandates of LDRRM Office when it comes to DRRM...so ang mag-take snag lea,d over-all, it is the role of the Local Government Unit through the CDRRMO to set the policies, the direction, promotion and implementation of DRRM priorities within the area of jurisdiction. And one of that is the promotion of the multi-hazard Early Warning System. So if there is an office within LGU that is mandated to do that, it is the CDRRMO in partnership in other offices pa gid

Torreta: So basically Iloilo City Government through CDRRMO and in partnership with other offices and units

Magno: Actually, the policies, it has to be approved by the council, the CDRRMO being the secretariat we put together the data, the information, the proposal. Kumbaga at the center of that effort si CDRRMO. But again we cannot operate in silo di ba, kay te kinahanglan mo ang other offices like PIO, Liga

Torreta: In terms of the number of personnel whose primary function is related to EWS, how may do we have here?

Magno: we have i think 120 kami or perhaps 130, well people come and go, ang mga staff but then we have 5 divisions and one of that is the Disaster Response Division. Under that division we have four sections, we have the USAR, the ICER, the IT Section, and the OpCen. So mainly it is the Operations Center ang naga-take sang lead sina

Torreta: it falls under the Operations Center?

Magno: Huo, kay kung balikan mo diba. Let us define the Early Warning System. If we take a look of the four elements, you have to have risk knowledge, so another division naman ina ang in-charge for you to come up with the Risk Assessment and Risk Information. Actually duha, BDRRMS Division naman (Barangay DRRM Services Division. This is the Division that works in the 180 barangays. So in every district, we have a focal person. If we do the risk assessment, we have to go down to the barangay level. So sila ni siya ang gatake charge and putting together all, you have the city level na perspective when it comes to the risk knowledge of the city. So amo ina siya, kun i-pull together mo ang information, another division naman ina ang ga-work, amo ni ang sa Research and Planning kun sa RA 10121 pero sa amo ang ngalan sang post is the Pre and Post Disaster Management Division, so amo ina siya. So risk knowledge, sa monitoring and forecasting, iya na na ni OpCen. So using all the devices di bala ginalantaw nila, building on the risk knowledge...

Torreta: Okay that is for the forecasting

Magno: Sa communication, OpCen sila na gihapon kag balik gid kita sa barangay sang amon nga I-CARE (Iloilo City Action and Response Centers). So amo ina siya. Dayun sa response capability, under the Response Division sa gihapon amo na ina ang ICER, USAR, as you can see indi lang ni isa ka section

Torreta: ...sa communication and dissemination aspect, do you have a dedicated personnel or office for that or in partnership na siya with others?

Magno: Okay sige, so risk communication tama? If we have to communicate the risk, again ma build on ka sa risk knowledge mo right?but to analyze the data, may bagyo ka di ba, they have the scientific information from PAGASA, Manila Observatory, other available data from the different websites. Once they have that, it is the role of the OpCen to analyze what does it mean for the barangays of Iloilo City. So kon amo ni kabaskog, amo ni ang time nga maabot, diri nga direction, ano nga mga barangays ang high risk?So it is the role of the OpCen to communicate the risk pero ang channel where you will throw all those information ginapaagi kay BDRRMS namon kay at the barangay level, ang gina-obra namon sir, di ba RA 10121 says that barangay should organize its own Barangay DRRM Committee. So in every barangay, nag-establish man kami sang barangay Operation Center. So from the city level, amo na siya manaog ina siya deretso sa barangay

Torreta: so functional ini tanan ang 180 barangays?

Magno: kon basehan mo lang kon may bagyo and all, may nagasululod nga mga reports then you would know nga amo ina pero I do not think may consciousness, kamalayan ang mga barangay nga OpCen kami pero gafunction siya as monitoring and relaying the information

Torreta: and that is what we are trying to achieve gid from the LGU down to the community level

Magno: Up to the last mile, so amo ina siya

Torreta: So ang 120 or 130 personnel nga ini distributed ini in various divisions?

Magno: but not evenly, pinakadamo ang Disaster Response. Siling ko gani, under kay Darwin (Papa), almost 70% of the staff and ang pinakadamo dira ang ICER and USAR. Sa response di ba

Torreta:with that number, do you think enough ang number of personnel to facilitate and lead on the efforts about the early warning system?

Magno: balikan ta, we use the early warning to communicate the risk to trigger people to do early action di bala, so wala pa na ang response. Wala pa kaabot si bagyo mo, wala pa nagilinamo, pre-emptive, pre-disaster so I do not think you need that many people. Kon sa office lang, well you have the OpCen, mas ginatan-aw ko ang weight sang obra. We need more experts like technical staff like right now,we have an in-house meteorologist. If we can have more bala nga lain pa gid ang ila expertise para may scientific background, mas kinahanglanon ina. Always, even if amo lang ina sila kadamo ha, still we can come up with the kind of information that we want to communicate to the people. Ang tricky na prime dira is from us going to the barangays. As long as naga-work ang Viber, ang radyo, ang handheld radios, ang mga Messenger nila nga groups, makalab-ot gid ina up to the last mile kay amo ina siya ang mga barangays naton, they have this Public Address System nga once mabaton nila, ang iba na gina-announce nila. So amo ina siya, amo pa ina ang gusto namon i-establish man. We want to see kon how active ang mga kabarangayan nga once they receive that information, makalab-ot

Torreta: cascaded sa dalum. The uses of various channels, we will go to that later but initially this is the initial data

Magno: so kon ang pamangkot we have enough people, so I do not think it is not about numbers di bala. It is really about the channel that matters di bala. Kay even kon magpaguwa kami sang information, kaisa nagapangakig na sa ibabaw. Siling ko ano kamo si PAGASA, they will just copy and paste, that is not our role. Na-learn ko gid ina kay maam Tony before sang DENR. Di bala kada bagyo, mahambal sila, palpak man si PAGASA but we fault to understand nga it is the role of PAGASA to look at the hazard profile but it is the role of the Local Government Unit to tell the people what does it mean for you. Te kon taga coastal ka,te evacuate kamo, pre-emptive, daw amo bala ina

Torreta: so there is a sort of processing from the ICDRRMO level of this information for example typhoon, Bulletin Number 1 from PAGASA, there is a sort of processing halin sa inyo before you cascade that?

Magno: Huo, sometimes di ba ginapost lang nila pero it should include information on what you will do because this is the status right now of the typhoon or whatever. Remember si Mt. Kanlaon paglupok

niya, nagsala tana, kitaon ang fumes di ba. Tapos paglupok sala na tanan ma-post, siling ko Darwin paguwa na kamo sang warning kay damo ang nagsala-sala. What does it mean for us? Ang information nga volcanic ash, te daw indi kita malab-ot? So ano ang pinakapossible, malab-ot kita? So kay may in-house meteorologist kami, what we did kay we let him study the wind direction. Tapos they come up with this narrative, so part of the narrative "given the current wind direction, volcanic ash is expected to fall in the north and northeast direction". Siling ko de**** kamo, north and northeast sa diin ina? Kay kon ako ordinaryo nga tawo, duuuh, indi mo ko ma-warn, indo ko mag-take action kay wala ko kaintindi. Liwata! Pagliwat nila, diin ang areas? "Maam somewhere sa Miagao...gin-studihan nila liwat. Abi mo pagka gab-i, pagpaguwa ni PHIVOLCS sang information, amo gid to nga mga areas kondi nalipay kami. Oh di ba, that is what we are saying communicate the risk. Simplify it so that ordinary people can understand it and take early action kay naintindihan ko ang ginpalab-ot mo.

Torreta: Exactly, that is what from technical information from government agencies, there is that additional processing from your unit to give that additional context of information about it

Magno: Or to simplify it

Torreta: in doing that maam, are we using also the local language or mix na siya with other languages as well?

Magno: Alam mo naman Englishera ang aming meteorologist kag kami man kaisa mas dasig mo magsulat but then again we do understand that critical info like this, kinahanglan naka-Hiligaynon so sometimes kon indi kami mag-post sang written, kon nagafollow ka sa Facebook namun...salang to ang video para maintindihan ang Hilagaynon or ang OpCen staff ang nagatudlo-tudlo. Localization plus there was a time nga medyo ano lang be siya trabahoso, may PWD man kami mo, so may inset kami na last time, tingala kami nga that particular video nga may bagyo, damo-damo shares. Kag gali imo sa network sang mga deaf and mute, nalipay sila kay for the first time baw nabal-an ta man kon ang ang sitwasyon because we did something like that. So indi lang siya about sa written, about localizing sa aton nga dialect, but even sa language sang iban nga sectors. The deaf and mute...

Torreta: Actually diversity, inclusivity, and sustainability are really the core values of this research and of course it is participatory. So sa video nga ina if I may ask additional information, sa videos nga ang the one explaining are personnel ninyo, aside from that, may inset na parang may sign language interpreter. Ano ang specific hazard nga ina maam?

Magno: bagyo to siya last time...

Torreta: until now you are using that?

Magno: medyo trabahoso lang siya kay they have to edit...kon utihan mo by that time, tapos na ang advisory amo pagrelease

Torreta: Unless may in-house expert?

Magno: yes, in-house expert sa mga videography... but I think okay man siya (PWD personnel) sa live kaso syempre indi man kami nga professionals, huya huya pa na sila. Pero that particular video, nalipay kami ah it works. So kon indi man siya mga advisories, may iban kami, ginabutangan namon sang sign language interpreter

Torreta: sa risk knowledge, actually related to that man, you mentioned this earlier, pero basi pwede ta lang madugangan regarding the number of personnel with equipped knowledge and skills in the communication of EWS. You mentioned earlier nga mas maayo pa gid tani kon may additional technical staff, can you elaborate maam?

Magno: Like hydrologist... kay we are prone to flooding para studihan kay even ang drainage again using systems thinking kay indi man ini pwede nga individual like right now may masterplan sa pagobra sang drainage so we need a hydrologist, we do have knowledge where flooding happens pero mas nami tani kon may in-house kami nga amo na siya, then they can tell us nga amo ina ang bagyo, ang water diri ni siya ma-fall so kon magpa-obra sang drainage, maayo nga diri indi bala?

Torreta: sa technical info ina siya pero in the communication of that for example you are doing translation or using the local language

Magno: Kon mag amo ina siya, still we will rely sa technical person kay te di bala kami nana ang bahala sa pagsimplify, indi lang nga i-translate mo lang in the local language. Kundi iintindihon pa gid, ang tawag ni nila Science Communication. How do we communicate Science to the ordinary people. So iintindihon lang namon, amo ina ang role ni Darwin, ang akon ya role, indi ako expert, ordinaryo ako nga tawo ang mindset ko pirme is that "explain that to me". Kon indi ko kaintindi, "balik, balik, balik". I-simplify, we can do that pero we need an experts opinion nga magpa-intindi sa amon nga amo ini ang , this is how it goes

Torreta: pero doon sa communication of the scientific information ano, as of this time, we are already doing that no?

Magno: Huo like ang CDRA (Climate and Disaster Risk Assessment)

Torreta: pero in terms of the technical expertise sa language or in the communication aspect, do you think may pwede pa kita madugang or mapun-an on that aspect. For example, we are guided by Science already but in the communication of that to the public, as of this time, do you feel like we are doing good or are there areas that we can improved on on that aspect?

Magno: I think ano, we can never tell sa reception or acceptance of the public kay that is one of the, balikan ko lang, there is this survey done by DILG on the satisfaction of the services of Iloilo (City Government), so one of the questions was that, there was a question about Early Warning i think...ginpamangkot ang mga tawo, nakahibalo bala kamo, nalipay kamo sa mga services, so nabudlayan ko kay it is a system dali lang, dapat kabilugan ang lantawon mo. Anyway, nagahaboy lang kami mo, we just post , we just announce so we can never tell. Mabal-an ko lang na sa mga reactions" ay kadugay" but in terms of content maybe not really with the language per basi ang form kay halimbawa, damo na mga Gen Z, basi mas effective kon through TikTok. May nanotice ko lang ina siya kon imonitor mo ang mga posting sa daily heat index kay nagahulat sila kon may klase or wala, medyo damo na ang mga shares. Pro kon like air quality monitoring, weather advisory, wala na ina may nagasapak. So siling ko basi ang mas creative nga presentation

Torreta: and what directly bothers or affects them

Magno: Daw amo gid ina siya, lantawa bala kon may sunog, pinakadamo gid nga mga shares, nagadamo dayon ang amo nga mga likes... but again ang gusto ta matabo is ang sa prevention nga side. Sa early warning, may response ka mga phase, tani indi lang didto ang magtake action but you know right from the start. Sa Asia Pacific Ministerial Conference, isa sa pinaka-hot nga topic is early warning but kon si maam Jeck (Dator-Barcilla) pa, that is passe, dugay nana. Siling ko te amo subong ang bag-o subong, it is all about localization, end-to-end nga warning. So kumbaga ang measurement sang aton gina-obra, indi lang ini nakasalalay lang kay Early Warning kundi ara sa localization, something like that

Torreta: of the effort generally

Magno: huo tanan

Torreta: you mentioned this earlier...how familiar are you with the various elements of the early warning system?

Magno: the four elements, how familiar well I have learned about these concepts sang sa OCD days ko pa, that was in 2011 pa siguro. So you know it was something that was stuck with me kay that time there was a project as well by LFEWS, Local Flooding Early Warning System di ba dumduman mo? So didto ko nakita siling ko ah so this is how it works. Pero tama ka, there was no agency. I do not know lang basi may ara walang lang ko naka-reach out sa ila or wala lang nakalab-ot sa akon but I would like to think nga wala may nagtudlo sang concept of early warning system except for NTC (National Telecommunications Commission) kay Engr Monroy gani kag prime ko man ini siya nabatian kay DOST because they are the lead but I do not think, naistoryahan na nila...but how you see this being operated on the ground it is left to the discretion of the LGU, kon paano mag-interpet, paano mag-obra

Torreta: But that is one of the considerations in assessing the capacity of the LGU in SGLG?

Magno: But do you think ang naga-assess nakahibalo man?

Torreta: Ano naman ang common early warning messages that the Iloilo City Government communicates through your office?

Magno: Ang common related to typhoon sa flooding, sunog kay amo ini siya ang mga hazards nga gina-atubang kag frequent, kag amo ni ang sa init

Torreta: Let us go to the specifics of the communication of the early warnings and let us look at it per element. Sa risk knowledge, how do you communicate it to your target audience?

Magno: Lain-lain nga mga stakeholders. We use the CDRA nga report and kon barangay level ini siya ang ila nga hazard map and ang ila risk assessment in the barangay level. Ang city ang usual attack namon we present the city level risk profile, and then if we are talking in the barangays or particular districts gina tailor-fit ina siya sa ina nga context or kun sectoral naman ang approach we package it ang information nga relevant sa particular nga sector.

Torreta: ini sa community sa barangay levels through meetings?

Magno: huo kon through meetings amo ina siya pro usually kon may gina-organize kami nga seminars for the barangay leaders. So we leave it to them nga magpa-barangay assembly abi no, gina-invite man nila kami so we assist them nga sila mismo ang mag-share. Usually mahambal na ang barangay so kun kabalo nana sila again the formula of the disaster risk, hazard + exposure + vulnerabilities. Kay usually ang gina-istoryahan nila hazards, wlaa ni si exposure and vulnerability. So part sang pag-communicate sa ila ang pag-highlight especially sa barangay leaders kon ano ang vulnerability. Nga-a, amo ni ang naga-cause, sila ni exposure, amo ini ang nagadetermine sa level of risk mo sa particular hazard. That is why, if they understand kon ano nag interplay sang tatlo nga ini then they will also understand where you will invest your money. Kay di ba, we have to reduce our vulnerabilities. So focus kita sa vulnerability reduction strategies , so that is the secret

Torreta: to mitigate the negative impact

Magno: and that is the concept of the risk reduction. Paano mo mapanubo, tanawa, intindiha kon ano ang kahayang, ano ang kahayag , dira ka invest.

Torreta: maam sa risk knowledge, aside from meetings...

Magno: webinars, amo na usually sa mga forums. Maya ra pa gid, may KABALAKA Gallery kita. Ara pa gid sa gallery naton, we have all those maps. Tapos sa KABALAKA Tour gina-include ina naton.

Torreta: Ini ya from your end, from the LGU to the barangay. Are there means as well where the barangay leaders are the ones sharing their risk knowledge to you as part of the overall preparation?

Magno: huo because we use participatory processes so we can only come up with the solid risk assessment through key informant interviews, FGD. Nagsugod na amo ang sa participatory risk assessment ang mga data nga yara dira sa barangay. So sila na ang resource persons pero perception based ini siya.

Torreta: maam, information from DILG City Director Oscar Lim Jr, last year you had this activity with the barangay officials for them to...

Magno: Similar sa inyo (academe) UnRISK (Unpacking Resilience Inclusive and Innovative Strategies for Knowledge Building Capacity Building)

Torreta: where they are the ones who identified the risks in their areas, what do you call that?

Magno: UnRISK gani, part na siya ang risk assessment. Ang title sadto UnRISK. So subong nag-evolve na siya, we do UnRISK sessions para sa academe, next namon nga ubrahon is sa private sector kay what we realize is that "we cannot work with these sectors kon ang imo partner wala nakaintindi kon

ano ang risks". So even with the documents in the UNDRR, it all starts with understanding the risks. So that is why naconcpetualize ina siya ang UnRISK.

Torreta: So sectoral approach

Magno: Sectoral tapos later kay naka-mention man ko sa staff, siling ko lantawa bala it was Women's Month, siling ko wala gid kita ya activity para sa women. Siling ko kon gintipon niyo be ang mga kababaihan ta kag we start talking about disasters and how it affects women. Siling ya maam, desidido ko ya, ang next naton nga i-UnRISK si women. Siling ko indi anay ubosa ang private sector, CSOs, kag tanan nga mga kababaihan dira pangkuhaa para may ara na bala sang understanding...subong naintindihan niyo na ang konsepto, how does it affects women and start there

Torreta: again, exactly, because they are the vulnerables, the senior citizen,s the PWDs

Magno: that is why excited gid ako katama kay di ba there is only 120 of us, kaina pamangkot mo. Do you think this is enough? When you have sectoral nga mga representatives...nakita ko na ini nga formula nga nag-work sa CBARAD (Community-Based Adaptation and Resilience Against Disaster). Strengthen mo ang council strengthen mo ang academe, CSOs, PWDs, kita mo nag-work...ang ending we want to see the barangays nga naka-intindi sang risk knowledge nila, they come up with their solutions, with the understanding of climate and disaster risks...kami ang taga-trigger, we provide the platform, provide the avenue for discussions, hulag kita tanan

Torreta: and again, we are all affected eh

Magno: and that is the idea of localization, baliki bala si Sendai Framework, swak gid kita

Torreta: that is why it is important to document this not only for archival but for sharing as well

Magno: and we know that we will not live forever, apra may balikan man

Torreta: maam we are done with risk knowledge, primarily this is more on sharing of risk assessments, on the observation and forecasting, how do you communicate? Initially you mentioned this, there is some sort of processing

Magno: in communicating that to the public, we post ang advisories, tapos may (radio) frequency kita nga dedicated sa mga barangays. Tikal ko lang pero I do not think kon ginapractice nila kay kon kaisa gina-monitor ko sila, siling ko "wala na kamo naga-announce". Kay tani kada guwa sina, gina-radyo man nila. Sa start eh ginaradyo nila so kinahanglan gid i-eksido. Pero amo ina siya tani ang ihaboy. Think about it, kon ang 180 ka mga barangays are connected, pag radyo mo kundi baton sang tanan eh. Imagina, for example hit and run, pag radyo mo kundi dasig dasig but anyway that is one of the ways that we communicate the risks sa ila. Tapos amo na chast groups, Viber groups

Torreta: text messaging?do you still use that

Magno: yes kaso lang connected abi ina siya sa link sa FB so padala ko sa imo, here is my email address...wala be kami sang system parehos kag ICAG kag FedFire nga maka-text blast. Nag-attempt kami pero hindi pa sila handa kay medyo may kamahalan.

Torreta: this is you to the community, may ara man sang pabalik? Again because we are looking at the participatory approach

Magno: ang feedback and feedforward

Torreta: from the community for the observation and forecasting, do we also have that mechanism for example... sa river control early warning system in place, what are our existing mechanisms dira from the barangay to the city?

Magno: same thing, same nga channel. Sometimes they send us emails parehas sadto nga grabe ang ulan. Well we receive information from the barangays mismo

Torreta: through what?

Magno: email, same thing kon ano ang channel. Sa radyo or kis-a sa text messages or Viber group with matching pictures kay nagapangayo bulig. Nakibot gani ko sa area ni kap Barbie, sa diin na area ni kap, diri sa Nabitasan. Te kay ginapadala mana namon kay mayor. Mayor amo ni ang mga ginabaha, amo ni ang mga pictures. The following day, ginapada-an ni city engineers. So nagbalik si kap Barbie, siling ya maam thank you gid kay ginpalab-ot niyo. So bisan sila kaisa nagaka-amazae kay dasig ang action ni city government. So we encourage them that you report. We share information, indi ka magsiling nga wala man ina gihapon kay you can never tell. Lantawa kay gin-aksyonan ni Mayor kundi lipay sila may drainage sila... nami pa gid ang role of the media, ang baha diri sa Calubijan, nabatian ko lang sa radyo. Tapos sige ka istorya nagtawag ko kap, ano to kap kay nag-anticipate na ko, siling ko wala ka dayon nagreport. Te gi-ubrahan namon sulat, hatag kay city engineer sa DPWH...

Torreta: Maybe we can expound as well sa observation and monitoring especially diri sa flooded and coastal communities... sa flooding kun mag reach na siya sa level nga medyo critical na, sa threeshold. From your end, bal-an ninyo ina kay you have your technology here but si barangay. Do they also inform you about their particular situation?

Magno: that particular nga sensor is in Calubihan, ang determination of the flood height sila na ang naghatag because you cannot develop alert signals without discussing that sa public. Kay kon indi nila maintindihan how can they take actions. That is the purpose of the early warning system for you to warn the people earlier so that they can also take early action. So ang pagdetermine sina sila, halin sa ila, upod sa ila

Torreta: per for example sa threshold na, do they inform you about that?

Magno: huo, amo to gani ang istorya ko, "maam nagtunog na siya, nagtunog na". Naga-inform sila kag not just in Calubijan ha, sa tanan nga kabarangayan kay again ang kada district may focal person so may ano na sila, may chatgroup. So whatever happend, "maam, grabe na gid ang balod diri". So gapadala na sila sang videos sang coastal tapos ginahaboy na sang amon barangay (focal) diri sa OpCen or sa viber may ara man kami natawag man nga virtual OpCen. So si OpCen na diri kag tanan nga mga barangays namon, whatever information nga nagather sa barangay amo man ina ang ginapost namon or ang ginahaboy kanday mayor kag sa council members.

Torreta: ang sa coastal barangays maam the same?ga-inform man sila? Usually ano ang ila?

Magno: storm surges, sunog. Kaisa buhawi. Naga-inform sila, kis-a nagakalipat man eh pro mabatian ko sa radyo ginapavalidate ko. But there are barangays nga manawag gid kay ngaa mamangkot kon pwede nila magamit amg ila QRF, kay they need guidance. So kaisa kon malipat, ginasuut-sulit man namon ina sa mga focal persons, keep on reminding ang mga barangay magreport kay kon indi ka mag-insist malipatan ka man nila.

Torreta: going back sa UnRISK, lain ya ang risk per area

Magno: that is why nag-create kita sang district level. Again with the recognition of the peculiarity and uniqueness sang kada district

Torreta: Sa communication and dissemination, we covered this earlier but from the barangay, basi pwede ta madugagan ang sa Public Address System, sa coastal

Magno: tanan na, siguro majority of the barangays, may data na ang BDRRMS namon...

Torreta: for the response capability, if a situation requires snag response na for example baha, kinahanglna evacuation or kinahanglan pasuyupan tubig. Do you inform them about that?...

Magno: the protocol is that,if there is a need to do preemptive evacuation, sorry for context, typhoon or flooding, di ba nagapa PDRA (pre disaster and risk assessment). Usually, wala pa gani kasulod or ara na sa sulod, mga 2,3, or 5 days antes mag-abot sa aton, nagapa PDRA na kita kag monitor. So if there is a need to do preemptive evacuation, ang protocol is that upod na nga daan si CSWDO. So sila na ni barangay ang naga-istoryahanay. So if there is a need nga buksan ang mga evacuation centers, usually

mga schools so usually si CSWDO kag barangay, kag si school principal, si DepEd, sila ang naga-istoryahanay, so dasig lang man ina siya.

Torreta: Pero may specific role si CDRRMO on that, for example to communicate that to the affected population?

Magno: So after sang PDRA, usually na naga-raise nana kami sang alert status namon from white to blue. So kun blue, gina-encourage nana ang tanan nga mga barangays to activate their barangay emergency operation centers. Amo na ina siya, so any activities that they will do, they will be reminded nga palihog magreport kag usually may situation report kami so makita ninyo ina. Makita man ina ninyo kon ano ang gin-obra sang mga barangays. May mgan barangays nga naga-obra gid sang ila sitrep so gina-attach ina namon. Kon wala SitReo, ang actions taken nila. Interesting gani

Torreta:almost halfway naman kita, we covered this earlier but just to elaborate lang. The various strategies utilized by your institution or office in the communication of early warning messages. So earlier we discussed the use of handheld radios sa barangay, social media like Facebook, ano pa gid? Media? How do you partner with legacy media?

Magno: we have a very active nga PIO so kami gid ina, so if you want to know more about what we do, risk communication, sila na. And then we tap, kay active ang Iloilo City Press Corps, nami sila.

Torreta: So traditional media, of course we are also venturing new media, may mga online personalities or influencers, do you also tap them?

Magno: wala, tama ka no. influencers, sige nga let us try that

Torreta: since you mentioned yesterday, cosplayers

Magno: ang sa Gallery ato iya, to gain attention but you know that is more of a decoration

Torreta: maam how about ang sa interpersonal communication, te amo ni mag-meetings kamo with the barangays

Magno: huo. Webinars kay kaisa na naga go-online kami kon dasigay kay it is quite difficult na nga tipunon sa isa ka lugar so we utilize the online platform like Zoom

Torreta: ano pa gid maam, ang Gallery

Magno: KABALAKA Gallery, and KABALAKA Camp and Tour

Torreta: ano pa gid ayhan?

Magno: we develop our own videos man and IEC materials aside kay PIO nga gina-obra

Torreta: Commonly, ano ni nga mga IEC materials maam?

Magno: Depende kon ano nag prevailing nga event so like subong nga grabe nag init so related sa increasing heat. Kon tig-ululan, baha. Kon sa tag-ilinit pati ang sa health aspect ginasulod na

Torreta: pero in what forms ini ang mga IECs ninyo?

Magno: ano na siya, posters sa online, electronic copies sina. Sang una naga-record kami audio, amo na ang ginahatag sa mga barangays bala nga gina-play nila.

Torreta: sa channels/media utilize by your office, amo man ini no so far?

Magno: huo

Torreta: sa strategies, I think very vital diri ang sign language

Magno: Yes, ang pinaka-latest namon nga gin-obra ang communication boards.

Torreta: can you elaborate sa communication boards maam?

Magno: knowing nga ang mga responders naton cannot communicate with the mute and there is a recognition nga emergency situation ini siya. Well based on the experience with Japan, nakita sang mga PWDs naton, it might work nga kon indi ka kabalo sang sign languages naton. Tudlo-tudlo ka nalang. So amo ina siya, ang contest sang sign board daw mga possible answers sang mga deaf/mute nga sitwayson like are you in pain?

Torreta: Sin-o gagamit sina?

Magno: ang mga responders...ang mga basic questions nga kon mag-assess ka bala sa mga patients

Torreta: ang sa risk knowledge to, forecast, macover sa use of sign language but are you exploring or may additionla interventions kita subong to cater sang ila specific needs?

Magno: Huo like last year nag-consultation balik sa ila. Ginpamangkot man after pandemic like “do you think, in the efforts of the City Government to promote resilience sa Iloilo City, do you think your sector has been given enough attention, so naistoryahan. Ang plano namon this year, mapa-UnRISK man anay. And then just like what happened with the academe, once naintindihan ang risk, let us talk, what can we do together to help your sector

Torreta: Exactly, I think that is very vital

Magno: Siling namon, tama na ina nga sagi lang kita kademand sang rights ninyo. Agian following that community resilience building strategy, self help anay. What can you do to help yourselves?

Torreta: maam sa medium of language used in communicating the early warning messages? Ano ini siya ang language nga ginagamit naton?

Magno: Hiligaynon but usually sa mga documents it is in English

Torreta: why is it that the CDRRMO is using the local language?

Magno: Majority sang population naton are Hiligaynon speaking, it is easier to communicate, to express ang information in Hiligaynon, mas maintindihan ini sang mga pumuluyo. But again we also recognize nga damo turista dira, Kag mix community na kita, may mga Cebuano. So we also utilize English

Torreta: So it is like combination

Magno: Combination like sa IEC materials, may English ina siya kag Hiligaynon

Torreta: do you have a specific target audience in the communication of the early warning messages or it is just for the general population?

Magno: well we share information for the general public but for a particular event that will impact a certain community, naga-zero in kami dira. For example, bagyo do ba, ano ang mga preparasyon sa paghanda sa ini nga bagyo? Perog ina-highlight gid ina namon ang preparation sang mga coastal communities kay di ba as what we have discussed sa aton kahapon sa CPU, these hazards do not come alone, may mga upod. Ang baskog nga hangin, may storm surge siya ya nga barkada nga upod. So ang information namon, ma-zero in man ina siya sa coastal community. SO kamo dira kay may storm surge, so mag-alignat sa dalagko nga mga balod

Torreta: so targeted as well siya, while may general approach may target man siya. Maam balikan ko lang kadali ang sa medium of language, you are using a mix of languages, English and Hiligaynon as our local language diri. So far in your experience, do you feel like we are doing okay on that aspect on the communication of Hiligaynon or English, or medyo may mga constraints man kita? Ka for example, there are words in English especially with PAGASA nga “tail-end of a cold front, shearline: things like

that no in English and or technical terms, and medyo budlay siya, ako as a communicator budlay siya pangitaan counterpart or if may counterpart siya mismo. Do you experience that as well?

Magno: kon intindihon mo lang siya based on that term lang gid di ba, "tail-end of a cold front" amo ina, but I think it is within sa explanation ina siya. And still it is better understood kon explained in Hiligaynon. Ang pagpati ko, indi ini siya kinahanglan intindihon sang tawo nga word-for-word, but general concept, ano ang tail-end of a cold front. Kay kon iikspleikar mo ina siya sa akon in Hiligaynon, ay ah amo man lang ina gali. So then it will be easily understood but then the issue right now is all about comprehension. Nagpaguwa information about cancellation of classes, sin-o to nagpaguwa, si Panay News bala, nga wala klase, Nagilinaway sila, ano gid bala, may klase or wala. Te nagilinaway sila. Siling nila, ka mga mango, Sila man ang nagtilirinahay, so nagkadlaw ko . I think ang issue gid kay in the comprehension. Ang public naton subong especially the younger ones, they are not used in reading. Unlike sa aton...

Torreta: Headlines lang subong ang ila nabasa eh

Magno: Huo

Torreta: And sometimes strategies man ini sang iban man. So going back, explanation in Hiligaynon. Diri ini masulod ang contextualization, you give an additional information, you are explaining the concept and the context. Kon si Sec. Solidom pa, impact-based

Magno: Pareho na sang una di ba, siya man ina ang nag-istorya. When you explain, ano ina siya kabaskog si 120 km/h nga hangin haw? Di bala, so ano ang palahambingan nila. Daw parehos bala kon magsakay ka sa jeep, ang speed ya sina 120 so amo ina kabaskog ang hangin then people will understand, ah amo ina siya kabaskog

Torreta: exactly

Magno: contextualization or association, I do not know how you will call it. Give an example nga related sa day-to-day nga experience sang tawo then they will come to understand

Torreta: and we are doing that

Magno: hopefully

Torreta: of course that is the aspiration

Magno: kay kon nakita mo sa may glass namon ma board, may parte didto sa urban island heat effect, siling ko gani sa ila, explain niyo ina. Let us keep on doing videos explaining ina sa tawo para maintindihan, pati ang mga terms nila sa PAGASA naistoryahan namon, kay nami ni siya si Patricia, maam amo ini siya ang meaning niya, maintindihan namon

Torreta: maam sa early warning messages, ang vulnerable sectors, of course even though minute, or smaller ang ila population as compared to the general population, still they are part of the population and they need additional interventions because of course of their situation. How do you communicate this to the vulnerable population like for example the youth, the senior citizens PWDs?

Magno: well, ang general di ba, ang default nga pag-communicate through FB so we just assume nga ara kamo or bal-an na ninyo ina or was it last year, when we started issues with dengue, AGE, nag-organize na kami sina sang mga groups per sector, so ang sa youth may ara na ina siya kay ginapa-agi namon kay SK but we do understand nga damo pa ina kay I find it difficult to work with the young people nowadays, day ka budlay lang bala pero isa ina sa mga handicap namon sa subong. Pwede ko hambalon nga we have a way to communicate with them but how they use that information, how they respond to it, wala ko kabalo. So basi isa ina sa lantawon namon ano. Sa mga elderly, sang una active ni ang OSCA sa amon, since sini nga tuig, January naistoryahan na ina namon sang PWD namon nga staff, kinahanglan i-intensify ang work with the OSCA. Te ang PWD nasuguran na , liwat, CBARA day naka-obra na ina kamo together but last year, December lang kami nagsugod pero si OSCA, we still have yet to tap them.

Torreta: I think diri man ini masulod ang UnRISK maam no

Magno: amo na ina siya nag entry point namon sa tanan na nga sectors sa subong

Torreta: for you to establish that linkage first and for them to situate themselves

Magno: that is why ginapanumdom ko kaina samtang nagaistorya kita, so di bala nag inyo kahapon i understanding the concepts and looking at the application of these concepts sa kada district kon diin kamo. Pero samtang naga-istoryahanay kita siguro ang handling sa ila, siguro this is the concept, ano ang nakita niyo sa kaugalingon ninyo, ano ang inyo vulnerability sa nagkalain-lain nga mga hazards para pagbalik namon sa information, oh academe amo ini ang siling sang mga tigulang, basta baha amo ini ang vulnerability nila, so that we also understand their context.

Torreta: correct, and I think maam you have mentioned ang sa medium of language, nga in Hiligaynon, that is for the senior citizens on that sense nga mas mahapos man nila maintindihan generally. Sa process maam incrafting the content of the of these early warning messages before you communicate, you mentioned this earlier sa analysis. So generally, can you go us through the process

Magno: wala lang, kami lang ang naga-istoryahanay, I leave it to Darwin kay siya ang head. So what does it mean, amo lang ina pirme ang guidance, so the staff would recommend. There are times nga nagapungko kami like kon mga big events na gid bala. Like ano to man, paglupok ata sang bulkan, ginpungkuan gid ina namon. So ang ang general direction. So ma scenario setting na kami, that is where the analysis. Di ba, ano ang data subong, that is where the analysis would come in kag sige, knowing this, ano nga information ang paguwaon naton? So what do we want the people to know and what to do? Amo ina siya, kay grabe ang init so maano kamo. Like last year kay di ba grabe ang init, so maano kamo? So what we did was to meet with the different sectors. Gintap namon si city engineer, ang mga architect to talk sa mga contractors ta sa construction kay we also need to look at the welfare sang mga construction workers. Ginhamalan sila, so amo ini ang pinakamataas nga mga temperatura sa adlaw nga ini. So you might want to change ang schedule sang iyo obrahanay. Antes nga paubrahon niyo ang mga tawo ninyo after lunch, basi pwede nga ang breaktime nila, you start at 4:00 and then asta na lang sa gab-i.

Torreta: so again maam, there is this processing iya in your level...others usually in the context of typhoon actually even with the volcanic eruption of course because of the ongoing situation, kon ano ang advisory for example PAGASA or PHIVOLCS for example, commonly, kon ano ang information, as it is lang man ang pag-communicate. We understand nga that is the given information pero in your end you are doing the analysis, the scenario setting before you communicate. Why is that so? I mean are these available information in the advisories not enough? Or what is the reason as to why we are doing that extra effort?

Magno: because these advisories are based on scientific nga mga organizations and you know, scientists talk in a language nga quite difficult to understand by the common tao, so ang amon nga role is again understand that. How will we communicate Science to the public. I think it is the role of the CDRMO OpCen nga intindihon ina siya ang Science and then simplify that information kay again if we are tasked to communicate that information and we do not understand that information, how can you expect the public nga intindihon siya and to take action. Indi gani namon ma articulate, so int is incumbent upon us to understand all this anay. Limpyohe sa level naton kay we also anticipate nga interviewhon ka karun sang media, ano isabat mo...so we cannot influence people to do preemptive evacuation or early action because garbage in and garbage out, we also fail to communicate nga amo sini ang posible matabo. So ang siling ko pirme sa staff. Ang trabaho naton, we are several steps ahead of them. Kon si Sec. Solidon, disaster imagination so creating a common operating scenario matters gid ina siya. Kay kon indi mo maimagine ang pwede nga matbao, ano nga actions ang pwede mo maguide sa mga tawo

Torreta: we are down in the last few questions, maam do you consider the public as part of the process in developing and communicating the EWS?

Magno: of course, kay ngaa ano ang prime ginasulit-sulit sa four elements nga ina kag ni sir Monroy failure sa isa ka element, palpak. Tuod man kay that happened to me, bagyo OCD days ko pa to si Mayor Mabilog, wala ako nakabalo kon ano ang agreements. Pagka-gabi gahod gahod ya ang ambulansiya, pabalik-balik. Pinangakig ako siling ko ano man ini, indi sila kakaita kon diin ang

pasyente? Gali imo during the meeting he mentioned nga we will inform ang taga coastal nga maps-uwang kami but failure to inform ang taga barangay nga amo ina nag ubrahon, indi namon mainterpret kon ano ang buot hambalon sang uwang so failure. Te kundi , will I be motivated to do early action kay wala ko naintindihan. So amo ina critical ang mga tawo to be part of the process sa pagdevelop sang EWS...redundancy pa gid gali, you explore all channels, you explore all possible nga mga pamaagi to inform the public, redundancy para nga you cannot claim nga wala kami ya nakabalo

Torreta: maam how vital is the participation of the public in the development and communication of EWS?

Magno: critical kay at the end of the day ang end user of the product is the public . Again failure to understand what you want them to do, failure to take action would mean loss of live and destruction of properties

Torreta: but as what we have discussed earlier based on the information that you shared, what I am getting is that it is not only about the city communicating this to the public, because there are existing mechanisms from the community, the barangay level to the city level as well. So it is like , it is not just about them as the end-users but hindi lang sila recipient, they are part

Magno: they can also provide inputs, tama. Amo man ina ang feedback kag feedforward, pwede gid sila makareport

Torreta: maam you have discussed this yesterday sa aton nga workshop, last nalang man sa recommendation...I think importante nga ma-explore ang madocument naton ang KABALAK as the overall program sang Iloilo City Government, can you please expound on that?

Magno: this is the offshoot sang CBARAD nga project funded by JICA, so ang inspiration manlang sina came from the term itself "kabalaka" to show compassion, to show that you care kay at the end of the day we want nga Iloilo is a place where everybody feels secured living here I think we can only do that if we develop that culture of safety, resilience, sa tanan indi bala and that can only happen kon ang mga pumuluyo naton nakabalo kon ano ang ubrahon. They know what to do before, during, and after the disaster and at the same time, they do activities to prevent the onset of the disasters. Ang ikaduha ang local leaders gid naton, they govern based on well bal-an ta naman ang good governance but kon may siya sang leaning sa risk reduction, sa risk governance nga lens bala para when they do programs and projects, amo ina nag thinking , to reduce the risks that we have sa mga pumuluyo naton. So amo ina siya ang idea sa KABALAKA program naton. So to develop that culture of safety, may KABALAKA tour kita, may KABALAKA gallery, may KABALAKA camp. All of these are meant to educate people. Ano ang risks nga gina-atubang naton and what can you do. Amo ina siya. And then we also have programs kon institution naman siya, ang entry point is institution so CDRRMC, sa BDRRMC, kag subong ang sa pinakalatest naton ang District DRRM Council, so amo man ina siya we strengthen their capabilities man and competencies. May KABALAKA sa barangay kita , we assist ang mga barangays in understanding their risks to governance. So amo man ina siya ang sa may city level, so we invest in their education. By education we mean learning visits and then can we use the whole of the society approach as a strategy so we try to reach out to as many stakeholders as possible kay ngaa risk reduction, climate and disaster resilience, it is a business of everyone hindi bala from what you do as an individual as an organization, it contributes to the greater good sang syudad so amo ina ang gusto naton matabo from my level ano ang pwede ko mahimo, so amo ina siya ang sa may KABALAKA nga ano program naton

Torreta: maam can you please expound sa District DRRM Council? Because again what is stipulated sa RA 10121 is the LGU so city, municipal, down to the barangay. This is a district eh and this is of course in the context of a city which has several districts. Can you please expound?

Magno: The creation of district nga clustering of the barangays no is something nga I do not know sa history sini, something nga daw pang mas management nga strategy. This is not created by a particular ordinansa. Wala ini siya nga naga-create so wala ini siya sang political nga division, recognition lang ini siya. So that is why it is not covered by RA 10121 nga ginasing nga dapat may district level. So this is just an initiative sang CDRRMC naton kay again because of the localization efforts naton sa DRR, nakita anton nga it is quite difficult to work sa 180 barangays. And since naga-exist ang clustering of the barangays per district, and there is a recognition nga again ang kada district lain-lain ang timpla, lain-lain ang gina-atubang nga mga hazards. They have their own peculiarities, uniqueness so ang mga

local leaders diri they are used in working together as part of the district so siling namon why don't we try this one but we just have to be clear on the functions sini and ang sa role, so why try to check with the DILG kon ano ang ginasing sang layi kag sa mga DRR experts naton, isa lang ang guidance nila, klaruhon niyo lang kon ano nga powers ang may ara sa ila. So we agreed nga it is just a recommendatory nga powers ang may ara sa ila. They cannot get the funds, access the funds but they can prioritize for this district amo ni nga mga projects. So ang mag-manage sang mga proyekto is stil the CDRRM di bala and we can identify sa ini nga mga lugar butit can be anchored sa proposal sang kada district. So amo ina siya we patterned the composition to the RA 10121 nga composition but mas looking into mga local partners pag-abot sa CSO, private sector so like nag other city offices may mga focal person per district sa naga-swak man like City Health Office, may mga district health officers, so pasok. Si CSWDO mo, may mga focal persons man, pulis, BFP, so ang nami lang di ba we do not have the opportunity to talk as a district kay usually kon mag meeting puros nga bossing sa ibabaw, ang mga department heads. So this time, we are giving them the floor to discuss nga okay so since we belong to the same district, and we are more familiar with the issues, the data is with us, so what can we do together.

Torreeta: will the EWS also be part of the distinct level?

Magno: of course, and that is what I am most excited about kay nga-a for example dengue, so indi na kami maginistoryahanay diri sa city level, ma sma pattern mo siya kya for example sa Molo, ano kadamo ang cases. So how do we tell the public di ba about dengue, may generic na na nga campaign but where can we focus our efforts. Diri sa data ni CHO, diri ang damo nga cases for example sa Boulevard, so mazeroin, mas matutukan and the reporting can be done dira sa district pagpasaka sa ibabaw mapanghawakan namon

Torreeta: Strategic siya...aside form that part ba si I-CARE sa KABALAKA program?

Magno: Yes, it may not be labeled as a KABALAKA Center but ang prinsipyo, localizing the efforts, pasok gid si I-CARE. Kag ini siya di ba part of the localizing the risk governance kay ara kana mo sa community per distinct may ara ka, kaisa doble pa gani. Like in the case of Jaro, we have Balantang and Ungka. So bringing the services closer sa mga pumuluyo

Torreeta: Ano ini nga mga services maam?

Magno: emergency, tanan eh. May it be EWS, prevention nga mga programs tanan but currently ang available amo ina sya nag sa emergency, sa ICER sa USAR, pulis, sa mga sunog pero dala naan tanan kay may ara ka nga space sa kada district for the people nga magtililipon so amo ina nag target namon for this year, buhion ang kada district, ang mga leaders dapat nagakit-anay sila dira. Use that as your ano bala opisina nga dira kamo naga-converge

Torreeta: it is like decentralizing not only the power but also the responsibilities. Of course in doing that, we are capacitating them as a community in their own level

Magno: di ba, sa pagka ganda-ganda, so that is CFDRR to you at the local level

Torreeta: maam if there are areas that we can improve on or areas for improvement for Iloilo City Government in the communication of EWS, what would that be?

Magno: amo to siya siling ko, aside from the technical staff, the form eh, the form on how we deliver this one kay like for example, gapost post lang na kami, So parang specific to the millennials, keeping up with the trends di bala and to develop more materials nga mas sectoral

Torreeta: Actually connected to that ang akon nga last question, how can Iloilo City Government achieve or be more responsive, inclusive, and sustainable in the communication of EWS? That is my last question

Magno: again, amo to siya, following on the EWS man di bala, on the four elements, it should be anchored on the risk assessments gid ya kay you cannot develop a material that is not in sync with the current realities so ang understanding of the risks balik balik gid ina prime. It is really the understanding of the risks that will spell a lot of difference sa pagcommunicate mo sa tawo. Understanding that risks

and how it can affect these sectors nagamatter kon paano mo ginadevelop ang imo nga communication material and how you will communicate that to the public kay the mor specific you get the more aligned sa mga needs sa kada sector nga you are giving them the perfect reason nga tama this is what I am going through and this is what I should do

Torreta: of course this is response as what you have mentioned, what you are doing right now, this is you becoming inclusive to the sectors

Magno: and how do we make it sustainable, Lucy musy have mentioned the barangay information officers. In her change initiative in the international training program of MSB her idea was that for every barangay there is this information officer nga panaugan niya sang mga information. If we have the BDRRMC, within the BDRRMC, we included the participation sang Barangay IO. So ang role ni BIO, naka-angot kay PIO. So amo ina siya, what I would like to think nga kon ano ang sa city level, masustain ina sa barangay levels through the BIOs as aprt sang redundancy naton.

Torreta: but in terms of the mechanisms and processes for you paano siya mangin sustainable, RA 10121 says nga dapat kada barangay may ara sang BDRRMC. So amo ina siya...establish ya ang network ni DRR down to the barangay level. Amo ina ang nanamian ko sa RA 10121. That is why any information, ang iban nga mga offices for example we have this record of informal settlers for every, or in the City of Iloilo but this is not official, siling ko te pavalidate ninyo but we do not have enough resources, ano siling ko ipaagi kay CDRRMC panaug kay BDRRMC kay automatically mahulag gid ina siya because establish na ang network...
END

Interview with DILG City Director Oscar Lim Jr. Dated April 4, 2025

Name: Oscar Lim Jr.

Age: 53

Sex: Male

Civil Status: Married

Occupation: Government official

Affiliation: Director of DILG Iloilo City Field Office

Torreta: What is the role of City DILG in Iloilo City Government's communication of its EWS?

Lim: So if you look at sa system, ang role, especially kun mapa-guwa si OCD (Office of Civil Defense). Si OCD will send a communication to DILG Region VI, then they will download the communication to us, example mga weather disturbance or what then amo ina nag ipasa namon sa LGU (Local Government Unit). Kon need nga magpasaka sang alert level so abay naman ina sa advisory. The i-check namon una-una sa checklist namon " is the chief executive on station?" or diri siya sa area niya, kay bal-an ta nga damo mga banwa bala kis-a nga kon mag-abot ang bagyo, may emergency, wala ang mayor. So number 1 na sa checklist. Pag mag-okay naa na ina ang checklist mo, sunod-sunod...we have this checklist bala sir like within sa AOR si LCE, na-inform si LGU of the weather alert, supposed to be with proof of service kay before kinahanglan nga magpa-pirma kapa sa mayor sang proof of service nga na-istorya mo siya. Pero usually ang na-obra namon pag nag-textanay na kami, na-inform mo na siya, screen-shot, okay na ina siya. Then, na-convene na bala sa CDRRMC upon receiving the weather bulletin kag tanan-tanan ini. So kon lantawon ta, diri be sa city, the CDRRMO under kay maam Donna (Magno), they make things easier for us. Kay wala pa naka-abot ang communication nga ma-heightened alert, sila ya nakapasaka na sang alert. Naka-RDANA na sila. Kumpleto na. Ang iban be nga LGUs kun wala sang notice from the regional office, so wala, hulat lang. So diri sa city kaisa, naka-declare na si CDRRMO sang blue alert, wala pa naka-abot ang notice halin sa region, especially during weekends. So ang obra namon during weekends, gina-advance kay maam Donna, pati ang RDANA, ang tanan kumpleto na, prepositioned na ang mga equipment. Diri be sa city hulag ang mga equipment nila kay may I-CARE, so hulag siya katama. Kag ang naga-send text blast si CDRRMO, lab-ot dangat sa mga kapitan.

Torreta: I do not want to put words in your mouth director but the way I see it, the way I understand sa imo pag-describe earlier nga alert sila, so alert sila and daw ka proactive

Lim: Yes, very proactive sila

Torreta: Before the announcement from your agency, may ara na sila iya efforts

Lim: Yes, may efforts na sila

Torreta: Okay but DILG as the chair on the preparedness thematic area where the Early Warning System falls, so as what you have mentioned, so naga-coordinate kita from OCD as the counterpart diri ni NDRRMC to the LGU. And the same time, you mentioned this checklist, amo to ang abscess naton.

Lim: Basis naton kon ready si LGU ukon indi. Kapin pa bala nga kon ang tracking for example, baskog nga bagyo dira gid maagi, so tanan na, checklist. So kami naman, ang obra namon, tawag lang sa CDRRMO. Kay before sina, usually pag baskog nga bagyo ang maagi, may emergency na na si CDRRMO nga meeting. Didtio gid ina sa I-CARE sa Gaisano, so didta gina-discuss na ina tanan.

Torreta: Ang checklist, amo ina siya sa Operation Listo Manual

Lim: Oo, amo ini

Torreta: In the context of disasters especially of typhoons wala man ini iya sang schedule or earthquake, and proactive si LGU on that end, sa inyo office director, may dedicated personnel, or how many personnel does your office have whose primary function is on that aspect, ang pag-coordinate sang EWS?

Lim: Actually ang sa coordination, may focal person kami nga isa but during typhoons na nga naga-require nga naga-duty, ginalantaw lang namon kon sin-o ang lapit, usually ang taga diri sa city or outside like Pavia nga nagapauli...Bal-an mo diri, subong lang kami nagdamo, before pito lang kami so indi kamo kahambal bala nga tanan, may itudo. So kon sin-o lang ang available.

Torreta: Since monitoring ang coordination iya primarily ang function ni DILG director sa LGU, one focal plus augmentation if needed, ang augmentation depende sa availability of the personnel. Most of the time, mga pila ini sila kabilog?

Lim: Usually, minimum of two ang naga-duty...ang ginalantaw namon kon baskog gid ang bagyo ang availability of transport...

Torreta: Sa imo assessment based on your experience and severity of the situation before, may pila ayhan ka dedicated personnel ang ideal to man the OpCen ninyo or with the city government if that is the situation?

Lim: Actually, kon lantawon mo gid no need gid gani kami nga didto kay kaisa daw pabug-at pa kami didto kay with or without us, ang management sang CDRRMO is very effective so kon didto nalang, may additional messages nga halin sa amon, amo ina ang ginapasa namon sa tawo namon didto, para lab-ot ma dayon sa CDRRMO

Torreta: With the knowledge and skills naman in communicating this early warning system ang in coordinating this sa city as part of your monitoring director, do you think you have enough personnel equipped with the knowledge and skills to do that?

Lim: Actually, more than enough kay hambal ko gani ang focal isa lang, si Destiny kay very easy ang communication sa city, we have internet, bisan diin ka lang diri may signal ang telepono mo, maka-access ka Messenger, Viber, kag usually bisan diin lang sila. Ang ano lang namon kon baskog gid nag bagyo, dapat may tawo kami nga naga-duty kay gina-require man kami nga may tawo kami didto

Torreta: Director, how familiar are you with the elements of early warning system?

Lim: Indi ko na familiar gid kay pag-abot mo sa director, general ka nalang. Pero pag-abot mo sa specific, si focal.

Torreta: Okay, maybe si maam Destiny, would you like to answer that...

Binobo: ...for the early warning, isa man ka beauty sa office aside sa usual nga gina-obra namon for the monitoring, may ara abi audits nga naga-check man sa early warning ni city, sa SGLG naton sir, dira man nagaguwa nga capacity ni city for early warning system. So dira gid makita ang specifics sang ila capacity, kon ano ang available sa early warning nila

Torreata: Kay amo ina ang basis ninyo sa pag-check sa paghatag sang SGLG man sa ila..Sa inyo dataset Ms Destiny, in terms of early warning system ni Iloilo City, kumusta man sila?

Binobo: So far okay gid sila, ang barangays okay man sir ang early warning system ni barangay kay gina-make sure man ni CDRMO nga complete gid sa early warning system ang all barangays unless siguro kon indi gid kaya sang capacity ni barangays, dira na masulod si city nga mag-assist. And usually sa mga kilid sang coastal dira gid ang focus nila for early warning system especially for typhoon...mas focused sila sa typhoons

Lim: Kag ano sir, ilabi kon mag baskog ang ulan, pila na kabilog diri ang rain gage? Nagahaboy na dayon sa area nga ang rain gage naton for the last hour amo na ini ang volume

Torreata: Si city ina?

Binobo: Yes, si city kag usually naga-send man updates si maam Donna. Aside sa GC(group chat), naga-send siya personally sang updates during typhoon for example

Lim: Kag ang reporting abi nila...

Binobo: Every 12 hours

Lim: Sobra, depende sa severity. Pro kon ulan, may level lang ina nga ma-flash lang ina nga amo ini nga lugar, wala pa ka-flash si NDRRMC, si city ya naka-notice na. Kay di BALA sa cellphone mo naga-alarm. Si city iya ang actual nga nagakatabo kay si NDRRMC ma-alert sa cellphone mo pero actually wala gali naga-ulan. Pero diri iya, mag-ulan mamessage na sila nga base sa rain gage sa amo sini nga lugar, ang ulan ta diri amo ini so ang bahaon amo ina preparar na.

Torreata: Actually connected to that ang next ko nga question, about the specific common early warning messages nga gina-communicate nila through or to your office. You have mentioned director no, rainfall. Ano pa gid?

Lim: Super high tide, kay kon mag super high tide ang mga diri na lapit sa coastal kag kita mo bisan lab-ot sa University of San Agustin ginabaha, kapin pa kon may mha low pressure plus ang heat index. Naga-send na sila

Binobo: Everyday naga-send si maam Donna sir sang updates

Lim: Like subong bala sir, as of 12 noon, nag-send na sila sang heat index...

Binobo: Kag gina-direct man nila sa mga barangays, may per district man abi

Lim: Ang mga kapitan part sang ila nga ano

Torreata: When they communicate that, syempre part kita sa GC no, aside from that, ang pag-inform nila sa barangay may other mechanisms pa gid?

Binobo: May ano abi sir, sa amo sa DILG may district, may assigned man ina sa ila per district sa gina through man ina nila sa per district, mas dasig kay may assigned na gid abi.

Torreata: Ang per district or coordinator nga ini under ini sa LGU?

Binobo: Under sa LGU, may DRR officer, may ara sila per district man nga naga-assign

Torreata: so through him or her ang pag-communicate to the barangay officials?

Binobo: Yes

Torreta: When we categorize the early warning system, we have risk knowledge, observation and forecasting, communication and dissemination, and response capability. Pwede ta ma-specify ang messages or strategies nila...

Lim: Nagapanghatag be sini sila sir sang...ang gin-obra bala sang IPO nila diri, daw mga posters, IECs, and brochures...

Binobo: Every disaster may ara sila sir

Torreta: Pero in English siya director no?

Lim: May ara sila nga Hiligaynon...amo ina ang pinaka-latest nila...

Torreta: Pero for example, specific sa risk assessments. For example sa city proper, ang inyo dira hazards are the following...may communication of that sa pagkabalo ninyo or in coordination sa inyo?

Binobo: Yes sir, gina-discuss ina actually gin per hazard ina sir sang planning sa Boracay gina per hazard ina sir para mas hapos ang pag-approach sang disaster for example sa mga coastal areas, naka-separate na na sila sa risk analysis man nila

Lim: Sa Boracay kami sina nag-obra, gin-assist namon ang barangay together with CDRRMO, nag-obra sila sang DRRM plan which ultimately nagamit ni CDRRMO ang data kay sila man ang naga-facilitate

Torreta: ang barangay officials mismo?

Binobo: Huo, sila man ang nag-identify sir

Torreta: From the level iya ni CDRRMO, for example they have technologies and assessment in coordination with other agencies man, ang ini nga mga outputs nila gina-communicate man ini to the community level, to your knowledge?

Lim: Sa barangay sir, plus ang data gani nga gin-obra ni barangay sa risk assessment nila magamit man ni CDRRMO sa response. Ang good thing, actually ang naistoryahan namon ni Donna nga why not mag go down kita sa level sang District DRR councils. Hambal niya ano ang purpose? Para nga mas tutok ang hazards para nga like for example macombine ta bala like ang City Proper divide namon sa duha ka district DRR councils nga ang isa focus siya coastal kay lain ang hazards sa coastal kag diri sa sulod baha naman. Sa Jaro lain man sa coastal lain man sa baha para bala nga mas focused kag indi lang naton paghambalon natural hazards for example ang dengue, usually ang dengue naga-clustered so mas matutukan kon sa diin nga district lang to siya nga city applicable, indi nga bilog nga city ang response. Tapnaon lang ang naga-clustering, matapna na siya didto.

Torreta: What is stated in DRRM law, up to the barangay level, but city, municipal, and barangay level. Ang district is in the context of a city which is composed of several districts. On that aspect parang this is going beyond?

Lim: Yes, ang ginalantaw namon who is the best who can recommend nga response? Sila, kay sila ang naka-eksperyensiya sang baha. Ang aton iya ang hambal sang libro amo ni ang baha, amo ni ang obrahon pero sila, sila nga didto, how did they survive? So amo na nga gin-ano namon kag last nga CDRRMC Meeting, ginresolutionan na ina plus ang functions nga i-establish ang district DRR councils nga ang role nila mag-recommend policies, mag-identify sang hazards nila sa ila area kay bal-an mo naman usually kon nagahipos hipos ka lang, wala ka hazard. Pero kon ang inyo district magahod, makita ka liwat, wala sang problema. Mas focused bala indi nga generalized like sa Iloilo City may baha, sa diin sa city kay indi man tanan ginabaha?

Torreta: If that is the situation, ang funding diin ina mahal in sa barangay or city?

Lim: Actually, wala siya funding kay policymaking body lang siya, ma-assist lang siya. Kon lantawon ta si DRRM Council, magobra siya hazard, iprioritize ni city so kaisa may mga lugar nga ma-miss , indi siya mamention, pagbotobotohay wala siya namention, indi siya priority pero kon siya ara didto, nagobra sila policy kag ginpasa nila diri so for that district amo ini ang policy kag amo ini ang hazard didto which was identified by the residents mismo

Torreta: so more of a policymaking lang siya so there is no need for funding?

Lim: Yes kay ang recommendation namon, the district council will be headed by the District ABC nga bali siya ang nagapungko nga chairperson which will also be assisted by the district nga DRR kay may tawo sila per district... tapos tanan nga kapitan nila didto members, kay diri iya indi tanan plus ang mga NGOs and POs sa ina nga district, didto man sila mamember...ang city pagdako siya katamo kag usually kon sin-o ang magahod amo lang ina ang makita mga may deprensiya didto, kag is ana nga mapungkuan bala paano mo gastuson si DRRM fund? Kay kaisa kon nakita mo nga puro baha, may kwarta malang, nga india mo pag-imitigate ang baha

Torreta: Going back didto sa elements of early warning system, ang sa response capability, for example there is an ongoing no , let us say ang response capability ni LGU to respond sa specific hazard, may involvement kamo sa ila pag-communicate?

Lim: Wala na, sila na, response na nila. Pero kon lantawon mo, more than enough ang assets ni city

Torreta: In situations like for example there would be a need for an augmentation from the national government agency...like during COVID..if that is the situation, ano ang inyo existing practice or mechanisms?

Lim: usually be if they need additional support, sa level na lang nila eh. Wala na gaagi sa amon. Kami na lang, nagapangita na lang kami medyos kon ano pa ang mabulig namon sa ila pero ang ina abi nga question, mas applicable ina sa smaller LGUs pero sa city, first class city nga ang ila resources more than enough, I think it is not a problem sa city

Torreta: We covered this earlier, sa various strategies utilized by Iloilo City Government, you mentioned gina sa Viber, sa diin pa gid director? Emails?

Lim: ang emails indi masyado pero kon matandaan mo diri sa city tanan nga radio stations gina-capture nila ang..kay si city daw may press release so mabasahan na dayon sang tanan

Torreta: So the use of traditional media?

Lim: Huo, radio, Facebook

Torreta: Ah even social media?

Lim: Huo

Torreta: Okay but sa social media, they have their own account?

Lim: Yes may ara, si mayor i-share niya, i-share ni CDRRMO, si PIO...barangays nga may Facebook

Torreta: agn mga two-way radio ya, director may ara man?

Lim: ara gihapon ang two-way radios, ang barangays may ara man. That is why I think sa last nga meeting to , maps-meeting sila liwat nga mabutang gid sang isa ka radio nga dedicated lang sa barangays kay kaisa nagasirinamo daw ...ma-training dayon sila sa mga barangays paano mag-handle sang radio

Torreta: so may traditional media, new media,may two-way radio...may barangay level man, ginagamit pa subong sa inyo monitoring ang Public Address System?

Lim: May mga barangays nga sa mga kanto may mga Public Address System

Binobo: Especially sa mga coastal barangays sir

Lim: May trumpa sila daw sa baylehan bala

Binobo: Kag ang barangays may ara man sila sir base sa inventory ta sa SGLG, may ara sila nga mga Public Address System sir

Torreta: Or trumpa, ang iban they call it Bandillo..Ang house-to-house ya director, sa inyo monitoring?

Lim: wala na siguro kay kon lantawon mo ang tawo sa barangay ang staff bala sa barangay nga mag-house to house gid except lang siguro kulang sila gid kay bisan mag-response indi kaya nga sila lang mo, so usually mga tanods malang pero gacadab-ot man ang tanan

Torreta: I am thinking similar with COVID before and with dengue, they do house to house...

Lim: Lain man abi si dengue and COVID, kay selected lang, kon bagyo abi tanan...

Torreta: Ang medium of language used nila sa pag-communicate, primarily English. May use of Hiligaynon man?

Lim: Wala abi sa level namon ina pero sa mga posters nga gin-prepare may ara nga in Hiligaynon

Torreta: so these are IECs nila nga sa inyo monitoring ang iya language is in Hiligaynon. Ano ini nga mga materials director?

Lim: More sa preparation, kon ano nag ubrahon nila kon may bagyo, may baha

Torreta: Pero sa mga forecast and advisories for example heat index or typhoon bulletin number 1?

Lim: Wala na ako nakakita nga gin-Hiligaynon ina, in English kay te pagkita mo nga 45 grabe na ina kainit, kon bagyo man luwa sa makita mo sa news kon ano siya kabaskog, batyagan mo na siya, so no need. More lang siguro sa pagpa-intindi sa mga punuluyo kon ano ang ubrahon in case mag-abot ang amo sini which nga kon lantawon mo, may Hiligaynon na sila nga version sa barangay

Torreta: Sa imo director, is there a need to localize ang pag-communicate and pag-contextualize sa pag-communicate sa mga terms nga ini? For example, te magambal koita shearline, maghambal kita tail-end of a cold front, things like that?

Lim: Budlay abi ina sir i-translat sa Hiligayno. Ang makita naton, maintindihan niya kag sa indi basta baskog hangin kag naga-ulan, amo na ina

Torreta: so may context nga baskog ang ulan kay may ano siya description...

Lim: So need mo na mag-amo ni , Low Pressure or what kay ang tawo sa barangay once na-experience nila mag-ulan, dako ang tyansa nga magbaha. Pagbaskog ang hangin, amo na ini ang bagyo nga gin-forecast nga maabot kag ti dalagko na ang mga balod sa baybayon.Highly technical abi ang shearline bisan kami gani diri...pero kon lantawon mo sa coastal mas naintindihan nila, ano na amihan, habagat, timog, so bal-an na nila. No need na naton itranslate kay kon kaisa nagalaw-ay ang ngalan...ang importante naintindihan sang tawo nga baskog hangin, baskog ang balod, they need to be in safer areas.

Torreta: Moving forward, sa pag-identify ni city sang ila target audience sa ila IECs, general population ba or may specific materials for the vulnerable the marginalized sectors like PWDs, senior citizens, children?

Lim: Generic siya, wala siya nga targetted gid like nga si senior citizen. Ang importante lang nga message nga kon may bagyo, amo ini ang ubrahon ninyo. So assume naton nga this is for the abled persons. So kon magpanaug ka bi nga i-separate mo gid nga sa ila, sa subong daw indi pa gid nila kinahanglan. Subong gani ng parte sa mga kasapatan, may ara na nga kon ano ang ubrahon sa mga

kasapatan kon may bagyo. Siguro next na ina kay ang agi sang bagyo pareho sa mga able bodied kag sa mga PWD

Torreta: ...is there a need to communicate these messages man especially that they are part of the marginalized?

Lim: Actually there is a need to communicate to them pero once nga nagpaguwa ka sang generic, it is the role of the able bodied persons in the family to take care of the PWDs kay during that time we cannot be certain nga si gobyerno ara dira sa pagrescue sa imo kay ubahon na nila kon sin-o ang hardest hit so indi na anton mahambal nga kon mabagyohan si city, si CDRRMO tanan nga lugar, daw si superman ka bala, macover niya tanan. So selected areas. So ang message mo usually is that kon ready ang mga able bodied, these able bodied persons will try to save sa mga PWDs nila

Torreta: Ang pag-obra nila sang mga advisories, to your observation and monitoring, how do they craft the content of their early warning messages?

Lim: Usually ang mga posters halin sa national, gia-localize nila diri.

Torreta: Localize in what terms? Gina-translate in Hiligaynon?

Lim: Yes, isa na pero basic ina eh. Ay gin-obra na sila nga more bala sa kon ano ang applicable sa mga balay...like sa national balde, diri bisan ano nga container...gina-localize nila kag ang mga threats kag mga hazards

Torreta: Sa mga advisories like during typhoons, kon ano ang napaguwa ni PAGASA, as is lang ang gina-share nila?

Lim: yes, naka-template na

Torreta: to your experience with them, paano nila gina-communicate ang scientific and technical information for example risk assessments, mga hazards in the area, paano nila gina-communicate sa ila population?

Lim: Usually pag-abot sa dalom, wala na na sila ga-ano kon scientific or what. Kon ano ang makita, amo na ina. Daw empirical data na lang. Usually pagscientific pag-abot sa dalom indi na maintindihan sang tawo. Remember pagbagyo Yolanda, ginhambalan sila may storm surge, the pople did not know what is a storm surge. Kon ginhambal pa siguro nila nga may tidal wave, mabaha nakapreparar ang mga pumuluyo..ang ano naton dira, more on layman's term

Torreta: laymanizing the terms

Lim: Inang mga shearline, wala ya naka-intindi ang mga tawo kon ano ina. So ang aton na lang, ang effect bala pag mag amo ni, let us treat it as bad weather

Torreta: So amo ina ang gina-obra ni city? They laymanize these scientific information?

Lim: Huo

Torreta: Ang to kaina nga naistoryahan ta nga impact-base, amo man ini ang gina-obra nila

Lim: Huo...kag kabudlay nga mag-abot ka sa barangay mag English English ka tapos wala sila kaintindi kon ano, so much better nga nagaka-explain sa ila...

Torreta: ...diri sa may processing, developing, an communicating the EWS..ang public, to your monitoring, may participation ba si public, si community, sa pagdevelop and communicate sang ial EWS?

Lim: Yes, kag usually pag-abot sa mga hazards sa barangay indi lang man na si kapitan ang nagahambal. It is because of feedback halin sa iya mga pumuluyo.

Torreta: You mentioned this earlier, may rain gage, and I understand may mga flood monitoring system man kita diri no, do the locals, the community, or the officials inform the city about the situation there?

Lim: Sa mga barangays usually may mga ano na markings ang level pero ang pinaka-common diri ang ila mga rian gage kay daw covered nga tanan nga mga districts like sa SM may ara dira so kon magtaas ang level sang rain gage sa SM, mahambal na sila nga aligmat ang sa may dungon creek kag Mandurrioa areas. Tapos may didto pana sa Jaro, pag didto sa Jaro mahambal sila nga alert na along the floodway

Torreta: Pero ang paghatag nila sang advisory about that, is it a product of their own monitoring or it is the information relayed by the locals to them?

Lim: Ang sa locals, wala pa naka-abot ang data from them, si CDRMO nakapadala na sang message sa ini nga mga barangays nga halong na kamo kay base sa rain gage sige-sige gid ang ulan kag indi gid mag-untat

Torreta: but is there a mechanism man nga si local si community , sila nag naga-inform sa city?

Lim: through the barangay officials, kay i think may antabo na diri I think sa Dungon nagabaha didto, si barangay officials mismo ang nagita kon why nagabaha siya. Nakita nila karun, ginreport nila nga ang construction sang Esplanade daw ginsirad sang contractor ang..so ang tbig indi kaguwa nagabaha sa likod

Torreta:so based on that, do you agree that the city considers the public in the development and communication of EWS?

Lim: yes, kay gina-consider nila ang mga reports kay even ang mga barangay nga most hazards base sa feedback sa mga ano ang nga, how sure are you nga amo na, kay hambal sa zone nga ini kon mag-ulan diri gabaha nga lugar

Torreta: so both top to buttom and buttom-up approach siya?

Lim: Yes, kay ti sila ang apektado to mo ang aton diri iya idea lang nga may amo ni per wala kita nakabalo kon ano gid ang natabo didto

Torreta: Director, how vital is the participation of the public in the development and communication of EWS?

Lim: Very vital kay sila ang end-user. Sila man ang nagakaapektohan so as end user and sila ang nagakapaektohan ang feedback nila is very important kay sila lang ang nakabalo kon ano ang matabo sa imo kon magbahan kag sila man ang nakabalo kon ano ang ubrahon nila didto kon magbaha. So ang aton diri maubra kita plano but the plan is based on a certain assumption. Ang ila iya didto nakita nila, naexperience nila

Torreta: Last would be the recommendation, to your observation and experience as well if there are things or areas that we can improve in the development and communication of EWS? ...

Lim: siguro ang isa sa saabt dira nag districting sang DRR councils kay because daw mas mamicro, magagamy siya, indi lang prime nga macro lang kay si city makuha ka sang top 3 nga hazards, paano karun kon si district ang number 1 hazards niya wala nakasulod sa top 3 mo? Amo ina ang example...that is why pag-propose na ni Donna siling ko much better ini para sila mismo mag-come up sang hazards, ano ang solution kag sila man ang ma-tap nga magcommunicate sa ila community kay sila mismo ang didto.

Torreta: So ang districting, this is like tailor-fitting the response and management because of the difference of the geographical and other factors?

Lim: Yes kag ofshoot ina sang ICARE sang city. Kay halos ang kada district may ICARE. Diri lang na nga kada district may pulis, may traffic personnel, may fire personnel, halos tanan kumpleto na...siya didto na sa area...

Torreta: ...how can Iloilo City Government achieve a responsive, inclusive, and sustainable EWS?

Lim: same gihapon, ang districting kuha niya ang tanan...nakita ko nga mas maayo ini because you are managing disaster response in a smaller level. Okay lang na kon munisipyo pero the city has 180 barangays, problema ina kon maghambal kita nga isa lang madecide pirme...ang districting is the answer.

END

Interview with Mr. Karl Danielle Sira, Academic Assessment Head/Safety Officer/ DRRM Coordinator at JBLFMU dated April 29, 2025

Torreta: can you sir share with us, ano na kamo kadugay nangin member kag ano ang advantage or significance of you being a member of the City DRRM Council?

Sira: even before that I had before the safety officer of the school, the school already has a MOA with the city government as the official HEI representative...

Torreta: when was that?

Sira: I rethink 4 years ago so they have a MOA that the school is the official representative. The advantages that we have well we attend the council meeting especially the different current issues, may it be medical may it be hazards on the current climate so we attend the said meetings and we participate on the voting and we give on the suggestions on the side of the HEIs and th private HEIs. On the things that can hamper the university protocols...

Torreta: so it is being more advantageous than just being here...

Sira: just waiting for the news, for the policies and the guidelines they ask us if especially if the university has air conditioning, maybe they can go on with their classes but if the university is not really ventilated well , then at around 43 degrees they should suspend classes for them to keep safe their children. So more partnerships really, because of the council

Torreta: correct,so parang in a way it is better...

Sira: than just being a normal HEI in terms of the DRRM

Torreta: of course and it fosters gid ya sir no collaboration even outside and within the network

Sira: for the experience, we usually have visitors from the PTC, sea mariners, those who are NGOs who share the same passion about DRRM we have different seminars and symposiums about DRRM, especially with students. We have environmental activities together with them and the we make connections. They train students and teachers for free in the school. So I think those are the things that we share and have really been helpful in the university

Torreta: sir...ano naman ang role ni JBLFMU in the communication process, are you involved in a way or somehow in the development of it or as of this time, it is more on you receiving information from them?

Sira: in the first place all of the information for the evacuation or early warning comes up with the DRRM but we are the home of the one of the sensors of the CDRRMO so we home their early warning divide in the school, and we are also an official evacuation center in Arevalo so we have this new program with CDRRMO wherein we make this cluster of disaster council per district so we are really a indulge in that one because of the connection that we have with maam Charry and maam Gavan so literally if they ask us or become PIOs or again we become the official evacuation center then we should become ready since we have the MOA

Torreta: ang early warning device nga ini nga na-install, device for what?

Sira: for earthquake and rain gauge, it is a rain gauge

Torreta: kasan-o ini sir gin-install?

Sira: 2018 I think

Torreta: I am quite interested because again you are the one housing the device sir no, for example sino ang nga-man sina, kamo?

Sira: it is connected sir via satellite so no need for configuration or anything but we check it because sometimes it gives unusual signal I think sir Benk from the city operations center, they tell us to check it because the sensors are very sensitive as well

Torreta: in that aside from the actual monitoring, you are also tasked or requested to give information for validation for checking based on that device, so you provide information as well to them through that? In a way

Sira: ah in a way but the monitoring system is, we keep it on the server on the 5th floor so we are not required to give them the information sa CDRRMO but we just need to maintain the area. Actually this month we will have a maintenance by the suppliers

Torreata: but the data that came from the device, automatic na ini siya?

Sira: yes automatic they would go on the Operations Center of the city

Torreata: but they are requesting you to check if indeed that was the data?

Sira: yes or if pag nadula ang signal, they would ask us to check if the antenna is andiyan pa or wala. I think dugay na siya eh pila na ka years.

Torreata: so in terms of the communication process from the city kon magpaguwa sila sang information, you are also receiving this information kasi early warning. Sa diin niyo ini siya ma-access? Paano ninyo ina mareceive?

Sira: I think on Viber but I am not yet connected right now we have this council of different HEIs same on the different councils because may council man sa anti-smoking...on that Viber they usually send the memos and if it has conditional things that you need to process with the administrators then it is up to them to decide but most likely on the memos coming from the CDRRMO through Viber and I think social media they also have social media posting but mayor already has standard protocol on the temperature so most likely the DepEd is most likely affected, and the tertiary is depending on the president...

Torreata: you have mentioned sir no nga medyo damo ka role that is related to the DRRM or on this matter, sa early waring system. Sa inyo office sir, pila kamo na, ikaw lang ba isa or may mga upod ka?

Sira: officially on paper with the contract with the HR I am only the one but I have this protocol in my mind that if because if there is only one person and you would go outside of the country, what else, if you are not around then you will have a problem so the protocol that I have whenever I have a training I always bring one so that that other person, actually sa staff as well same with me as the department head, there is an alternate so for example they will send me in Camiguin they should be someone who is left so even though I am not there, if there is a fire there should still be the leader who will do everything. So we also apply that with the students that we have...

Torreata: so involve man ang mga students during training?

Sira: yes, one of the most unique that we do is that I involve my students because with the population that we have the ratio for example you have an emergency brigade which is 30 then students of 2000 in the real manner, you can't really

Torreata: have that control over them

Sira: yes sir

Torreata: on an estimate, around 2000 ang population of John B?

Sira: yes sir on the Arevalo Campus

Torreata: sir, you have mentioned this, how did you make your students involved on this?

Sira: okay so we created an organization, we call this organization JBLFMU Disaster Risk Reduction Unit I think it is one of the best practices that we have...

Torreata: student organization ini siya?

Sira: yes sir, student organization. It is what we call an institutionalized organization since it is adapted by the school

Torreta: adapted from?

Sira: the proposal was the one that i had sir

Torreta: when was this isr that you had the proposal?

Sira: when I started to become a safety officer 2 years ago so it was a hard start since there was no budget like they won't see the essence then I told them stories that if we ever have an actual fire an actual incident, do you think we have emergency brigade to handle this 2000? So with the help of CDRRMO, I told them about the sustainability that if we have this organization then we will not have a problem..and there are certain organizations that appreciates on this kinds of activities on DRRM

Torreta: pero ang organization nga ini, may pila ni sila kabilog and you serve as the adviser, right?

Sira: currently I have 120. Those are certified with fire safety training and basic first aid training because most of the students take the basic safety training because maritime they know how to make CPR...

Torreta: ...on that aspect , in terms of the communication process, how do you keep them involved or how do they participate in the communication process for example may memo na sa city then it was shared to us via Viber, then what happens next?

Sira: the next one for example there is the when there is a threat on high temperature was given, we had a huddle in the school together with the, because we have the board those who are the higher officers and the juniors are also there so I would ask them on the concerns, so we ask them their concerns from the senior high , and then if they have any problem that for example they become thirsty always or the temperature is always high so we make a letter to the administrator and we ask our administrator, these are the current things that happen. So for example they saw a student washing his hair because it was very hot in the building and some of them have problems with the almost going to heat stroke so we need to make mitigation then the administrator will call us then we will call the whole department and then we will discuss with this concerns, then a memo will be passed so currently we do not dress in uniform, we have water around the school and the DRRMU gives a free water as our mandate...

Torreta: sir you mentioned senior high students so indi lang ini college students?

Sira: we have difference program withs senior high since senior high school has various DRRM programs

Torreta: and may DRRM coordinator

Sira: for senior high they have a different coordinator but I make the program annually for the senior high. We did a different approach with senior high because usually last year they are on table tap, more on power point, so I did a different approach. I involved different agencies coming from OCD, PHIVOLCS went there, MGB as well, CDRRMO, BFP, and we have a swell the...

Sira: yes we have a symposium every week, every Wednesday. So they could learn different things on the disaster...

Torreta: may ar aba ang organization sang your own communication platform like social media account...in your group you also disseminate it to others?

Sira: yes actually we have a Facebook page, we share usually for example the NSED, the things that will do in case of earthquake, fire

Torreta: ang advisories from the city, gina-share niyo man dira?

Sira: yes, sometimes we share it there sometimes what we do if the publication is the first to post it, we will reshare it

Toreta: the publication of the university?

Sira: we kind of do that kung sin ang mauuna, sometimes we do it ourselves din sir

Torreta: how about the other communication platforms, for example do you still post sa mga bulletin boards, or ginagamitan niyo ba public address system, rikorida?

Sira: yes we have public address but usually, to avoid immediate panic, may ano kami protocol that we just use the public address in the drill lang and actual pero kun example usual indi naman siya ginagamit, emergency lang siya

Torreta: but have you used your public address na?

Sira: yes sir, during drills and actual gid sir

Torreta: what was that actual experience?

Sira: that was long time ago, yung sunod-sunod na earthquake, we have an actual earthquake na nung pumasok na balik yung students, nag earthquake ulit

Torreta: sir sa early warning system, how familiar are you on it?

Sira: for the early warnings with the talk with the PHIVOLCS actually may plan for this year we will create an EOC pero subong lang ako nakatraining sang EOC kay after training sang BICS amo ang EOC. So the budget outlay for this year will go to the EOC namon sir then we have an office where we put the example the Windy, the PHIVOLCS na required na platforms...but aside from that before we have an annual forum about disaster risk where we discuss the hazard mapping of Arevalo district, dira kami so we talk about, in case of earthquake what is the most probable disaster that will happen

Torreta: annual ini sir, sino ang naga-attend?

Sira: our students especially the officers of the school since limited man kaina but if we have the chance, ang sa kay MGB wala man gid naga-change but we keep reminding them about the hazards nga indi na mahakas

Torreta: so that is how you communicate these hazards to the students, through that forum?

Sira: yes sir..because sir ang nagahambal dira sir aside from me, because I do not want to like do it myself, so students man ang involve so one of the greatest achievement nga naubra sang DRRU sang John B is that we were the only institution that represented the Philippines in the Yokohama I think 2 years ago, sa city net online malang siya sir...

Torreta: ano ang ginpresent ni John B sir?

Mira: the project AMLIG so we created a portion of the libraries about disaster risks so we have different schools like the RANS, Sto Nino, so we created small spaces there we put some information, secondary and elementary schools ini siya, and this was initiated by my students...I plan it out for them that we presented it in the citynet Yokohama for students

Torreta: part of the activities of the students?

Sira: yes sir

Torreta: sir may ara si city nga KABALAKA tour and KABALAKA art gallery as well, may ara , naimlement ini sa inyo so far?

Sira: we are part of the KABALA tour sir, I can't accommodate the art nga kwan ni mama because it is really big but everytime they have a KABALAKA tour, they really stop sa John B sir, bali usually kami ang 2nd to the last so everytime may KABALAK tour, part gid kami

Torreta: so ano ang inyo part sa KABALAKA tour sir, as an evac area?

Sira: a s an evac area but what they do they usually stay sa DRRU corner

Torreta: ano ini ang DRRU Corner sir?

Sira: DRRU Corner is part of the library wherein...

Torreta: similar with what you did in the schools

Sira: yes sir,

Torreta: but the information there is from

Sira: different man from CDRRMO, MGB, we have also innovative activities like for example games like ASSIST wherein...

Torreta: is that from the CDRRMO?

Sira: bali upod man kami sa CDRRMO they have their ASSIST man nga board game, we have as well sa amon, so what we do is that they went of the school may dala man sila extra boards, ang pinakadako nga crowd siguro namon mga 20 to 30 then we me and my students make the activity for almost an hour then by playing games sa disaster risk, maka-learn sila. So it is a unique game nga everytime ara sila, amo na amon gina obra.

Torreta: what do you call that game sir?

Sira: MOD board, Master of Disaster game

Torreta: sin-o ni ang common participants?

Sira: anyone sir from all ages siguro starting from Grade 3 until high school nga nagavisit sa school. Ang naghatag sini sir is ASSIST

Torreta: ano ang ASSIST, NGO?

Sira: huo NGO siya sir. Sang una may ara pa sa National Book Store subong daw wala na that is one of the instruments

Torreta: but you have developed your own game similar to that?

Sira: indi sir, we adapt them kay ang first part sang tour is that we give the profile kon ano ang DRRU

Torreta: amo na ag tour ang gina-feature ang organization?

Sira: yes sir then kon ano nag mga activity together with the CDRRMO. We inspire the students na in your school it is nice to know these things, activities nga hambal nila wala ta gina-limit si youth bala nga like maybe in a disaster kon ipwede nga inid ikaw ang victim, you are the one who could help the community.

Torreta: through that game, you are alsì giving information about the hazards

Sira: yes sir, for example ar aka sa baha the game itself ask you what to do or kon ano man ang imo ubrahon both hardwork and soft skills

Torreta:...so far ano ang mga common early warning messages nga gina-communicate ni city sa inyo? You mentioned earlier heat index

Sira: during summer, heat index tapos kun may typhoon warning usually they have that one ah indi taman mahambal nga si CDRRMO ang nagahambal sang pagmay rally, si mayor naman na, pero we share since wala man siya hazard but part na siya sa management

Torreta: the school is in the coastal community sir no, so what are the early warnings sa inyo? Storm surge, tsunami, have you received such information?

Sira: usually may ara man ginapasa sa amo na usually they ask us to stay tune sa mga advisories so kon rainfall advisory and tsunami advisory so far wala mans ang actual nga natabo

Torreta: was there an instance nga may advisory about tsunami or storm surge?

Sira: ang instance nga nabal-an ko nga nag-worry ako is ang earthquake nga lapit sa Negros indi man siya tama ka taas ang level pero of course, especially kun baha naman sir. When we have baha and orange rainfall, usually early off students and employees. We ask students and employees nga ang tanan nga mga gamit sa idalum sang lamesa, since wala man brown out ipababawon para madula siya sa hazard

Torreta: kay sa coastal kamo, may mga advisories kamo nga nabaton or nacomunicate before regarding storm surge?

Sira: huo sir ay ara man when we had a meeting with CDRRMO ang ginahambal ya gid na nga very prone ang barangay gid na namon, Calumpang, Sto Nino Sur and Norte

Torreta: so so far heat index, typhoon, flooding earthquake, and storm surge may mga advisories man regarding protest but this is more on the management. Te may human induced hazard man eh

Sira: yes sir

Torreta: sir sa pagcommunicate sang risk, sa riks knowledge ang mga assessment ao to kaina ang sa forum, seminar, kon paan gina-share bala sa constituents from the city government, ano pa gid?

Sira: si hazard mapping kay kwan naton ginakuha sir kay MGB, tapos ang hazard sa actual barangay kay city gid ya sir

Torreta: sa observation and forecasting sir, ano ang mga mechanisms ninyo like for example si city kay ara sila monitoring, do you also have your own monitoring system?

Sira: amo na ina siya sir ang amon so far subong ang amon social media namon may ara sa amon pero this year and project is ang EOC sir

Torreta: kay coastal kamo sir no, when there is a hazard because of that do you also coordinate or inform city governemt about the situation?

Sira: there is a chance

Torreta: paano?

Sira: we could call them, and then ang amon nga barangay upod mana sir mo, we could call them kon ang hazard dira

Torreta: was there an instance before nga nakacoordinate kamo sa CDRRMO about a particular hazard in your area?

Sira: so far nag ginakahadlukan ko manlang oil spill...kun dako medyo ayawan kami

Torreta: you have mentioned call, sa Viber

Sira: kag may ara man assigned nga coordinator per district

Torreta: sa response capability sir for example mahambal si city nga dira sa mga coastal barangay, evacuate na kamo..how do you communicate that to your constituents and the affected population?

Sira: usually limited man ang ginahatag namon nga area for them but as part of the commitment of the school, for example sa typhoon to te wala man sang klase sir, we take all bisan gab-i usually ang amon man ya nga mga employees sila mana ng mabailin sila nagatake sang evacuaees

Torreta: paano ninyo ina ginacomunicate sa ila?

Sira: sa CDRRMO?

Torreta: sa inyo personnel

Sira: we have this huddle kon like for example the CDRRMO would call the administrator, they would call us then we are going to be the official evacuation center, matunga na nag work for example si Arevalo Disitric nga mga barangay siya ang sa logistics, siya man sa mga pumuluyo. Si JOhn B naman ya sir ang iya role ang accommodation, kon diin sila ipamutang ang storage facility nila,...kami ang aon they have the counting kon pila ka bilog nga families, naga-assist kami sa ila kun may mga bata

Torreta: sir sa strategies nga ginoobra ni city sa pagcommunicate sa inyo sang early warning, so, they have sa social media, sa Viber, Facebook, emails?

Sira: may ara ma sir email pero kon emergency call gid

Torreta: text messaging?

Sira: talagsa, call gid ang laban

Torreta: nagligad may UnRISK nga program and a syou have mentioned per district nga DRRM, so this is their strategy to localize the early warning, its communication. Para sa imo, as one of the partner in the academe, ano ang imo impression on the project?

Sira: for me it is a long shot kay pagka indi tanan tanan nga involve is not really passionate about that one, I think it will not pull off but since I experience man nga sang una mabudlay but you keep on training them, if we already have the actual committees, and then the capacity building sa mga distrito I think it will really be for us to move as a team, para sa district kon may ara gid mana actual for example kon assigned si barangay on a role kag si JOhn B may ara man, I think it will be effective but for the start up to ni maam, it is a long way to go. Hambal ya gani ang EOC ilocalize man. Pero nagapati gid ko na kay maam Donna kay naexperience ko gid na nga sang una nga daw wala pa mga ICARE kay anything naubra man nila

Torreta: but what is the beauty or advantage of having that?

Sira: for the localization I think ang the best thing that we could do with that is faster response time, and then more there will be more community nga ma-tap since if we put it in a localize nga setting indi lang tanan nga tawo daw wala sila labot because in a localized setting they will be responsible in their areas and then of course smart cities and safety communities will be there

Torreta: what happened last time kay ginpa-identify per district kon ano nag hazards in that particular area as well, what is your impression on that?

Sira:well kun very ang mga nagparticipate is really kabalo sang area te kumbaga actual mahambal nga risks then okay siya pero kun dapat may ara kita snag long term nga risks nga makita, if you see studies ike ang ginalantaw namon nagligad nag liquefaction, lapit sa amon ag basurahan, may air quality kami nga problema. Tani ang makita advantage siya but for me there could be more nga pwede naton makita nga long shot nga mga risks kay sang una ang byabya namon sa Arealo is that malapad kay dira man ako nag eskwela

Torreta: layo pa

Sira: huo , layo pa subong ya, sa unahan nalang siya tapos kon mag low tide naman lapad-lapad meaning kumbaga indi ko pa makit ang pure risks...

Torreta: that supports the sealevel rising, that is one area that we should also look into sa language used ni city government sa pagcommunicate sang early warnings, ano ni siya ang common?

Sira: I think sa early warnings sa teaching sang city government on the family-based DRRM, kay kaagi ko na siya tudlo sang family-based DRRM sa Sto Nino, the materials we used is really in Ilonggo

Torreta: in Hiligaynon

Sira: huo so mas malapit mo siya maintindihan, mapaintindi sa pamilya why it is important to talk with each other about what to do during emergency kay ang mga balay didto sa amon especially sa Calumpang medyo dikit-dikit. We brought he family sang Sto Nino Sur sa eskwelahan and I talked about family based DRRM ang nami didto kay ang material is Ilonggo na

Torreta: from city

Sira: from city sir, ginshare man ni maam Sharry sa akon. I was thinking nga kon gin-English mo ini siya wala man sang may mamati sa imo kay they do not know kon ano ini siya

Torreta: sir aside from that they also have their posters, linog, baha, in Hiligaynon as well, may ara kamo copy?

Sira: may ginshare sa akon si CDRRMo we posted it sa schools

Torreta: in Hiligaynon gid man

Sira: may ara nga in Hiligaynon pero may ara man in English pero ang amon nga ginabutang usually in English sir maybe sa ISO standard sang school nga requirements pero sa kabaranggayan in Ilonggo gid ya like ao ang ubrahon kon may linog, sunog galing usally ang makita naotn pirme sa basketball court

Torreta: pero sa school iya ang napost usually in English

Sira: huo English sir, kalabanan parti ang what to do

Torreta: pero may ara man in Hiligaynon?

Sira: na posters, malaka guro sir, didto lang siguro sa opisina namon na post nga amo na sir

Torreta: there are students nga indi halin sa Western Visayas, kun ikaw ang papillon in terms of the medium of language sa pagcommunicate, ano ang preference mo? As observed in the filed as well
Sira: kon sa field it is much better nga kabalo ka sa dialect nila sir because if you want an effective na movement in DRR like for example ang expeirndce sa Kanlaon didto, kon paano magpaguwa sulod sang tawo, ang iban kun medyo gin Tagalog mo medyo laina ang ano. Kon actual nga rescue use the dialect na local

Torreta: sa inyo ya sa ginapaguwa ninyo nga information from the city government to your stakeholders, mag ubra kamo sang communiciation or information, ano ang ginagamit ninyo nga language?

Sira: English gid sir ang kalabanan namon nga meos is Enlgish gid sir

Torreta: kun magpaguwa kamo information sa social media for example or kon magshare kamo sang ila, ano ini siya general population or may specific nga stakeholders sa university? May specific audience kamo?

Sira: usually ang audience namon ang ginapriority ni school ang students sa kabarnaggayan naman ya all I know sila maam namon sa DRRM sila ang nagahambal sa kwan tapos ang nami sa may sto nino is that kis-a kun bal-an na nila nga taas nag typhoon signal, sila ang ginasugat namon, sir maevacuate na kamo kay basi maanod ang balay niyo. Maayo man nga nagasunod sila may ara kami experience nga naanod gid ya ang balay , wala na ang balay niya after. Ang dira lapit sa linyada sang Tatoys bala

Torreta: how do you communicate sa mga member sang vulnerable sector inside the university like the youth, senior citizens and PWDs? May specific or general approach?

Sira: usually general siya nga approach tapos after sang memo usually si DRRU ang last nga nagaguwa sa school, naka PPE na ina kami sir tapos we check the classrooms

Torreta: ang iban nga stakeholders PWDs, may mga special instructions like flags or bells for them

Sira: sa students wala kami sang PWDs pero sa workers damo kami sir nga mga PWDs we usually have a place them lapit sa exit, according sa DOLE ang amon PWDs na employees dapat lapit sila sa exit so pati ang akon nga teachers nga kwan, wala sang teachers nga PWD nga ara sa 2nd floor or 3rd floor, ara sila sa idalum. What we do is we assign sa mga safety officers, bali ang safety team nga nagapang evacuate for example nagabaha,

Torreta: so sila ni ang in-charge to ensure nga naka-evacuate?

Sira: yes sir

Torreta: okay team 1, first floor ang inyo icheck dira si maam A?

Sira: ang search and rescue team until 4, ginadivide namon ang area tapos sila nag nagalibot. Usually ginalibot nila patay ang mga electric fans

Torreta: before the team would arrive, is there a dedicated personnel assigned or tasked or requested for PWDs na teacher?

Sira: kun for example alas tres, uwian na. Amo na paglibot kag pag-assist sa amon PWDs gid

Torreta: sir kon magpadala sang information si city, through DRRM abi ni, ginaprocess niyo pa in your level before niyo siya irelease or kun ano ang ginarelease nila amo man in anag ginarelease ninyo as it is lang?

Sira: kon mabaton namon ang memo, we pass it sa amon nga administrator and then the administrator will be talking on the senior ang mga dept heads, principal, deans and they will talk about the protocols. Usually ang una gid man kwan si senior high, ang college bilin pero kun for example super init gid, grabe nag ulan, gabaha, usually gina shorten namon ang klase

Torreta: pero ang content sini?

Sira: ang content is from the admin ang amon lang iya from administrator ang nagapacheck sa amon like sang una ginapacheck sa akon kag sa upod ko ang status sang dagat, ang status sang hangin, very important for us. Bali assessment lang kami sir, si administrator makuha siya inputs sa amon may ara kami sir monitoring sang ulan and typhoon mabase kami na dir anga sa amo na nga oras makusog ina ang ulan and may orange rain fall so si administrator mabase ina siya sa amon nga ihatag sa iya nga data then madeice siya kon ano oras matapos ang klase

Torreta: Okay so you provide information and assessment for his decision making. Sir ang mga scientific and technical information related to early warning for example the ridge of the tail-end of the cold-front, easterlies,...ang information nga makuha from cdrmo do you think scientific and technical gihapon like that or may strategie ssila nga ginaobra para mas maging simple kag maintindihan?

Sira: si CDRMO may ara isla code for rain gina adapt man ina namon for example sa ini nga adlaw kon grabe ang ulan, gina-adapt namon sir, kay ginalocalize nila sir, ang mga cold front and mga typhoon kon sa amon okay lang kay may meteo kami sir

Torreta: may in house kamo nga meteorologist?

Sira: indi sir, may subject kami sir nga meteorology so medyo naintidihan namon pero for me sa community, isa man ina sa mga struggle for example hambalan mo nga ag pumuluyo nga signal number 2 na ilikas na ang mgagamit anay, indi na sila kaintindi sir

Torreta: sa imo assessment sir, scientific and technical information gihapon bala nag pagcommunicate ni city or may intervention man sila or strategy sila nga ginaobra to simplify?

Sira: may strategy sila sir nga ginaobra nga daw gina hambal siya nga code, may code nga ginagamit especially sa typhoon kag rain level may code na sila nga ginagamit dsi CDRMO kag ginatudlo na nila sa local nga DDRM sa barangay. For example ginahambal nila sa responder, amo na ini siya nag sitwasyon, may ara nana nga automatic nga ubrahon nila pero kon sa community medyo dira ang struggle

Torreta: for you sir, ginaconsider ba ni city governme tkamo as an academic institution sa pagdevelop kag communicate sang early warning system? Feeling mo kabahin kamo sa ila pagdevelop kag implement sang early warning system?

Sira: if they have any project or innovation they are ginalantaw nila kon pwede nila ibutang sa akon kag kon asset kami kay like every year, ginakuha nila kon ano nag available nga resource,s pila ang ready namon nga personnel, ano ang assets akg trainings nga pwede namon mahatag sa ila. I think ginalantaw na nila sir kun ang ini nga area or institution could be a partner

Torreta: by that, ginaconsider gid kag part gid kamo sa process sang developing and implementing the early warning system?

Sira: yes sirm ang is anga indi ko malipatan nga gin ubra sa amon kay they let us develop they whole contingency plan sang amon nga school nga gingamit nila sa seal of good governance and gawad kalasag kay dapat bal-an namon kon diin ibutang ang mga evacuees, kag diin ibutang ag mga evacuees so nappreciate ko man nga gina-upod gid kami nila

Torreta: how vitan nga dapat kabahin kamo as a stakeholder sang development and implementation of early warning system?

Sira: it is important because as a stakeholder in the SDG nga safe cities and smart cities, bal-an ni CDRMO kun ano ang needs para may effective nga evacuation contingency kon school man or communities dapat involve ang mga pumuluyo sa pagplano amo ina nga upod gid si barangay because there are some concerns nga indi nila mabatina kon higher ups lang...for example sa logistics or sa early warning indi sila kabaton prime, we could look further bala

Torreta: re recommendation sir, for you what are the areas nga pwede pa maimprive ni city sa pagcommunicate sang ila early warning?

Sira: if you know the lungsod nga application wherein it was expected nga gamiton ni city. This application should tell kon ana ang gakatabo sa syudad. I was expecting nga mamaterialize siya because of mamaterialize siya for example we have a road accident or a heavy rainfall, personalize siya nga application, makita mo siya

Torreta: developed by?

Sira: si city man wala lang siya I think natapos example may traffic ay may bngguanaya sa Molo if you have that information, amo na siya modern, amo na ang part snag modernization nga makita naton nga SMART city si Iloilo

Torreta: parang real time updating and monitoring

Sira: at these days, ang population daw kagamay nga bagay gaka stress sila kag mahambal mo nga SMART city ka kun you have that

Torreta: in that application, the audience can see

Sira: yes, for example may accident sa ini nga street or gabaha so non passable siya...

Torreta: when was that sir?

Sira: I think 2 years ago, nag register man ako kay naghambal si maam pero isa ni siya sa ginalantaw ni sir Papa nga dala sa early warning. Bisan like si students nga nakaregister makita mo

Torreta: aside from that, ano pa gid?

Sira: kon sa early warning system, wala ko pa nakita sblack-out system...for example very dependable kita kay cellphone, may ara man sila radyo pero kon may strategic ka nga mga areas like si barangay, si school...

Torreta: wala kamo radyo nga ginhatag nila?

Sira: wala kami sir nga ginhatag nila pero maya ra sa school daw parehas sa barko...ang akon lang what if black out system nga ang Iloilo

Torreta: how can Iloilo City Government achieve a responsive, inclusive, and sustainable early warning system?

Sira: so kun maghambal kit anga sustainable siya, mayb continuity maybe we could really invest in Science and Technology, one of the things that we really could look into tapos ginhambal man gani nila, if we have the Artificial Intelligence pero dapat controlled for example to give you recommendations only and disaster nga daan indi mo mapaktan so one thing nga lantaown naton kun naga-evolve ang mga hazards sa syudad dapat makita ta na ina siya. So for example kon makita naton nga daw naganaba na ang part nga diri, mas sustainable ang pagprepare snag syudad kon ano ang mga hazards

Torreta: so may aide with technology

Sira: ang technology dira gid masulod ang sustainability

Torreta: ang tong in terms of responsiveness and inclusivity? Ang DRRM council do you think this is one way of making it inclusive kay te everybody like per district, more membership, pwede ayhan?

Sira: pwede siya pero dapat equipped for example we do not have the capacity sa district nga ina ang ang tawo indi well trained , syempre medyo downfall pero kon well equipped tapos gina-actualize ang ubra. Kay kabudlay may ara kamo ao na kag wala man, daw display na lang

END

Interview with Mr Joel Franco of RMN Iloilo dated April 22, 2025

Torreta: sir sa imo as a media practitioner, ano ang papel ni Iloilo City Hall Press Corps sa pag-communicate ni City Government sang ila early warning system?

Franco: Oftentimes, always gid na nga gina-channel nila sa amon ang ila nga communication pakadto sa amon mga networks tapos ginahaboy man ina namon sa amon nga mga networks ang information nga ginahatag nila sa amon galing kay te bal-an mo naman subong iya with the advent sang social media sometimes una nila post sa ila nga page kag ipasa sa amon for wider dissemination. Pero may partnership kami ina ya sa PIO maya ra kami sang seminar parte sa DRRM, laymanizing sang mga terms par amangin mahapos sa amon kag currently may ara kami sang partnership tawag nila na KABALAKA TV, idiscuss na dira ang preparedness, awareness, kami ang mahost sina tapos sila ang maprovide sang resource person para ang warning preparedness mas masangkad ang malab-utan.

Torrera: sang nagligad nag UnRISK man kamo sir no

Franco: yes

Torreta: sa city hall press corps sir, ano kamo kadamo sa subong?

Franco: currently ang active diri mga 17 kami

Torreta: from legacy, traditional media lang ini or may online man?

Franco: may online platforms man kita, may cable TV, may tringers nga gahaboy balita sa Manila

Torreta: mga roughly, pila ang halin sa traditional media?

Franco: te ara gid na ya ang four big networks, RMN, Bombo, Aksyon, and DYSI, dugang dira ang Radyo Pilipinas sa government. May ara kita sang FM, K5, may ara kita GMA nga tv, IBC, Daily Guardian kag Panay News. Amo na ang mainstream nga common nga naga-cover diri

Torreta: how familiar are you sir with the various elements of early warning system?

Franco: elements meaning?

Torreta: mga information dissemination, risk knowledge?

Franco: actually amo na ang isa sa mahambal ko nga medyo may kulang sa mga katapo sang media siguro indi lang man ako pero amo gid ina ang isa sa mga pinakakulang which we strive sa amon sa press corps amo na nga nagaayo gid gaayo kami sa PIO nga magconduct sang trainings, seminars para nga ma-enhance man ang amon nga ideas pero te bisan papaano we can communicate kon ano man ang gusto namon ipalab-ot nga information sa city hall sa public. As a matter of fact may ara na sila before nga a day before i-announce ang heat index, isa gid ina sa mga ginatutukan namon kay syempre ginahulat ina sang tawo mo. So dasig ang amon nga bulig sa ila sa information dissemination

Torreta: sa mga challenges sir, pwede ta lang ma-expound pa gid?

Franco: ag mga challenges, sometimes ma interchange ang mga term disaster, calamity. Indi ta kaisa ma distinguish ang disaster, indi ta madistinguish ang calamity. Mga limitations nga naandan naton sang una pa bala sa initial reporting naton nga daw ginapareho lang naton ang disaster kag calamity.

Te amo na ang gusto namon matun-an, as a matter of fact nagaplan kami nga mag-work with CDRRMO nga maubra kami sang glossary of terms sang disaster kag calamity, disaster preparedness and calamity para sa disaster reporting para nga amo man ang magamit namon eh kag mangin bible namon sa pagubra sang balita. Indi mo manmalikaan ang interchanging of words kag sa publiko daw naandan naman nila ina pero we need to change ang percetpce para effective delivery man sang information

Torreta: sir sa may risk knowledge...ang mga hazards, mga kalalat-an, on that aspect, paano si city government nagapartner sa inyo sa pagcommunicate sina ngva mga hazards for example?

Franco: actually ako personally oftentimes pila na ko kajo in sa KABALAKA Zoom webinar and training snila kag ginahsar eko lang ang role snag media . Gusto ko ipaintindi ang role sa publiko nga media is not enemy ang media is partner sa information dissemination. So indi sila magkahadlok magpadala sang information because we are here to help them, indi nila pagkabigon nga kontra nila so daw naga-evolve man.. Subong open naman in terms of information dissemination maghaboy sila sang information daw ka hapos na lang man.

Torreta: for example sa mga hzards nga gianatubabg sa city for example sa subong heat index, storm surge, liquefaction, Paano nila kamo gina-involce kon i-communicate nila ina sa public? Let us say gapadala lang sila sang information sa iny about it tapos ginashare niyo man sa public?

Franco: before sina may ara kami ginconduct nga daw training with CDRRMO, ginistoryahan namon ang mga protocol sa declaration sang suspension sang face to face classes, option nga kon madeclare ang eskwelahan ukon indi. Ginistoryahan namon iwith CDRRMO with Mr Darwin Papa, then nag-follow na ina dayon ang EO ni mayor kon paano ina i-execute. So since may prior na kami nga training dira so ang communication na lang is constant feeding of data kay te nabal-an naman namon kon ano ang himuon. KOn amo ni ka celsius nag heat index ano ang himuon so easy na lang ang pagcommunicate namon kay prior dira nakatraining kami, naka seminar kami. So ang pag-cascade sang informatio sige-sige na. Nahatag na sa amon ang information

Torreta: ...nakamention si maam Lucy and maam Donna nga nag-UnRISK man sa media last year with maam Jessica Dator-Bercilla, how was the experience sir?

Franco: actually ako nakita ko dapat pa ako gali dapat matun-an, sa disaster risk reporting. Kadugay na sa akon sa media pero I need to learn a lot pa. Agud nga mangin effective ang reporting kag delivery sang information sa publiko kay bal-an man naton ang public iya medyo “may pagka hard-headed ang tawo” indi dali dali magpati unless they will experience firsthand, maano sila pero bisan na experience na nila madali naman sila malipat. Amo na nga kinahanglan gid ang effective communicator in terms sa pagdeliver sang preparedness and response sang isa ka LGU

Torreta: similar sa gin-ubra sa amon, they discussed first the concept, ang local equivalency...ano an nanamian mo sa training sir sa konteksto sang disaster risk communication?

Franco: ang pagpaintindi sa matuod-tuod nga kahulugan sang tagsa-tagsa nga term nga ginagamit, kon ano ang kahayag. Confused pa kami mo , indi lang ako, all of us were confused kon diin ang kahayag, kon diin ang mga amo na bala.Siling ko amo gali ini dapat. Oftentimes we fail to delivery sang information kay kita mismo sometimes may confusion pa sa ginagamit nga term. Which is good na subong kay ginabuligan na kita sang LGU nga mas makagamit kita sang precise nga term sa pagdeliver sa publiko

Torreta: as experiencde and observed, very scientific and technical from government agencies...ano ang importance of localizing it or in its sense pagsimplify or pagpakahulugan sa lokal naton nga lengwahe?

Franco: mas madali maintidihan sang publiko plus updan mo ina sang concrete example mahambala ka abi nga storm surge, ano gid ina nag storm surge. Mahambal ka abi nga kon may storm surge, ano kadako ang halit niya maintidihan sang tawo

Torreta: sa may context

Franco: huo icontextualize mo siya

Torreta: sa risk knowledge sa UnRISK, ginpa identify man sa inyo ang mga hazards ukon katalagman nga nakita ninyo sa city..for you, not only as a reporter but as a resident mismo sa city, how important nga kita mismo naga-idenitfy sang mga hazards or katalagman naton?

Franco: very important kay not only in times of calamity, that is everywhere eh. Kadto ka lang sa downtown dira, damo hazard dira di ba. So ikaw bal-an mo kon ano ang hazards syempre makahimo ka sang self-restraint, makahimo ka sang personal precaution so if everybody nabal-an nila kon ano ang hazards, makabalo sila magprotect sang ila kaugalingon

Torreta: not only with hazards but also with the possible solutions

Franco: huo, syempre makahimo ka sang imo nga , makadevice ka sang imo nga plano on how you make yourself safe sa mga hazards

Torreta: sir sa observation ang forecasting, te daily man ina ang forecasts pro kon may typhoons or eruptions may mga advisories or bulletins, of course we have a direct line sa concerned national government agency...pero with the city government, do they also communicate that with you, paano?

Franco: currently siguro dira sa isa ka aspeto medyo may kulang gamay ang city government of Iloilo because oftentimes ang ginahimo namon kon may gusto sila i-communicate ang ginahimo namon, gina-view lang namon ang page nila sa CDRRMO, dira lang kami nagakuha sang data sa ginahatag nila. We also want to encourage them whatever nga ginapost nila sa social media, pwede man nila ina-masend sa amon ang link para mas easy. Kay indi man sa tanan nga oras malantaw mo ang Facebook. What is good lang kay may ara kami nga GC dira para s aila, so dira naga-agi ang tanan nga communication. May Viber, may GC, ang PIO actually ang naga-share sina sa amon nga mga information

Torreta: so mga typhoon bulletin, weather forecast, dira na naga-agi kag mga hea tindex advisories as well?

Franco: huo dira ina gaagi

Torreta: ano ang mga kind of information nga ginahatag nila sa inyo sir, as posted sa socmed nila, like ano ang language niya sini?

Franco: English actually ang language nila nga ginagamit, nagapost sila sang halimbawa mapost sila sang data then a little analysis sa idalum, so para mabuligan kami dissect. Kay technical, sometimes kon indi gid namon magrasp ang konsepto nagatawag kami sa ila para maexplain nila sa amon

Torreta: especially during typhoon sir no... kon may bagyo may kinalain ba ang forecasting nila nga pag-communicate sa inyo or as is lang sa gihapon mas frequent lang ang information sharing?

Franco: actually mat ara na sila abi nga ano mo, once nga may bagyo activated ang ila nga Emergency Response Center, so kami on our own, nagakadto kami dira sometime nagatambay kami agud nga mag ano dira magmonitor para nga dasig lang ang delivery sang information

Torreta: but do you also feed information sir for example may mga hazard or let's say may information nga nakuha ninyo sa barangay may storm surge didto, do you also feed that sa ila sa CDRRMO or sa PIO?

Franco: kon may ara te gina-feed namon halimbawa may mga instances sang nagligad nga grabe ang hangin, natumba ang nga kahoy kay te indi man sa tanan nga oras makita nila no so kon kay te bal-an dasig magpadala sa mga media outlets so kami mismo nagapadala snag information, natumba nga poste, nabugto nga kuryente mga kahoy. Kami mismo nagabulig kami share sang information sa ila kag sometimes, kon i-ano mo bala imatch mo sa ila data mahambal sila nga tapos na pero kon kaisa maoverlook na so gabulig kami sa pagremind sa ila which is good man kay partnership man kita

Torreta:sir sa pagcommunicate nila sa inyo kag ninyo man sa ila, ano ngamga platforms or channels ang ginagamit?GC, Viber, ano pa gid sir?

Franco: ah Messenger, amo malang na ang pinaka-common abi

Torreta: kamo man sa ila?

Franco: Huo

Torreta: kon kamo naman ya ang magcommunicate na base sa information that you got from them..paano ninyo ina ginacomunicate sa ano nga channel?

Franco: sa platform namon usually sa social media kag sa on-air...pinaka-una gid dira post sa social media then public affairs kag dasig abi ang social media

Torreta: included man dira ang sa response capability for example may advice abi nga need na mag-evacuate so dira man ninyo ina ginacomunicate?

Franco: hu, kag isa man sa amon ginalantaw enough bala ang evacuation center, ano ang mga provisions of the city government of iloilo, kag te ang tawo eh how they would response kon maghambal nga evacuate ang city government isa man ina sa part nga gusto man namon icomunicate nga kon maghambal si city government nga evacuation, evacuate indi nga maghulat panga i-force pa sila mas maayo gani nga voluntary mag-evacuate ka nalang

Torreta: was there a specific situation sir before nga nag-advice sila tapos you disseminated the information? Ano to nga particular incident sir?

Franco: kadamo ang storm surge gid actually kay dira sa Calumpang , baybay area notorious gid dira nga bisan guba na ang panimalay nagabalik man sa gihapon kay dira na gapangabuhi ang hambal gani namon, sila sila man gihapon ang apektado, sila man ang nagabenepisyo...sila man sa gihapon unless irelocate mo sila

Torreta: sir sa strategies, aside sa usual nga reporting naton, I think diri magsulod si KABALAKA TV, san-o to sir ang target ta?

Franco: actually this month of April galing wala lang kay syempre may constraints, hopefully matapos ang political season mapush through namon inakag mapsatr actually may plano na ina, program flow, may schedule na kun sin-o ang tawo...

Torreta: sir namention man ni maam Donna nga naga-agi kamo media tour?

Franco: hu several times na nagtour kami, may tour ina siya kag sort of a little training like nagligad nag tour kami gintudlan kami dira sa Bureau of Fire sang basic paano mag-evacuate paano magdala sang tawo nga injured, gintudluan kami. Nagkadto man kami sa PAGASA, sa radar station, nakita naton nga oriblema gid, kulang...mas maayo pa ang ICARE Center sang city kay kumpleto ang mga gamit

Torreta: ang tour nga ina sit plus with trainings te nakita naton didto sa ICARE asta ang capacity of the city , sa monitoring with their technology, how important it is that experience, sa aton, sa inyo abi as a practitioner for you to communicate as well information related to disaster and disaster reporting?

Franco: te sometimes dapat gid ya you know what you are talking about . Te mahambal ka kon paano himuon tapos wala mo gali na-experience daw indi ka bala, daw wala ka snag authority, daw wala ka sang credibility to say that. Kay because naagyan mo makahambal ka nga, makahaboy ka snag information nga husto kay naagyan mo

Torreta: kag naintindihan mo ang proseso

Franco: correct kay naagyan mo

Torreta: sa medium of language, ano ang medium of language nga ginagamit mo or naotn sa press corps sa pagcommunicate

Franco: Hiligaynon

Torreta: kay primarily Hiligaynon kita, what do you do with terms nga English, scientific, and technical how do you report that as it is lang?

Franco: may mga words nga maintindihan mo siya in English pero kinahanglan mo siya i-contextualize para mas mahangpan sang taow may mga words abi, kita abi ang Hiligaynon abi nga kataga kabudlay, not sa English nga specific. Kaisa ang isa ka word sa English, duwa or tatlo ka words sa Hiligaynon daw kabudlay siya, lain lain pa ang meaning sina. Contextualize lang ang tinaga, kun kinahangan nga English te English pero kon pwede mo siya translate into Hiligaynon nga indi man maguba ang meaning niya, pwede siya matranslate

Torreta:sa pagcommunicate ninyo sir sang Early Warning Messages, may specific target audience bala kamo or general population kita?

Franco: may ara nga general population pero may ara nga specific target nga halimbawa ang sa coastline for storm surge for landslide ang sa bukid, ang for baha, ang sa mga low-lying areas pero we do it generally para nga daw massive ang information dissemination nga malab-ot sa public

Torreta: for vulnerable sectors like senior citizens,youth, children, PWDs, may specific man kita nga way sa pagcommunicate sa ila or macover sila sa general population nga intervention?

Franco: sadly for us sa media wala pa sang specifics for that but we just emphasize nga priority ang vulnerable sector, iprioritize ang sa vulnerable sector maka-inform kita sa ila folks, direkta sa ila folks nga amo ang maga-take care sa ila . Halimbawa ibdi man kita makacommunicate direkta sa mga deaf and mute so we can communicate our information sa ila nga mga folks to prioritize sa mga vulnerable sector...Subong gani indi lang man sa tawo ang aton nga gina-push mo like for us sa RMN pati sa kasapatan. Ang advocacy sang amon mga upod, ang station itself sa mga evacuation indi lang mga tawo dapat ang kasapatan. And ang city sa pagkaremember ko may ginpaguwa ni sila nga resolution nga sa pag-establish sang evacuation center dapat kon may manager sa evacuton center, dapat may provision for pets

Torreta: sir ano ang process ninyo if there is an institution/zie abi nga proseso sa pagcraft ninyo sang message? From city sa inyo, ano ang process ninyo befor eyou disseminate that?

Franco:of course ginakuha namon ina form the government sources na reliable sources para husato ang information, then ubrahon namon ina siya invalidate tapos amo na paghaboy...te subong uso ang pubmats te dira na ginacontextualize halimbawa storm surge syempre butangan mo dira sang mga picture man

Torreta: sir sa city hall press corps, may mga trainings and partnerships kamo with the city government especially woth teh CDRRMO and PIO, do you feel nga part nila kamo sa ila proseso sa pagdevelop sang ila early warning system through this trainigns and KABALAKA tv, and not only about the development of it but also on the communication of it?

Franco:basic ang amon gid nga papel is for partner sa information and dissemination pero ginawork out ang partnership nga sa pagubra sang sina nga mga communication materials, IEC, part na ang press corps kay may mga suggestions man kami nga ginapanghatag sa ila

Torreta: why do you think important nga involve gid ang media int he development and communication of early warning system?

Franco: very important tkay as a media indi lang kita focus sa reporting, we should own, daw may sense of ownership ka bala sa proseso kag ina nga mga product nga ginahaboy sa public, kay te kon wala ka involvement, mere nga pagbasa, mere lang nga paghaboy sang information but kon involve ka dira daw deliver mo by heart ang imo nga trabaho kay mahambal ka nga akon ni , may part ako diri, part sini ginobra ko so you will deliver by heart ang ina nga information, pro kon ginahaboy lang sa imo ginafeed lang sa imo so haboy mo lang man sa ila pero kon ikaw nagtrabaho syempre, butang mo sa pinsar mo nga ginpangabudlayan ko ini so kinahanglan nga ipalab-ot ko

Torreta: may instances ba nga si public, ang audience magashare sa inyo sang information, kag amo man ini nag ginashare ninyo sa city government?

Franco: syempre sa amo na ngamga bagay maka imput man ang mga katapo sang medi,a naga call out man gani kami sa ila kon ano ang pwede madugang which is good kay receptive sila...

Torreta: ano ang areas for improvement in Iloilo City Government's communication of EWS?

Franco: ...further accessibility of information, further accessibility snag mga resource persons, kag amo to ang hambal ko imaterialize na tani ang amon ga glossary of terms, localize for disaster reporting dako gid ina nga bagay nga makabuig sa amon...okay naman ang partnership one call away sa amon dasigay lang nga habuyanay sang information

Torreta: sir how can Iloilo City Government, through the media, achieve a responsive ,inclusive, and sustainable nga early warning system?

Franco: the key to that siguro is critical collaboration. When I say critical collaboration, indi lang sila mamati sang amon manami nga pagdayaw pati ag mga negative to help them improve sa kon ano man ang kakulangan kag bal-an man na nila, we are not enemy but partners sa ini nga aspeto.Critical collaboration, good or bad,accept ina kay part ina nga makabulig nga maka-impoive sa delivery of services.

END

Interview with Buntatala, Jaro PB Starlene Hosenilla and Kagawad Rhea Saban dated April 8, 2025 (Barangay Information Officer)

PB Hosenilla: Siya ang chairman sa Health, ang amon nga barangya information officer, solid waste...

Torreta: Ang tanan nga barangay may information officers?

PB Hosenilla: Hup depende sa kapitan kay te tungod sa mahilig siya sa technology, dasig siya mo

Torreta: ano ang practice naton diri sa barangay upod sa city government sa pag-communicate sang Early Warning System? Ano ang existing nga process ninyo?

PB Hosenilla? Bali ano si City, si OpCen, Operation Center na ga-send sang message sa akon diri tapos ako, ang message na halin nana sa ila. Tapos ako tungod kay may pito nga kagawad, may group

chat kami, i-send ko na sa council nga group chat. Tapos si kagawad in-charge, ang kada zone na bal-an sir, may group chat mana, i-send yaman na didto

Torreta: Okay, paano ginapadala ni City OpCen ang message? Ano ginagamit nila para ipadala ang ina nga mensahe?

PB Hosenilla: may ara group chat, sa liga, liga ng mga barangay gapadala mana sila, ang liga na gasulod mana diri

Torreta" okay so si OpCen nagadirekta sila nga message sa inyo, then games man sila sa liga, tapos si liga amo man nagapadala man sa inyo

PB Hosenilla: Huo, gapadala man sa amon

Torreta: same lang na nga message? Same lang nga information?

PB Hosenilla: huo, same lang na

Torreta: magluwas sa GC, ano pa gid ang mga pamaagi nila, kay te dasig ya ang GC, Messenger. Ano pa gid ang mga pamaagi nila sa inyo previous experience kun magpadala sila sang mensahe, gagamit ma sila text messaging, cellphone, telephone, email, radyo?

PB Hosenilla: text, radyo

Kagawad Saban: once bala nga may ginapa-abot bala nga bagyo or what, ang iya ka liga nga radyo, ginarequire nila kami nga i-open namon

Torreta: si liga ng mga barangay, may specific kamo nga radio frequency?

PB Hosenilla: huo

Kagawad: nga makasulod man ang iya sang OpCen

PB: dala na ina

Torreta: so dira ginapaagi man ang information?

Kagawad: maka-monitor man kami dira sa ila pero una gid nga nakasulod ang through GC

Torreta: te ang radyo ya back-up, pero may ara kamo sang gamit?

PB: huo, may ara,

Torreta: pwede siya magamit if ever? So functional ina siya? Everyday ginagamit or during may ginapaabot lang?

Kagawad: during lang

Torreta: kun may ginapa-abot, back up guwa niya nga channel to communicate.

PB: kaagi mana sir nga kada adlaw ginarequire nga i-open namon gali g may beses gid kaisa nga kagahod gid pamatian. Damo bal-an mo, nagamonitor dira si pulis,BFP, sa liga, ang kada barangay pa gid

Torreta: sin-o ang naga-handle sina nga frequency si city government? City opcen

PB: huo city na, iya na ka liga nga frequency

Torreta: so GC, text, radyo, ano pa gid kap?

PB: kon kaisa sa Facebook, makita mo na sa napost nila sa Facebook

Torreata: so kon magpadala sila sang mensahe sa inyo ang guw aniya kamo ang nagashare sina sa inyo constituents sa barangay so amo to may mekanismo kamo nga from them to you then to kagawad, then kagawad then sa zona. In cases ya be kap nga kamo naman ang may namonitor diri, may suba diri sa Buntatala?

PB: creek

Torreata: so creek, for example sa creek, I do not know if it happened pero for example nagtaas ang level sang tubig sa creek so in a way mafall siya sa monitoring no, so si kapitan or barangay officials kay namonitor ninyo nga nagtaas ang lebel sang tubig, ginapabalo niyo man si city?

PB: yes, huo

Torreata: paano kap?

PB: ma-message kami sa Balantang namon nga focal person sang disaster

Torreata: iya sang city no?

PB: huo iya na tapos ang CSWDO gina-message man ina namon tapos kaisa ang pulis nagapamangkot man ina sa amon, gina-message man ina namon ang pulis. Tapos amo na be ang message halin sa city kundi ginhaboy sa akon, ginhaboy ko sa council, nagapaaman gid ko na dayon sa council nga monitor ta ang aton nga creek kon nagataas ukon wala, monitor ta ang mga tawo ta kay daw halos sir saulo namon diri sa Buntatala kun diin example abi may ulan may bagyo kita nga paabuton ukon nagaulan na abi. Mahaboy na bi si city sa amon, tapos mahaboy ko na sa council, may paaman gid na dayon sa akon nga ulualigmat, monitor ang aton sa masami nga ginabahaan nga pamalay kon nagasaka ang tubi tapos amo na, sila nagahaboy mana sila ara da sa palibot sa mga vulnerable areas na da naton, nagahboy mana sila, nagamonitor mana sila nga mga kagawad

Torreata: so kun may mamonitor kamo...

PB: nagareport sa akon

Torreata: tapos ikaw ginareport mo man sa city, sa cdrrmo?

PB: huo kay nagapamangkot na sila dayon, naga-update na sila

Torreata: paano mo sila ginapahibalo about that? Like sa ano ng channel, sa gc man o sa text?

PB: sa GC man gihapon, sa Messenger, tapos may dala na nga picture sir

Torreata: so ginasend mo lang sa Messenger account city ni cdrrmo?

PB: ni focal person namon

Kagawad: kay may affected families ta abi sa flood, nakaspecific na kon pila ka families ang affected

Torreata: kay focal person niyo ina ginapabalo

PB: huo

Torreata: si focal person tawo siya ni CDRRMO?

PB: huo

Torreata: kada barangay may ara sang focal person

PB: kada district

Torreata: kada district okay, so in a way kap kon maghambal kita sa papel ni barangay sa communication sa early warning, receiver kamo but at the same time, nagapadala man kamo sang information. So active siya ang vice versa ang pagpadala sang information

PB: kag indi lang na sir si CDRRMO ang ginahaboyan namon pati si CSWDO si pulis, kaisa si pulis nagapamangkot man ina, nagamonitor mana, nagalibot sa amon diri sa mga affected areas tapos mamangkot ina sa amon kap. Te ang ano na lang namon para isa na lang, kon ano ang nahimo namon, kon ano ang ginahoboy ni kagawad nga data sa akon kag mga pictures, haboy ko na sa cdrmmo, kay cswdo, sa BFP kag sa pulis

Torreata: syempre kap ini ya nag sistema ninyo diri sa barangay pero sa imo pagkahibalo sa iban pa gid nga mga barangay diri sa city, amo man ini ang ila nga sistema? Kay syempre lain man ya ang kada barangay

PB: ambot sir, lain-lain man abi kon ano ang sa amon, basi indi man applicable sa iban daw amo na bala, te waay man ta kabalo kon ano ang ano ni kap sa ila

Torreata: so far sa subong, daw wala pa sang standardize nga mekanismo nga parehos sini city-liga-barangay-kapitam-kagawad, then kagawad sa zona and amo man sa monitoring, indi pa ini siya standarize tawag nila, wala pa na?

Kagawad: ang city down to barangay level standard na ina sir pero ang sa barangay level nga ginadissemminate sa per zone, amon ina ya strategy, depende na ina sa barangay

PB: practice na ina namon ya sa Buntatala, tapos sir saulo nana nila kon sin-o nga mga families, pila ang apektado nga mga families

Torreata: kap naintindihan ta nga sa barangay damo sang mga concerns nga gina-atubang, sa pagcommunicate kap ni city government sa inyo sang early warnings diri sa barangay, sin-o kag pila ni ka officials ang involved nga amo gid ina nag ila nga trabaho? Ang information halin sa city bala

PB: tanan

Torreata: tanan nga barangay officials so kapitan , then

PB: pito ka kagawad...tapos ang kagawad namon sir may partner na nga BHW amo na ang upod niya nga galibot sila, kag si BHW amo na siya ang kag sa mga recorndings sila na ang naga-obra

Torreata: si ano ya kap, si SK kag ang iya council?

PB: sila ang in-charge sa mga donations, sa mha relief

Torreata: pero may active man sila na role sa communication aspect?

PB: actually sa council ara da siya maghaboy ako dira sang information sa GC namon, mabasahan man ina ni SK. Daw lesser gawa ang iya nga participation compare sa mga kagawad

Kagawad: ...si SK kagawad, ginhatagan man niya sang task nga ikaw partner ka kay kagawad sa amo ni nga committee niya buligan mo siya , te amo na gina-tap namon

PB:kay te burubaskog pa sila ya

Torreata: pero on practice gaupod man sila sa inyo?

Kagawad: te amo lang na eh iban gaeskwela te ginapa-alerto lang...

Torreata: kap sa imo pagbanta, kamo be mo nga mga barangay officials plus the hws kag SK kagawads, enough ba ang inyo nga number para mapun-an ang concern sa pag-communicate sina and kamo, sa

pamatyag mo equipped ba with the knowledge and skills sa pag-communicate sina para maps-intindi sa ila?

PB: kay te ang sa number siguro masarangan namon sa numbers ah kay ang zone 7 ang pinakdako namon sir mo, pero enough nga malibot ni kagawad kag BHW plus may tanod pa kamo nga gina-tap. Kada zona may tanod man nga in-charge ...ang gamay malang namon nga zona amo ni ang Zone 1 along the highway te hapos lang ini ya ang sa ano naman sa skills, may mga training man kami nga ginahatag ang city kag tapos ang iban p agid be nga NGOs para dira kun kaisa gakaalipatan man...may mga trainings kami

Torreta: madumduman mo kon ano ini nga mga trainings?

PB: iya sang red cross, PAPI, CPR and first aide

Torreta: ang specific sa communication

PB: ang CDRRMO lang gid amo na kita lang mga mga barangay officials

Kagawad: kami lang ang nagarelay sa mga BHWs kon ano ang proper way...

Torreta: may ara si city nga training sina?

PB: sa mga barangay officials

Torreta: amo ni ang community-based DRRM?

PB: huo

Torreta: ...kap ano ikaw ka familiar sa various elements sang early warning system?

PB: before nga mag-abot kon ano mana da, kinahanglan mapaguwa kana da sang imo nga communication sa mga tawo te ang amon diri may ari kami diri nga trumpa, ginapaandar na siya namon. Amo na gani sir nagapangayo gid ako sa city nga para daw , indi para nga kinahanglan kami mahambal, mahambal man kami sa microphone para sa trump ag gusto ko ya tani ya, kapila na ko maghambal kay maam Donna ina bala nga padala kamo sa kada barangay kay total istandardize niyo malang, ipadala niyo kon ano ang dapat nga ihambal kay total patukaron malang ina sa amon nga trampa nga gina-ano na be ang tanan gina-aligmat

Torreta: pero kaagi na ninyo gamit ang trump for that?

PB: huo, nang iban sir Tagalog tapos kaisa nag ginapadala sa amon sang CDRRMO ano man daw kalip-ot, daw indi catchy sa pamatin-an

Torreta: pero parte sa ano ini siya, baha, bagyo?

PB: bagyo lang gid, baha wala . tapos ayawan pana kami kaisa...ano ang iya sang city nga early advisory nga ginahambal. Ang gusto ko tani ang daw catchy man para mamati man ang tawo, daw parehas sa Bombo Radyo nga sa tion sang amo ni, kita mag amo ni...may pwera

Kagawad: nami tani bisan parehas sini bala,, makanay-kanay

PB: mga drought ni bala, gusot tani namon may amo na sir

Kagawad: indi kinahanglan nga hulaton pa nga may mag abot nga bagyo ukon baha kag amo magpa-andar

PB: te nagapatukar kami sir mo

Torreta: ano ang coverage sang trump ninyo?

PB: damo sir, lab-ot kami sa relocation site

Torreta: banta ta mga pila na?

PB: mga 20

Torreta: so macover niya ang bilog nga barangay?

PB: indi man kay ang Zone 2 ato na gid sa sulod sa iya kang DA tapos ang zone 4 namon ato sa eskwelahan pero ang zone 1 namon along the highway, zone 3 kag zone 7 makabati gid na ya

Torreta: so roughly pila na ka percent sa barangay?

Kagawad: sa akon mga 70%, sa 70% nga ina sir madisseminate nila sa neighbor nila sa family nila kay amo na mabatian nila bisan gabantay kalang da sang jeep oh

Torreta: luwas pa gid ya sa inyo nga mga barangay officilas nga nagalibot

PB: huo

Torreta: si ang trumpa nga na diin nakaposte diin nakabutang?

PB: ari diri along the highway may trumpa kami, diri abi ayon nga gawad kalinga, sa relocation site, kada poste

Torreta: ang mga terminal, sakayan, may ara man trumpa

PB: wala kami terminal...ang sa tricycle may ara sir sa highway

Torreta: may flood control kamo diri kap nga project...ang sa creek niyo may flood control dira?

PB: subong may project, nag creek dira subong ginahimuan sang revetment wall subong

Kagawad: kay kauna sir nabaw nada ang sapa, amo na sir dasig kami magbaha sa gamay nga ulan pero kaluy-an sang nagligad bisan ano nga kulit sang CDRMO, "wala kami dir gani ginabaha", kay well kown abi ang Buntatala nga ginabaha

PB: flood-prone kami sir mo kami ang catch basin diri from camalig, balantang, tagbak, ang lanit nga tubi diri pa gakatdo sa amon, kami nag catch basin dira te nabaw dira, so nagataas diri sa amon

Torreta: pero wala nana subong?

PB: wala na

Torreta: ang sa creek may ara kamo sang monitoring system dira sa level sang tubig

PB: may ara, may color, color coding may ara kami kaso subong kay ginakay-o

Torreta: pero makita siya subong?

Kagawad: mat ara siya sir, makit-an pa man

Torreta: ginamonitor niyo ina?

PB: huo sir ginaflashlightan namon kon gab-i kon gasaka gid man

Torreta: sin-o nagbutang sina?

PB: syempre sa time pana ni Lovejoy (former PB) kay te kami ang pilot barangay sang una sang CBARAD, lima ka barangay. May ara gani kami sang Gawad KALASAG

Torre: ano ang ginarecognize sa inyo?

Kagawad: ang amon gid ya nga PA system, may ano kai sanguna rainwater harvesting, may flag hoisting nga triangular nga red tapos may black sa sulod...

Torre: te ginagamit pa ninyo na subong?

PB: wala na

Torre: ngaa man?

PB: kay daw gindula na

Kagawad: gindula nana namon sir tungod nga indi na gid man siya, kinahanglan taast-taas gid par amareach out ang iban nga zone, so gin ano na lang nga sa trump

Torre: so instead of flag, trump na lang?

Kagawad: tapos ang amon tarpaulin ginkakas namon kay ginapakay-o dira sa tubang pero may ara kai sang for example alert level 1, alert level 2, color coding ina sir

Torre: best barangay DRRM Committee ...

Kagawad: sang una kami ang gin-example, kami ang model for pero gin-untat kay indi applicable sa iban nga barangays

Torre: pero until now ginagamit ninyo ina ya nag color coding sa pagmonitor?

Kagawad: ang yellow, aligmat. Ang orange, amat-amat na preparar panghimos tapos ang red amo nana siya nga ma-evacuate na sila

Torre: when was the latest nga nagamit ninyo ina?

PB: kada ano ah, sang Krsitine bagyo Kristine...last year. Amo gid na always gid na

Torre: sin-o ang nagmonitor? Kay di ba siling ninyo nagamit sang Kristine, so sin-o ang naglantaw sang leveling? Barangay officials

PB: hu

Torre: so pagkakita ninyo ano gin-ubra ninyo?

Kagawad: haboy dayon kay kap, then sa city

Torre: may ara kamo existing kap, di ba gagamit kamo Public Address System, so sa Public Address System, mayspecific na kamo nga amo ni ang mateial sa yellow, orange? Or paano ni yo na-intagrate or wala pa

Kagawad: wala sir bali tarpaulin lang ina siya ang nakabutang nga instructions

Torre: pero may trumpa man ina dira, sa creek?

PB: malab-ot siya sang PA namon..kag isa sa Buntatala kay tungod may maps ang Buntatala nga napaskil sa dingding sang una. Sa lima ka barangay ang Buntatala lang ang may mapa makita mo ang legend...

Kagawad: kun magkadto diri ang Hapon, amo na ginacheck nila...

Torre: para s aimo kap kag kagawad paano ini nakabulig sa barangay?

PB: dako gid sir ang nabulig sina, ang pumuluyo namon aware nga mag-abot nag amo sina bal-an na nila kon ano ang ila himuon kag ang mga kagawad mismo kag BHW bal-an na nila ang ia nga himuon kumbaga mahapos na bala sa ila ang , mahapos na para sa akon, te kay may PA system man indi na mabudlay nga kumbaga ara na sa sistema namon nga kon mag-abot ang amo ni nga kalamidad bal-an na namon kon ano ang himon kag bal-an na kon diin makadto amo na bala bal-an na namon dayon kon ano ang amon obligasyon maglab-ot sa evacuation center baw natestingangan gid ang amon nga kapasidad pagsunog pero biskan ano mo gali nga damo na nga training, indi mo gid maperfect

Torreta:...ano ang mga common early warning messages nga gina-communicate sa inyo ni city? Nahambal kaina nag bagyo, flooding no, ano p agid?

Kagawad: kon sa barangay level sir, drought

Torreta: pero si city gina-inform yaman na kamo parte sa drought?

PB: huo ang sa heat index ni bala oh

Torreta: how about ang earthquake, linog?

PB: indi masyado

Kagawad: amo man diri sa aton kap kay naagyan kita sang fire

Torreta: pero gacomunicate man sila sa inyo parte ssa fire?mga fire prevention

Kagawad: ang BFP sir wala untat

Torreta: si city

PB: si city nagaremind lang gid nga amo na be maghalong, amo na ang ila nga communication kay fire prevention month peor si BFP amo na ya nag kulit naman tapos sang sini sir gin-train kami ni BFP parte sa fire. Nag-intra naman kami sa fire olympics, te nag-champion naman kami sir

Torreta: kap ini specific na ini sa pag-communicate sang early warning...how does your office communicate ang early warning system halin sa city, una sa risk knowledge sa risk assessment sa barangay...?For example flooding, paano ninyo ina ginacomunicate sa mga residents nga ina nga area flood-prone?

PB: general assembly

Torreta: ang pag-identfy man ninyo kap sang hazard-prone, risk prone area, ano ang inyo proseso? Paano kamo mag risk assessment diri sa barangay?naga-conduct kamo risk assessment?

PB: huo eh...kay sa mapa ta bala sa hazard map, may color nada sir, may color ina

Torreta: pero ang hazard map ninyo paano ninyo gin-obra?brgy officials or ginapresentar ninyo sa general assembly?

Kagawad: mag general assembly gina-flash ina sa screen te ang iban nga mga pumuluyo familair naman sa ila nga area kay dira flood prone or fire prone area sila

Torreta: pero magluwas nga ginapresent sa barangay assembly for example zone 1, flood prone so may dugang pa gid kamo nga communication sa ila like posters trumpa, may kasubong kamo nga practice sina?

PB: galing kay ang tumpa na namon general man mo

Torreta: sa observation and forecasting, so paano ninyo ginacomunicate ina? Using GC, trump, sa trump paano bay, ano ginahambal ninyo?

PB: amo na gani kon ano ang mapangayo namon sa CDRRMO nga ihatag nila kay ako nagapangayo gid ako

Torreta: may sample kamo kap?

PB: may ara sir sang sample galing daw kaluya bala nagreklamo ako kay daw k boring kag tapos damo sonata. Damo pa ang sonata sang sa hambal sang tawo te paano na be macatch ang attention sang tawo. Te nagreklamo gid ko na kay maam Donaa tapos ang ano sir ang nangita na lang gid kami galing Tagalog naman, da windi gid applicable sa amon te kinahanglan dapat tani local gid te ginapasulit sulit ina namon ya matukar

Torreta: sa response capability especially sa flood prone sa creek, for example ara na sa orange so maprepare na sila for possible evacuation, paano ninyo ina ginahambal sa ila especially kon mag red na?

PB: sila mismo bal-an nila, sila mismo nagaarak ang message sa kagawad sa BHW, sa akon gaarak na ya, "kap gataas ang tubig", Sige na bakwit na, kadto na diri". Gamontor man kami sa iya sir.

Torreta: te paano ninyo sila ginapabalo kap?

PB: gina-inform ko na si kagawad

Torreta: paano na ni kagawad gina-inform?

PB: ginakadtuan, ginasugat pa gani. Si BHW , tanod

Torreta: te may mga GC kamo, ginapost niyo man ina sa GC ninyo?

PB: huo

Kagawad: wala labot dira, giakadtuan gid ya sir kay idi man tanan maka-open dayon sa Messenger. Aware nana sila ya gapanghimos isla dayon

Torreta: ang inyo evacuation center diri kap kumusta?

PB: ang malapit diri sa barangay hall kay bal-an mana namon kon pila ka pamilya ang apektado. Tapos may ano kami, may JPT nga pavilion pero connected ina sa garden namon sa barangay, pwede siya magamit didto

Kagawad: bal-an na nila sir halimbawa lapit didto sa JPT, te didto sila makadto

Torreta: kap ano ang strategies nga gina-utilize mo sa pagcommunicate, so face to face, GC, trumpa, pubic address, ang radyo ninyo may ara mans a kada zona?

PB: wala diri lang sa barangay hall

Kagawad: kon may radyo gid man kami, ang mga tanod namon may mga raydo na sila

Torreta: pero ginagamit ninyo ina especially kon radyo for monitoring?

PB: pero sa tuod lang mas madali ang pagtawag sa cellphone

Kagawad: ang radyo nagaburot burot pa

Torreta: ...ang mga posters ya for example diri sa barnagay anyway mafall siya sa risk knowledge, si city nagahatag sa inyo tapos ginapost niyo or nagaobra man kamo sang inyo nga posters?

PB: maya ra kami kais anga gina-obra, gnapost lang namon sa Facebook tapos ang Day Care Center may ara man, ang Health Center may ara man

Torreta: pero diin halin?

PB: sa city, ginaprovide na sila

Kagawad: sa school may ara man

Torreta: ano ang medium of language nga ginagamit sa pagcmmunicate like sa poster, sa tarpaulin, sa trump

PB: Hiligaynon gid

Kagawad: kon ano ang iya ni city amo na ang IC pero sa barangay nga alert level, amo to ang yellow, orange, kag red, local gid ya

Torreta: Hiligaynon?

PB: hu

Torreta: ngaa ginatranslate ninyo in Hiligaynon?

Kagawad: kay mas hapos abi intindihon sir mo

Torreta: kon mga typhoon bulletin paano ninyo ina gina-translate?

Kagawad: sa flag hoisting may ara na da Hiligaynon

Torreta: pero wala na ina subong

Kagawad: ang nabilin sa flood nga alert level

Torreta: may specific kamo nga target audience sa inyo pag-communicate sang inyo early warning especially sa flood?

Kagawad: general

Torreta: pero didto sa creek, didto lang man kamo nagapabalo

Kagawad: hu

Torreta: ngaa kagawad nga magluwas sa general may specific pa gid kita nga pagpahibalo sa ila?

Kagawad: reminders lang sa ila kay iban kampante man mo...”ah indi nana magsaka kay ginapanilagan man nila ang flow snag tubig kay dugay na sila gaistar dira. Anad na sila makit anila ang flow snag tubig ad da wla agaw gadaludo gid , indi na sila magsaka

PB: ah okay lang kami diri kap ah

Kagawad: nagapabalo kami nga halin na kamo, pero one time may ato gid kap no

PB: nga ginsugat sang coast guard

Kagawad: indi na gid sila ka agi sir

Torreta: indi na sila ka evacuate ginrescue na sila

Kagawad: hu

PB: amo na nag kampante bala nga halin sang una amo na nag sitwasyon te daw waay bala sila nagexpect nga dasig ang pagsaka sang tubi waay sila dayon kahalin, ginsugat sila kag ginakigan. Kami ya kapila na kami mag-ano kadto diri sa barangay hall kay ang iban nagkadto na diria ang katupa dna nagkadto na pero sila yam indi...

Kagawad: wala untat nga remind

PB: nami bal-an sir nga kadtuan mo nga face-to-face gid kay ikaw mapafeel mo nga ano ka gid sa ila nga safety

Kagawad: kag gina-document ina sir once nga mag-approach sa ila ginadocument para nga at least may proof man kami

Torreata: ...kap aris pacific sa pagcommunicate sa vulnerbale sectors like senior, PWDs, youth, children, may specific kamo nga pag-communicate sa ila? Or general?

PB: general

Kagawad: pero may suvrey kami sir so maidnetify diin nga balay ang may PWD, diin nga balay ang mga senior citizen, diin nga balay ang may pregnant. So amo na ang gina-priority pirme once may information...

Torreata: for example, PWDS, may pila ka bilog ang PWDs ang ano ang disabilities?

Kagawad: sari-sari, amo na ang purpose snag tarpaulin mabasa sang pamilya nila, inkaso may bulag ang pamilya nila makabasa

Torreata: pero sa trump kap, magluwas sa recorded or canned may kahigayunan nga ikaw mismo nagahambal dira?

PB: nagahambal gid eh kaisa gani sa megaphone nagalibot ang patrol (sang barangay)

Torreata: sa flooding ina kap?

PB: huo galing kaisa nagaburot burot man

Torreata: te paano ninyo ina ginaprocess ang information, for example ote maaligmat na kamo dapat maghalin na kamo. Pano ninyo ina ginaprocess nag inforrmation?

PB: halin ina sa city tapos ginahambal lang sa simple nga paghambal kay indi mo man nga basahon kay tak-an mana sila mamati ang tanan ginaturaligmat na kay nagsaka na ang tubig, mo na ka simple

Torreata: sa mga words ya kap nga, hapos lang ya kon matranslate naton in Hiligaynon ilabi sa konteksto sang typhoon kay te may mga leveling pa, tropical storm, super typhoon, kun sa eruption. Paano ninyo gina translate ina?

Kagawad: daw wala naman kami nagamind kay mas ano kami sa flood, daw na use naman sa amo nga mga IEC dir akag ginaplay sa trump, wala na kai naga translate. Amo na ang challenge sa amon ang sa eruption kag iban pa gid Kon paano namon translate sa local language

Torreata: ginaconsider ninyo bala ang publiko sa pagproseso sang pagdevelop kag pagcommunicate sang early warning. You mentioned nga sila mismo nagapahibalo sa inyo so may participation

Kagawad: may participation gid sila y adako gid nag bulig sang mga pumuluyo sa sapa kay te although nga ginamonitor namon,, ara dira sa creek...

Torreata: ano ka importante ang ila participation nga indi lang sila beneficiary or recipient snag information?

Kagawad: dako gid nga bulig kay te sa amon mas mapahapos ang ubra kay te kon kami lang gid ya...pero syempre ang tubig galakat,,mas manaim nga sila miami gahaboy sa amon sang information, amo na bisan indi kami kalab-ot didto, makadesisyon na kami diri

PB:dako gid eh , importante gid nga may partisipasyon sila kag may ano pagulikid sa amon diir nami kay nagabulig man sila tapos nagapablo kaisa gani sila pa una gapabalo sa amon kay sila didto, sila gamonitor...

Torreta: whar are the areas for improvement for Iloilo City Government's communication of early warning system?

PB: amo gid to, ang pagpadala sang pahibalo mga reminders bala nga dapat tani daw ka catchy man bala sa pamatin-an, lip-ot pero straight to the point, lip-ot kag catchy nga daw mamati ka gid, may impact sa tagpalamati. Dapat tani tanan nga barangay hatagan kay para nga kada may kalamidad or before may calamity mag abot may ara na kami patukar para maremind ang mga tawo nga ara na sa ila paminsaron

Torreta: luwas dira kap, ano pa gid ma improve? Sa pagpati mo mas maayo bala kun istandardize ini for example tanan nga barangay may public address system? Kag mas mayao kon translated in Hiligaynon

PB: huo daw amo gid ina tani

Torreta: ngaa man?

PB: mas mahapos sa mga kapitan sa kagawad kag kinahanglan may training simplified training bala kon paano iaddress ang calamity. Daw kadamolang ngatraining ngatechnical daw indi mo man ma ano sa barangay, daw amo na bala simplified lang nga kami nga barnagay officials kay indi man tanan mga kapitan wala man may tinapusan or may pagintindi nga amo na kaano, i simplify nga para deliver nila sa tawo nila nga amo lang na kasimple oh

Torreta: nagligad nagtraining kamo sa UnRISK,...sa imo kap, ano ina kaimportane nga mga trainings kay kamo miami nagaintendify kon ano ang inyo mga hazards dira kamo mismo nagaintendify kon ano ang dapat ubrahon kag pwede maubra, ano ina kaimportante kap?

PB: importante man pero ang namean ko bala tani ginaspimple lang example ko lang ang a Boracay tam-an ka technical . Nag-attend kami sa Takas para sa paghimo sang BDRRM Plan biskan ano ka training sa Boracay, pag-abot sa barangay gaugas sila kay wala pa sila kapasa sang BDRRM plan namon kay mga sala sala kuno kay indi namon mafill-in ang mga ano ang ginapangayo nila nga dapat amo gid na maguwa. Karun gin-coaching nila kami sa Takas ginsimplify pa gid nila sa Takas amo to ya ang pinakanami ...ang nag-attend to kapitan, kagawad kag treasurer...

Torreta: kap last, sa imo pagbanta paano ni Iloilo City Government malab-ot nga mangin responsive, inclusive, kag sustainable ang early warning system ninyo?

PB: nalab-ot na pero daw wala sustainability pamatyag ko daw indi masustain ang style bala nga ato kana gulpi naman nagoya kay abi nila nakuha na sang mga abrangay. Ang isa pa gid dira naton nga lantawon may eleksyon. Syempre kon lain naman nga set sang officer syempre matraining kana naman to ang ginbayaan, for example kami ha pilot barangay ang Buntatala sa CBARAD, dapat kuntani nag nagbulos ang time nga to nga nagpilot barangay si Lovejoy to ang kapitan, dapat ang nagbulos kay Lovejoy continue niya para may sustainability kaso ang training niya indi parehas sa previous kag basi lain iya priority

Torreta: so sa ina nga political reality, paano naotn ina mangin sustainable? May kinahanglan ba nga mainstitutinaize ini tanan paagi sa mga plano

PB: yes para sa strict implementation na lang, kumbaga ara na implement ya, oblige siya nga implement para malikawan ang sulit-sulit nga mga problema..Paano siya kaimplement kon ang iya background appreciation indi bala amo na swak dira?

Torreta: kon ara sa plano, implementation na lang?

PB: for example sa akon, nagpungko ko after 6 years after kay Lovejoy, t te pilot barangay sa CBARAD, te pagpungko ko ya kumbaga bala lain naya akon priority kag kay sang time nga nagpungko ako...lain na ya ang akon. Ang akon goal naman ya mangin child-friendly barangay te BCPC ang ginsudlan ko..

Kagawad: bisan same ang mga barangay official, lain gid ya kun every year, marefresh kami kay kadamo daan sang obligasyon

Torreata: kap ano ka importante nga ginaistoryahan naton ini ang early warnings?

PB: tam-an gid ka importante, dako gid ang mabulig. Dapat ipangabuhi sang barangay ang amo sina, pati ang sa basura ini oh

END